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EXTERNAL ASSESSMENT OF INTERNATIONAL CAPACITY BUILDING PROJECTS
IN HIGHER EDUCATION:
VALUE AND EFFECTIVENESS AS PERCEIVED BY DIRECT BENEFICIARIES

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Abstract

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The objective of this study is to explore direct beneficiaries' perceptions of the value and effectiveness of external evaluations in international capacity building in higher education (ICBHE) projects. External evaluations are mandated by funding institutions for the purposes of accountability and learning, but their impact and relevance for project beneficiaries remains underexplored. This study addresses this gap by examining evaluation processes, the role of individual evaluators, and the perceptions of direct beneficiaries in two ICBHE projects.

Capacity building projects aim to effect a tangible change in the lives of specific beneficiary groups, specifically direct beneficiaries. However, there appears to be a discrepancy between the objective of capacity building projects and the evaluation method employed during the external evaluation process. Traditionally, the design and implementation of evaluation processes are undertaken by funding bodies or external evaluators. This top-down approach has the potential to relegate direct beneficiaries by failing to incorporate their perspectives and needs into the evaluation process, thereby reducing their sense of ownership over the project.

The research adopted a comparative case study methodology, focusing on two European Commission-funded projects conducted in Latin America: Fortalecimiento de las Capacidades de

Gestión de Entidades Cubanas (FORGEC) and Strengthening Impact in Latin American Universities (IMPALA). The research design is based on multiple data sources (document analysis and semi-structured interviews) to improve validity and mitigate potential confirmation bias. Key documents related to the evaluation process, including the terms of reference of the evaluation and evaluation reports were analysed. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key stakeholders, including direct beneficiaries, external evaluators and the people responsible for writing the terms of reference of the project evaluation. This approach helps to minimize the potential impact of researcher bias and provides a more comprehensive understanding of the evaluation process and how the direct beneficiaries perceive it.

This study reveals inconsistencies between the indications provided by the funding bodies and the actual evaluation process regarding beneficiaries' needs. While the European Commission advocates prioritising beneficiaries' needs during the evaluation process, this research found that the evaluation process in these two cases did not adequately consider these needs. This research underscores the importance of the external evaluator, who should have adequate knowledge of the project, the needs of the beneficiaries and also the context of the projects and the evaluation. This misalignment between the evaluation criteria and the EU's official objectives points to a potential issue in how EU-funded projects are evaluated.

By analysing actual evaluation practices in two concrete ICBHE projects, this research identifies key areas where current methodologies are not sufficiently addressing the needs and perspectives of direct beneficiaries.

The conclusions and recommendations derived from this study provide robust foundation for the refinement of evaluation methodologies. These evidence-based recommendations can

inform policy reforms and practical improvements in project evaluation, which may result in more impactful and sustainable capacity building outcomes.

Abstract (Italian)

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Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

Dedication

To my son, Jofre

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List of Abbreviations

- CAS: Complex Adaptive System
- CB: Capacity Building
- CBHE: Capacity Building in Higher Education
- CCS: Comparative Case Study
- DAC: Development Assistance Committee (OECD)
- DFID: Department of International Development, United Kingdom
- EC: European Commission
- ECB: Evaluation Capacity Building
- EFMD: European Foundation for Management Development
- ER: Evaluation Report
- EU: European Union
- FE: Final Evaluation
- FER: Final Evaluation Report
- FORGEC: Fortalecimiento de las Capacidades de Gestión de Entidades Cubanas
- HE: Higher Education
- HEIs: Higher Education Institutions
- IAF: Impact Assessment Framework
- IMPALA: Strengthening Impact in Latin American Universities
- ICBHE: International Capacity Building in Higher Education
- IHE: Institutions of Higher Education
- LFA: Logical Framework Approach

M&E: Monitoring and Evaluation

MES: Ministerio de Educación Superior de la República de Cuba

MTE: Mid-Term Evaluation

MTER: Mid-Term Evaluation Report

OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

OM: Outcome Mapping

QA: Quality Assurance

RBM: Results-Based Management

ToC: Theory of Change

ToR: Terms of Reference

UFE: Utilization-focused Evaluation

UN : United Nations

UNEG: United Nations Evaluation Group

UNDP: United Nations Development Programme

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Research Interest and The Topic

For many years, I have worked as a program manager on international capacity building in higher education (ICBHE) projects funded by various national and international institutions. Observing how some direct beneficiaries (the direct recipients of the actions) disregarded evaluation reports while others valued them led me to question: Is there a basic set of principles that all ICBHE evaluations should follow? What is the real value of these evaluations for beneficiaries? How do beneficiaries perceive the evaluations? These personal inquiries evolved into this research project, which aims to explore direct beneficiaries' perceptions regarding the value and effectiveness of external evaluations.

Through the analysis and comparison of the evaluation processes in two European Commission-funded ICBHE projects—Strengthening Impact in Latin America Universities (IMPALA) and *Fortalecimiento de las Capacidades de Gestión de Entidades Cubanas / Consolidating and Strengthening Managerial Capabilities in Cuban Entities* (FORGEC)¹—I identified how the evaluation process and subsequent reports influence the perceptions of direct beneficiaries about the value and effectiveness of such evaluations.

According to Brix (2019), defining capacity building (CB) is challenging because the concept encompasses both a process—developing or enhancing skills and competencies individually or as a group—and an outcome, where these capacities improve as a result of the

¹ Throughout this thesis, the original names of projects and institutions have been maintained in their original language. However, in certain instances where clarity for the English-speaking reader was essential, English translations have been provided alongside or in place of the original names. These translations are intended to facilitate understanding while remaining faithful to the original names.

process. The United Nations (2024) defines CB as: “the process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts, abilities, processes and resources that organizations and communities need to survive, adapt, and thrive in a fast-changing world”. The European Commission (2024b) emphasizes that capacity building in higher education (CBHE) initiatives foster international cooperation through multilateral partnerships, modernize higher education in countries not associated with the Erasmus Program, and address global challenges such as economic globalization and inequality. CBHE projects focus on individual, institutional, or national levels.

Capacity building is a central activity for many international organizations and development agencies, with substantial financial investments aimed at improving sectoral capacities—such as in higher education—through training, sharing best practices, and providing policy advice (Escarré, 2015). Although it is difficult to quantify global funding dedicated specifically to CB, the total budget for CBHE under the Erasmus+ program for 2021–2027 is €613 million (European Commission, 2024a).

CBHE projects can be considered a significant form of internationalisation in higher education (IHE), that it is closed linked to the evolution of the concept of IHE. This relationship is manifest in the definitions provided by key scholars in the field and the growing emphasis on societal impact in the context of internationalisation efforts. Knight (2015) redefines her previous concept of IHE as: “the process of integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the purpose, functions of delivery of post-secondary education” (p.2). This definition provides a basis for understanding CBHE as a way of internationalisation of higher education and fulfils Knight’s criteria as CBHE projects inherently involve international partnership and aim to integrate global perspectives into higher education institutions.

CBHE also aligns with the concept of internationalization of higher education for society (IHES), defined by Brandenburg et al. (2020) that emphasises activities that “will intentionally and purposefully seek to provide benefit to the wider community, and they will be carefully planned and evaluated and their impact on society will be visible in some way” (p. 28). This definition supports the classification of CBHE projects as a form of internationalisation, as these projects generally aim to enhance institutional capacities and foster global engagement. CBHE initiatives facilitate cross-border collaborations, knowledge exchange, and capacity development (European Commission, 2024b). These initiatives have been demonstrated to contribute to the internationalisation of higher education and to be a benefit to society (Jones et al., 2021).

The OECD (2023) defines evaluation as “the systematic and objective assessment of a planned, ongoing or completed intervention, its design, implementation and results” (p. 31). The two main purposes of evaluations are learning and accountability (European Commission, 2024; OECD, 2023). In funded projects, donors need to demonstrate, in a comprehensible manner for all stakeholders involved, the results of the investments made, and the impact of the activities conducted (OECD, 1991, p.5). Monitoring and evaluating (M&E) the activities undertaken is the only way to achieve this goal. Evaluating CB projects is often complex due to their intrinsic characteristics: the sometimes-intangible nature of their objectives and outcomes (e.g., knowledge transfer), their international scope, differences among stakeholders operating within diverse political-economic dynamics and socio-cultural contexts, and the varying needs of team members throughout the project lifecycle (Linzalone & Schiuma, 2017).

There are two main approaches to evaluating capacity-building (CB) activities. The first is based on technocratic thinking, specifically the Results-Based Management (RBM) approach, and the second is the complex adaptive system (CAS) approach (Watson, 2010). The RBM approach prioritizes strategic planning, impacts, outcomes, and outputs (UNDP,

2010). Tools commonly used in RBM include planning instruments such as logical frameworks, organizational assessment tools, and the Theory of Change (ToC) (Simister & Smith, 2010). The CAS approach encourage the adoption of more flexible evaluation methods that focus on understanding patterns and relationships rather than predefined outcomes (McEvoy et al., 2016). The CAS approach views CB as a dynamic phenomenon, with interconnected systems characterized by non-linear change, unpredictable and multiple interacting factors (McEvoy et al., 2016; Preiser et al., 2018).

Evaluations of CB projects often follow donors' specific Terms of Reference (ToR), which can be considered “the contractual between the commissioners and a consultant/evaluation team and establishes the parameters against which the success of an evaluation assignment can be assessed” (*Better Evaluation*, 2024). In CBHE projects the main aspects to be assess are the ones developed by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) Development Assistance Committee (DAC) criteria: relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability of an intervention (OECD, 2021).

When comparing the Terms of Reference (ToR) for evaluations of different ICBHE projects, one finds significant variation, depending on organization needs or the nature of the evaluation (*Better Evaluation*, 2024). However, a recurring question in relation to the ToR is whether the ToR clearly define the methodology to be used by the evaluator, or whether the evaluator could define the methodology. In the case that the methodology outlined in the ToR has been defined exclusively by the funding institution, there is a risk of promoting an evaluation approach that serves only the learning and accountability needs of the funding institution, thereby neglecting the interests of other stakeholders (in this case direct beneficiaries). Ideally, the lessons learned should inform decision-making processes for all stakeholders (OECD, 2023).

When planning the design of this research, I anticipated that the literature review would unpack relevant concepts and provide additional insights from direct beneficiaries regarding their opinions on evaluation processes and the importance they attribute to them. However, the results were not as expected. The literature review revealed a substantial body of work related to evaluation in general but offered limited insights into CBHE evaluations in the context of funded projects. While the review identified project evaluation results, only a few studies included the opinions of direct beneficiaries.

For this reason, the findings of this research contribute to addressing this identified gap. They will benefit all stakeholders involved in ICBHE projects—particularly funding institutions, implementing units, and project evaluators—by helping to identify evaluation methodologies that consider the needs of all stakeholders, especially direct beneficiaries. Understanding the beneficiaries' perceptions is crucial for improving the effectiveness and value of ICBHE evaluation projects, making this research highly relevant.

1.2 Purpose of the Study and Research Question

The aim of this study is to explore direct beneficiaries' perceptions regarding the value and effectiveness of external evaluations in ICBHE projects. Specifically, this research seeks to:

- Assess the value and effectiveness of external evaluations for direct beneficiaries.
- Examine the role of external evaluators.
- Understand how the evaluation process and reports of external evaluations influence direct beneficiaries' perceptions.
- Consider whether there are basic principles that all ICBHE evaluations should follow.

The overall research question of this study is:

- How effective is the external evaluation process of international capacity building in higher education projects in meeting the needs of the direct beneficiaries, as perceived by these beneficiaries?

The importance of this research question lies in its relevance to the necessity for evaluations that meet the expectations of both donors and direct beneficiaries, thereby contributing to the enhancement and sustainability of capacity development efforts in higher education. By emphasising the perspectives of direct beneficiaries, a more comprehensive and effective evaluation approach is proposed. This approach is imperative for the long-term success of such projects in higher education. This research question is subdivided into three sub-questions and four operational questions, which are outlined in the methodology chapter 3 (c.f. 3.1.1)

To address the research question, a comparative case study approach was adopted. Following a thorough analysis of the ToR and the external evaluation reports for both projects, a series of semi-structured interviews were conducted with a range of stakeholders, including implementing units, direct beneficiaries, and external evaluators. Despite the qualitative nature of the research, a quantitative methodology was applied to analyse the ToR (using the Q-ToR checklist) (c.f. Appendix 1) and the evaluation reports (a meta-analysis using the EV-Form) (c.f. Appendix 2). The results of these analyses provided answers to the sub-questions and the overarching research question.

1.3 Dissertation structure

This research is organized into eight chapters. Following this introductory chapter, which offers an overview of the dissertation, the subsequent chapters are structured as follows:

Chapter 2 reviews the relevant literature and establishes the theoretical framework underpinning this research. This chapter integrates key concepts critical to this research:

capacity building, stakeholders, evaluation, meta-evaluation, value and evaluation, and effectiveness and evaluation. The theoretical framework of this research is developed by exploring agency theory applied to ICBHE projects but other complementary theories, such as stakeholder theory in the context of program evaluation theory, and context-focus evaluation have been considered. Finally, the chapter discusses the methodological implications of these theories for this research.

Chapter 3 outlines the research design and methodology employed, detailing the research question, sub-questions, and operational questions. It also describes the case studies presented and the documentation analysed, alongside the limitations and ethical considerations of the study.

Chapter 4 is dedicated to the FORGEC case study, including its description and an analysis of the ToR and the mid-term and final evaluation reports. The perceptions of direct beneficiaries were analysed through semi-structured interviews with participants from the Universidad de La Habana and Universidad de Camagüey (both Cuban universities).

Chapter 5 focuses on the IMPALA case study. This chapter follows a structure similar to Chapter Five to facilitate comparative analysis in the subsequent chapter. The direct beneficiaries participating in the IMPALA case study were from the Universidad Agraria de la Habana (Cuba) and Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá (Colombia).

Chapter 6 provides a comparative analysis of the findings from both cases. The comparisons include: (1) the ToR of two evaluations, (2) the evaluation reports, and (3) the analysis of the direct beneficiaries' perceptions, considering roles and locations.

Chapter 7 discusses the findings of the study, addressing the sub-questions and operational questions. These findings are discussed in relation to the existing literature and the methodology employed, including its limitations.

Chapter 8 concludes the study by providing a comprehensive answer to the overarching research question posed in the introduction. The chapter synthesizes the findings and offers implications and recommendations for policy and practice, as well as suggestions for future research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Introduction

The objective of this chapter is to provide a comprehensive review of relevant literature and establish the theoretical framework underpinning this study. The structure of this chapter moves from a broad theoretical framework to a more specific aspects related to the research, from the literature review to the theoretical framework. The chapter is divided in two main sections, and it concludes by summarizing key points, reiterating the importance of the theoretical framework, and providing a transition to the next chapter.

In the first section, the literature review, the following logic order was applied to introduce the different concepts and theories.

First, the theoretical foundations of CB are presented, from its historical context and diverse dimensions to its specific application in HE projects, thereby establishing a robust foundation for understanding the concept and the type cases of this research.

Second, the stakeholders theory, is introduced to understand the power dynamics in the context of ICBHE projects.

The third point is the most extensive, as it constitutes the principal aspect of the research: evaluation. It provides a comprehensive overview of the evaluation process, beginning with definitions and purposes and progressing to types, theories, methodologies, as well as its practical aspects and connections CB. This approach offers a detailed exploration of the evaluation process within the context of the study.

The fourth point is related to advance concepts (meta-evaluation, value and effectiveness) which examines critical aspects (quality and impact) of evaluation practices and theory.

The second section focuses on the agency theory as it is the theoretical framework of this research.

Both sections end with a conclusion that summarises the key points which provide a foundation for the research methodology and findings.

The methodology I applied to my literature review was an exploratory scoping review. This method was chosen due to the scarcity of literature on specific aspects relevant to my research. I consulted “Web of Science”. The keywords used were “capacity building,” “evaluation,” “stakeholder engagement,” “value,” “effectiveness,” and “higher education projects.” The results revealed a substantial amount of literature on capacity building, with fewer results related to the concept of evaluation. The number of relevant sources continued to decrease when I focused on the intersection of these concepts. When adding keywords such as stakeholders, value, or effectiveness, the number of entries was even more limited. An analysis of the articles found shows that the voices of stakeholders or direct beneficiaries are not present in most studies; rather, these articles primarily discuss project outcomes or general theories.

Table 1

Selected Literature. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Step	Description	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Initial search	Conducted a broad search in “Web of Science” database using the key words: “capacity building”, “evaluation”, “stakeholder engagement”, “value”, “effectiveness” and “higher education”	Period: Articles and studies written between 2000 to 2024. Articles or studies discussing any of the key words in the context of higher education, capacity building or evaluation	Articles or studies unrelated to capacity building, evaluation or higher education
Filter by intersections	Focused on the intersection of multiple keyword	Articles or studies exploring minimum 2 key concepts (e.g.	Articles or studies focusing only on general theories or

	(e.g. “capacity building” and “evaluation” and “higher education”	“capacity building” and “evaluation” or “evaluation” and “higher education”	projects outcomes without conceptual intersections
Refine by stakeholders focus	Narrowed search results to include articles or studies that mentioned stakeholder engagement, direct stakeholders, or beneficiaries	Articles or studies that include stakeholders voice or direct beneficiaries in higher education context	Articles or studies that do not mention stakeholders’ involvement or only discuss theoretical frameworks
Assess for Specific Values	Further refined results using keywords like “value” or “effectiveness” in conjunction with previous criteria.	Articles or studies evaluating capacity building or higher education projects with specific outcomes related to value or effectiveness	Articles or studies lacking a measurable or evaluative perspective on value, effectiveness, or stakeholder involvement
Final Selection	Reviewed selected articles and studies to ensure relevance to the exploratory scoping review on capacity building and evaluation in higher education.	Articles or studies providing unique insights into the intersection of capacity building, evaluation, and higher education projects	Duplicates, unrelated fields (e.g., not specific to higher education), or articles without clear methodological contribution.

Source: Authors' creation

2.1.2 Theoretical Foundations of Capacity Building

2.1.2.1 Historical Context and Evolution

The concept of capacity building (CB) is not new and has evolved over time.

According to Kühl (2009), CB emerged from various concepts and approaches dating back to the 1950s, with the introduction of “institution building programs”. These programs aimed to strengthen governmental infrastructure in post-colonial states. Over time, these approaches evolved: in the 1960s, the focus was on institutional development (enhancing the abilities of the public organizations in developing countries to manage essential government functions); in the 1970s, on human resource development (focus on the individual potential and actions); and in the 1980s, on new institutionalism (that focuses on how economic and political conditions

affect and interact with organisations and institutions) (Kühl, 2009). By the 1990s, a comprehensive concept of CB emerged, integrating all previous ideas to strengthen capacities at the individual, institutional, and systemic levels, while considering the economic, social, and political context of all stakeholders (Ceccon & Cetto, 2003). CB is now a key element in most development programs (Craig, 2010). However, there is no universally accepted definition, and the concept is often too broad to be practical in many cases (Potter & Brough, 2004). Additionally, some authors define CB as the process by which individuals, organisations and communities acquire and develop the skills, knowledge, and resources needed to improve their performance and address challenges (Groot & van der Molen, 2000). This approach is particularly pertinent in the context of higher education (HE), where institutions seek to adapt to a constantly changing environment and improve their effectiveness. In summary, while there are many slightly different definitions of CB, I use the definition by Groot & van der Molen (2000) as it emphasizes the development of skills, knowledge and resources, which is particularly relevant in the context of HE as well as the definition of Enemark & Williamson (2004) that stress the idea of contextualization of the different activities of CB.

Table 2 below presents a comparative overview of how major donors and organizations define CB, reflecting the diverse perspectives and emphases of different organisations. It illustrates the evolution of the concept of CB (focus on narrow technical assistance) to capacity development (a more integrated approach that considers socio-political and organizational factors).

Table 2

Definitions of Capacity Building by Major Aid Donors and Organizations (Direct Quotes)

Organization	Definition of Capacity Building
UNDP (2009)	“A process that supports only the initial stages of building or creating capacities and assumes that there are no existing capacities to start from” (p.3).
World Bank (2009)	“Capacity development (or capacity building) is a locally driven process of learning by leaders, coalitions, and other agents of change that brings about changes in socio-political, policy-related, and organizational factors to enhance local ownership for and the effectiveness and efficiency of efforts to achieve a development goal” (p.3).
OECD (2008)	“Means by which skills, experience, technical and management capacity are developed within an organizational structure (contractors, consultants or contracting agencies) - often through the provision of technical assistance, short/long-term training, and specialist inputs (e.g., computer systems). The process may involve the development of human, material and financial resources” (p.62).
UNITED NATIONS (2024)	“The process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts, abilities, processes and resources that organizations and communities need to survive, adapt, and thrive in a fast-changing world” (Capacity-Building United Nations).
European Commission	The European Commission adopts the OECD (2006) definition of capacity development: “the process whereby people, organisations and society as a whole unleash, strengthen, create, adapt and maintain capacity over time” (p.9).

DFID (2010, pp. 5-6) outlines the principles of good CB: “Conceive CB as a process; strengthen existing processes; ensuring full local ownership; role of external expertise (mentoring and joint processes); a different way of working (implication of the organization and the team); skills and resources (they need to be in place); group development and partnership and collaboration”.

Cunningham (2020) highlights the importance of collaboration in CB, learning from past challenges, and investing in human capital to foster sustainable development in communities or organizations. Lee & Kuzhabekova (2019) suggest that the local environment and cultural differences are essential considerations in CB interventions and, recommend that interventions be adapted to the local cultural context for better effectiveness and sustainability. Sometimes the terms capacity building (CB) and capacity development (CD) are used interchangeably, but there are sometimes differences between the way the two concepts are

used. For example, the OECD (2006, p. 9) defines CD as “the process whereby people, organisations and society as a whole unleash, strengthen, create, adapt, and maintain capacity over time. The phrase capacity development is used advisedly in preference to traditional capacity building.” The OECD prefers the term CD over CB because CD implies a process of change, whereas CB suggests the non-recognition of existing capacity where the action takes place and the failure of capacity. However, many agencies, including the European Commission (EC), continue to use the term CB in their documents or calls for proposals, although EC to define CB borrows the OECD’s definition of CD.

According to McEvoy et al. (2016), the change in language also suggests a shift in ‘donors’ political positions: from an instrumentalist view of capacity as a means to fill skills gaps to the injection of transferred knowledge, particularly technical and scientific skills. In Figure 1, I can see how CB is distinguished from technical assistance and is considered the step before CD, indicating that the two concepts have different meanings and implications. In the framework of CB and CD, technical assistance is seen as a short-term, donor-driven effort that generally provides technical skills without considering the developing country context (Wilson, 2007). I have used the term CB instead of CD in this study, firstly because it is the term used in the two cases of this study and secondly because the EC uses this term in its calls.

Figure 1

Capacity Progression

Source: McEvoy et al. (2016)

There are several different approaches that can be taken with regard to capacity building (CB) projects. Traditional CB projects are typically structured around training, workshops, technical advice, and project management support. However, more sophisticated capacity development (CD) projects require deeper forms of stakeholder engagement and dialogue, such as knowledge brokering, networking, change and process facilitation, mediation, and leadership development. This requires an effective and dynamic relationship between the many actors involved (Datta et al., 2012; Ika & Donnelly, 2017).

Furthermore, the distinction between CB and CD can be further delineated by the different expectations associated with short- and long-term outcomes. Thus, CB is linked to increased skills and knowledge, whereas CD is linked to changing organisational, systemic or structural performance, thus focusing on continuous learning and adaptation rather than short-term interventions (OECD, 2006; McEvoy et al., 2016).

The concept of CB has been criticized by numerous scholars for its association with short-term actions that lack long-term sustainability, a criticism that has received considerable attention in academic discourse. Other researchers, such as Vincent-Lancrin (2007), note that CB is about sustainable development, takes a long-term rather than short-term perspective, and strives to address the shortcomings of traditional donor projects. As far as the European

Commission (EC) is concerned, the sustainability of CB activities depends on several factors, including that they are designed and implemented with a view to achieving specific results, and are limited in time, budget, and staff. In addition, structural impediments that may affect individual projects must also be considered (Edmunds et al., 2018).

As evidenced in the literature, CB projects have encountered significant problems in achieving their objectives despite the considerable resources and effort devoted to them. The success or failure of a CB project can be attributed to different factors such as clear donor and government policy, and strong local ownership of the project (Edmunds et al., 2018; European Commission, 2011; Ika & Donnelly, 2017). In the absence of a clearly defined project, success is inherently challenging. Success is typically measured in terms of the project owner's strategic organizational goals and objectives, as well as the satisfaction of users' and stakeholders' needs in relation to the project's final product.

As stated in the *EU Capacity Development Toolkit for Capacity Development* (European Commission, 2011) projects need to be owned by those seeking to develop their capacity. Consequently, donors must ensure at the beginning of the project that the beneficiaries have an interest in the CB project and that all results, including the necessary knowledge, are transferred to them at the end of the project (Baccarini, 1996; Bayiley & Teklu, 2016).

The *EU Capacity Development Toolkit for Capacity Development* (European Commission, 2011) highlights one of the fundamental principles of successful capacity building: the importance of ensuring that beneficiaries take ownership of projects. This concept of local ownership is crucial for the long-term sustainability of a project, as it aligns the development process with the interests, needs and aspirations of the beneficiaries themselves. Without local ownership, the likelihood of CB projects succeeding over time is significantly reduced (Edmunds et al., 2018). The toolkit emphasises that donors need to

ensure the active participation of beneficiaries from the beginning of the project to ensure that interventions are appropriately contextualised and adapted to the local environment.

The role of beneficiaries cannot be underestimated at any stage of a project. Their involvement from the outset of a project can facilitate active participation in its implementation and foster a sense of ownership of its outcomes. Their ownership is based on their participation in all phases of the project, from planning to evaluation. This involvement ensures that the project is not just an external imposition but is tailored to the needs and objectives of the beneficiaries. This approach is especially important in international development projects. According to Chambers (1997), a lack of beneficiary involvement can lead to projects that are disconnected from beneficiaries' needs, resulting in poor outcomes and unsustainable impacts.

Baccarini (1996) stresses that the sustainability of a project, once the donor's involvement has come to an end, depends on whether the beneficiaries have the necessary skills and knowledge to continue their work. This concept of 'capacity transfer' involves not only the acquisition of the necessary knowledge, but also the ability to apply this knowledge to local systems and practices, so that it can be maintained and expanded independently over time. Consequently, the knowledge transferred during a capacity-building project becomes not a temporary intervention but a catalyst for sustainable development (Lusthaus et al., 1999).

Bayiley & Teklu (2016) go further to suggest that "capacity transfer" in capacity building is a complex, dynamic and iterative process that requires careful planning and an understanding of the local context. Beneficiaries must be able to understand and adapt the knowledge, as well as apply it effectively in their daily work. This requires an integration of formal and informal learning methods. Training sessions (formal knowledge) should be accompanied by opportunities for informal learning, such as mentoring, practical applications in their work or solving real-life problems. By combining these approaches, the project

becomes more relevant and better adapted to local contexts, increasing the likelihood that the knowledge will be assimilated and used effectively (Engel, 2007).

According to the European Commission (2011), effective knowledge transfer is a deliberate and planned process which occurs throughout the project lifecycle. It encompasses activities as capacity-building workshops, coaching and the establishment of knowledge management systems, the function of which is to document and preserve lessons learned. The transfer process should not be rushed and should be structured in a manner which fosters deeper understanding and ownership. A successful execution of this process enables the beneficiaries to adapt and continue developing the skills and knowledge gained during the project without external support, thereby ensuring the project's sustainability.

The Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness (OECD, 2005), and the Accra Agenda for Actions (OECD, 2008) also emphasize the principles of country ownership and alignment with national priorities in relation to capacity transfer. These principles emphasize the need for projects to be aligned with the goals of the recipient and for mutual accountability between donors and recipients (OECD, 2005). In practice, this means that donors must invest time and resources in understanding the local context to ensure that capacity-building initiatives are both relevant and feasible within the local institutional context.

Capacity building initiatives are only successful when beneficiaries take ownership and knowledge is transferred effectively. Planning, commitment and a partnership between donors and recipients are essential. It is a long process, so the beneficiaries must invest in the project and maintain knowledge after the donors have left. The adaptability and sustainability beyond the end of donor involvement also depends on national and environmental factors that also play a critical role in determining the success of CB projects. According to Cedergren & Hassel (2024); Khan & Spang, (2011), the creation of adaptive organizational capacity enables

institutions to respond effectively to crises and unexpected changes that contributes to the success of the project.

To implement successful CB, a comprehensive approach is necessary. In addition to the development of technical competencies, this approach should also aim to create an environment that encourages learning and collaboration (Lennie et al., 2015). However, it is important to recognise that the capacity-building process is not without challenges. Resistance to change, lack of resources, and the diversity of interests among stakeholders can hinder the effective implementation of strategies. It is therefore essential to adopt a flexible and adaptive approach that allows organisations to adjust their strategies as needed.

CB is also described by some authors (Brown et al., 2001; Horton et al., 2003; Merino & Carmenado, 2012) as an abstract and multidimensional concept that can follow either a top-down (external intervention based on financial and physical resources provision and technology transfer) or a bottom-up approach (a process of change discussion). In the case of capacity building in higher education European Union (EU) projects, both approaches can apply (Jongsma, 2016).

Whereas a project is an indivisible operation defined by a specific schedule and budget. Typically, it is managed by a single operator. Consequently, programmes consist of projects that adopt a similar approach within a predefined framework.

In conclusion, capacity building is a multidimensional process that encompasses individual, organisational, and systemic development. Each of these levels is interdependent and contributes to the overall strengthening of capacities within the educational context and beyond. Holistic consideration of these dimensions can yield substantial benefits in terms of the efficacy and sustainability of implemented projects and initiatives.

Considering all the above, in this research I consider CB as a complex and multidimensional process, requiring clear definition, local ownership, environmental

adaptability and a focus on sustainability. Furthermore, the evaluation of such projects should include some of the elements described above. By addressing these elements, CB initiatives can achieve significant and lasting impacts at individual, organisational and systemic levels.

2.1.2.2 Dimensions of Capacity Building

In the context of this research, the different dimensions of CB are of particular significance because they provide a comprehensive framework of how CB operates at different interdependent levels. A more accurate assessment can be made in relation to direct beneficiaries' perception of value and effectiveness of the evaluation. Direct beneficiaries can enhance their competences through CB initiatives, but this improvement is also shaped by organisational support systems and external factors (policies or regulations). Evaluations that avoid these factors can be seen as incomplete and could impact on direct beneficiaries' perceptions of the project and the evaluation.

In their 2004 study, Potter & Brough introduce a systemic approach to CB, which they define as a hierarchy of nine interdependent components across four tiers: structures, systems, and roles; staff and facilities; skills; and tools. This framework aims to improve project design, monitoring, and resource allocation. According to DFID (2010) and UNDP (2008), CB operates at three different levels of intervention, and their interdependence defines the framework (planning and evaluation) of the program or action and its success.

- Individual level: Training, experience, motivation, and incentives enhance individual skills, knowledge, and performance. This approach recognises that the success of any initiative largely depends on the ability of individuals to perform their roles effectively.
- Organizational level: Improves organizational performance through strategic planning, partnerships, leadership skills, and organisational systems.
Organisational capacity is strengthened when institutions establish effective

knowledge management systems, promote the active participation of their members, and cultivate a culture that values evaluation and feedback.

- **Systemic / Enabling environment:** Establishes and implements effective policy framework that considers interrelated economic, political, environmental, and social factors. This level recognises that institutions operate within a broader context, which includes government policies, legal regulations, and social dynamics. To achieve true capacity building, it is necessary to consider how these external factors influence organisational and individual capacity

2.1.2.3 Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE)

Higher education plays a pivotal role in the development of skilled human capabilities and supports research and policy at all levels because higher education institutions offer specialized training in different fields (Chan, 2016), undertake research and innovation which will contribute to the society (Varriale et al., 2023) and has policy influence (Hassock & Hill, 2022).

The primary objectives of higher education (HE) are to ensure the quality of learning through teaching, to enable students to acquire the latest knowledge through exploratory research, and to sustain the development of society through service (Xing & Marwala, 2017). In addition to enhancing individual capabilities, higher education fosters heightened awareness in a variety of areas, including health, socio-economic and political understanding, societal contribution, peace, and enhanced life satisfaction (Umapathi & Venkatramana, 2015) that contributes to the creation of healthier communities, informed citizens, active engagement, peace and stability, economic prosperity, and overall improved well-being.

We must also consider the relationship between education and economic growth. Capacity building (CB) in education has both economic and social implications, as education is seen as an important driver of economic growth and the competitiveness of a region or

country (Holland et al., 2013; Merino & Carmenado, 2012). According to Temple (2003), education policy should be prioritized when it is seen as a determinant of a country's growth. Sustainable economic growth depends on the potential of human capital. Through higher education, a country produces a skilled workforce and builds the capacity to generate knowledge and innovation, which increases productivity and economic growth.

According to Ndaruhutse & Thompson (2016), universities should be recognized not only for their long-term contribution to the economic growth of a region or country but also for the impact they have directly on graduates in developing countries (related to health, gender equality, and democracy), as well as for strengthening the institutions to which they belong and training professionals needed in sectors such as education and health.

European CBHE projects, such as those being investigated in this study, aim to enhance the quality, relevance, and responsiveness of HE (Tsirakidis, 2021). These projects can be more successful if they clearly define their objectives, have committed leadership, and possess specialized skills in project management (Lumato & Issa, 2023). During the evaluation of these projects, it is crucial to analyse these aspects, as they will influence direct beneficiaries' perceptions of the project's value and effectiveness.

According to various authors (Escarré, 2015; Vincent-Lancrin, 2007), CBHE interventions can be distinguished at three different levels: micro-level (individual: acquisition of skills through formal education or other forms of learning and scholarships/grants), meso-level (organizational: improvement of domestic educational institutions, curricular reform, and governance reforms), and macro-level (societal: HE national system and global: the international context in which the country operates).

According to Jongsma (2016), EU CBHE is conceived through programs or projects² supporting the modernization, accessibility, and internationalization of the higher education sector in a beneficiary country through various actions that improve the quality of HE and enhance its relevance for the labour market and society. These projects aim to improve the level of competences and skills in HE institutions by developing new and innovative education programs, enhance the management, governance, and innovation capacities of HE institutions, and increase the capacities of national authorities to modernize their HE systems by supporting the definition, implementation, and monitoring of reform policies. Additionally, they foster regional integration and cooperation across different regions of the world through joint initiatives, sharing good practices, and cooperation.

In conclusion, HE contributes to the wider society in different ways such as economic growth, societal well-being, through research, and policy influence. The specific focus of CBHE projects is on particular aspects of the HE (e.g. in this research in the FORGEC project on knowledge transfer in relation to improving the efficiency of Cuban companies, and the IMPALA project on measuring the impact of third mission activities of institutions of higher education (IHE)). In summary, CBHEs provide a tangible and beneficial contribution to the development of skills and knowledge within the HE environment, thereby contributing to the wider societal good.

² In this research, the terms "programme" and "project" are sometimes used in an indistinct manner, although they possess different characteristics. According to the Evaluation Methods for the European Union's External Assistance (European Commission, 2006) a programme can be defined as a set of simple, homogeneous interventions grouped together to achieve global objectives. A project is an indivisible operation defined by a specific schedule and budget. Typically, it is managed by a single operator. Consequently, programmes consist of projects that adopt a similar approach within a predefined framework.

2.1.2.4 International Capacity Building in Higher Education Projects: Power and Participation

ICBHE projects enhance higher education systems in developing countries. This improvement is achieved by fostering global academic partnerships, modernising educational policies and strengthening institutional capacities. However, ICBHE projects success depends on the local ownership of the project, a factor that is intrinsic linked to power imbalances within the North-South partnership, integrating both Northern theoretical knowledge and Southern contextual insights.

According to the European Commission (2020) CBHE projects also help participating institutions in developing countries at different levels: a) International (projects foster the establishment of collaborative networks, enhancing institutions to engage in global academic partnerships and knowledge exchange); b) National (projects foster the modernization and reform of HE systems, thus they influence the national policies related to HE and contribute to the overall development of the country's educational landscape) and c) Domestic or Local (institutions increase their visibility outside their area of influence, establish cooperative links with non-academic sectors, thus increasing the impact of such a project and also developing personal skills of academics and administrative staff). The importance of ICBHE projects lies in the long-term structural effect they have in these countries.

In the two cases of this research, academics develop management functions and assume an administrative role in the project, and the staff involved develop their intercultural competencies by being part of a multinational consortium where countries from regions beyond their own are represented. Both cases demonstrate an aspiration to exert an influence at the national level. FORGEC aims to enhance the efficiency of Cuban companies, while IMPALA seeks to improve the quality mechanisms of universities in three countries and establish a reference framework for measuring the impact of third mission activities. This

national impact can also become international in the medium/long term, as the improvement of the economy of Cuban companies can make them internationally competitive (in the case of FORGEC) and as the quality referential (and the tools on how to do it) for impact measurement can be replicated in other countries with similar contexts (un the case of IMPALA).

The field of ICBHE has attracted growing attention in recent years, as universities are increasingly seen as essential players in addressing global challenges and advancing inclusive development (Chankseliani & McCowan, 2021). Nonetheless, scholars have pointed out that the practices and underlying assumptions of capacity-building initiatives in HE can sometimes reflect the lingering influence of colonial systems and power dynamics (Morreira et al., 2020).

During the 1950s and 1960s, the USA and later European countries began to support HE and research in many of the world's low-income developing countries. The motivations for such support were diverse, including counteracting communist influence in some regions and compensating for the colonial occupation these countries had suffered and its consequences (Girgis, 2007; Hydén, 2016). Thus, paternalism and patronage based on neo-colonial structures can be seen in this North-South relationship: the weaker partner is perceived as needing guidance and help from the stronger (Dannecker, 2020; Ishengoma, 2016). The Northern partner (generally considered the “donor” or “sponsor”) acts as a tutor assisting and supporting Southern partners (local actors, the recipients) in developing their skills (Bernstein & Van der Ven, 2017).

According to Marginson & van der Wende (2007), for decades, concepts, scientific knowledge, and educational methodology have been transferred from the North to the South, and scientific “quality” has been judged according to so-called global standards, Dannecker (2020) argues that the European Commission (EC) through its CBHE projects shares knowledge, skills and resources from the Global North to the Global South based on their own

cultural and institutional perspectives. These global standards are based on Northern knowledge and, as a result, are considered superior to those produced in the South (Girvan, 2007).

According to Vann & Ziguras (2017), recipient developing countries generally have fragile economies and depend on external assistance not only to reform but also to sustain their overall education systems. In this context, ICBHE is a means of developing robust national higher education institutions, although financial benefits are often seen as a primary factor for the recipient developing countries as these countries benefit from external financial assistance that helps them to sustain and reform their education systems and improve infrastructures, resources and capabilities (Bradley, 2008). North-South partnerships can also be viewed as opportunities to raise their profiles (Dannecker, 2020) as Northern institutions increase global competitiveness and visibility in the global education market and the Southern institutions increase reputation and credibility not only at the national level but also internationally.

Examining why donors support higher education through CB projects in developing countries reveals multiple motivations such as enhance the economic growth, societal and socioeconomic development of the recipient countries (Holland et al., 2013; Ndaruhutse & Thompson, 2016; Temple, 2003) For instance, the European Commission (2020) views international cooperation in HE as an effective tool for enhancing the EU's public diplomacy and supporting policies in areas such as development, migration, and intercultural dialogue.

However, in the past, Northern partners often dictated agendas, methodologies, and budget allocations (Jamil & Haque, 2016; Vann & Ziguras, 2017), leading to challenges in achieving their objectives. Literature indicates that North-South relationships have evolved from donor-recipient models to partnerships with shared ownership and decision-making (Asanova, 2006; Edmunds et al., 2018; Girgis, 2007; Nossun, 2016). Concepts such as power,

knowledge (and experience), and ownership should be revisited, as they are key to the success of North-South CB projects and, by extension, ICBHE projects.

According to Girgis (2007), power is essential in CB projects to overcome external challenges, and developers cannot carry out capacity building without empowerment. However, the perceptions of power that donors and recipients hold can affect their relationship. Donors may perceive themselves as more powerful due to their role in decision-making, budget control, and management of funds, as well as their knowledge, experience, and status as outsiders. However, CB projects are based on specific objectives: local needs must be assessed by practitioners (staff employed by donors), and this assessment is sometimes done superficially, with insufficient empirical support or disregard for local circumstances and knowledge (Edmunds et al., 2018; Girgis, 2007; Vann & Ziguras, 2017). Additionally, practitioners often have short-term contracts and fixed project deadlines, which limit the development of expertise with local partners. On the other hand, local partners may also perceive donors as powerful mainly for economic reasons: those who control the funds also control decision-making and knowledge.

The transfer of knowledge between the North to the South is crucial to success of CBHE initiatives, traditionally the North contribute with theoretical knowledge, but the knowledge of the South also needs to be considered as they have the vision and knowledge of the context and the practical insight. This exchange of knowledge helps the South to improve their capacities but enrich the North with new perspectives and approaches, creating not only impact during the project or at the individual level but also sustainable and effective partnerships that contribute not only to address South development but also global knowledge production (Barasa et al., 2023; Färnman et al., 2016).

According to Edmunds et al. (2018), one of the major problems lies in local ownership. Donors need to transfer their theoretical commitments and persuade recipients to accept their

way of thinking and support their programs on those terms. Depending on the degree of ownership, the recipients' commitment (the final aim of the CB project) may be short-lived. The degree of local ownership could be increased if local partners were involved in the entire project process, including planning, implementation, coordination, and evaluation. To improve "local" ownership practitioners' relationships with local partners should change; they should develop constructive personal relationships aimed at building capacity collaboratively. Practitioners not only recognize the alternative knowledge of local partners but also supplement it with external knowledge. Certain instruments (negotiation, suggestive dialogue, and helping) and capacities (sensitivity, creativity, commitment, and shared understanding) are needed to achieve this (Girgis, 2007).

According to Aga et al. (2018), ownership also implies that beneficiaries can transform the knowledge acquired through the project into sustainable practices within their specific contexts. This is especially relevant in externally funded projects, where there may be a disconnect between funders' expectations and beneficiaries' actual needs (Regeer et al., 2016).

Decolonial theorists have criticized how HE institutions and curricula often prioritize Eurocentric knowledge systems, marginalizing perspectives from the Global South (Morreira et al., 2020). This critique has inspired calls to redefine the mission of universities, shifting from a narrow focus on human capital and modernization to a broader role in fostering intellectual curiosity and promoting inclusive societies (Fregoso & De Lissovoy, 2019; Morreira et al., 2020).

Some capacity-building collaborations between universities continue to reflect colonial power dynamics in knowledge production (Adriansen & Madsen, 2019). To improve outcomes, recommendations include clarifying responsibilities, improving fund allocation, and decentralizing tasks (Lumato & Issa, 2023). Addressing colonial influences is crucial for decolonizing CB projects and supporting equitable partnerships in HE (Adriansen & Madsen,

2019). Overall, CBHE projects are vital for modernizing HE systems and fostering international cooperation. Many scholars argue that North-South relations grounded in equal partnership, mutual respect, shared ownership, and decision-making can transform previously unequal relationships (Jamil & Haque, 2016; Nossun, 2016).

The power relations between the North and South and the concept of ownership that leads to the establishment of a continuous cycle of learning are relevant concepts in my research. According to the reviewed literature, ownership and in consequence the active involvement of beneficiaries in the evaluation process are crucial for two reasons. First, it can improve the quality of the evaluation by incorporate local insights and perspectives. Second, it ensures that the interventions are relevant, context-sensitive and effective. This approach can enable educational institutions to recognise the importance of empowerment and active participation of direct beneficiaries, leading to more meaningful and sustainable outcomes in CB projects.

2.1.3 Stakeholders Theory

2.1.3.1 Key Concepts

In the context of this research, stakeholders' theory is important because it helps us to see the power dynamics between all the stakeholders of ICBHE, considering that direct beneficiaries are considered key stakeholders in CBHE projects, as their perceptions of the effectiveness and value of the final evaluations are critical to the project's success (Roche, 1999; Rossi et al., 2003). According to Freeman (1984), "[a] stakeholder in an organization is any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization's objectives" (p. 46). The Project Management Institute (2021), in its latest review of the *Project Management Book of Knowledge* (PMBOK) guide, defines stakeholders as "an individual, group, or organization that may affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by a decision, activity, or outcome of a project, program, or portfolio" (p. 250). Thus, while the

main idea of being affected is consistent, the latter definition pertains to projects or programs, emphasizing stakeholders as participants in these initiatives (Pirozzi, 2019) and is particularly relevant in the context of CB projects (Eskerod et al., 2015; Freeman, 1984).

According to Freeman et al. (2018), stakeholders are individuals or groups who have an interest in the outcome of an action or decision. This implies that evaluations should be designed to measure outcomes and to consider the needs and expectations of these groups. It is crucial to recognise that beneficiaries are not merely passive recipients of information; they must be seen as the "owners" of the evaluation process. Involving beneficiaries in the evaluation stages encourages a sense of ownership and responsibility, leading to greater utilization of the results (Cousins & Earl, 1995).

Stakeholder theory is considered to have originated with Freeman's publication of *Strategic Management*. This theory is based on the active participation of all stakeholders in the decision-making process regarding the results and outcomes to be achieved by an organization. It is not only morally correct to understand how stakeholders will be affected by activities but also strategically beneficial to do so. Thus, stakeholders not only contribute ideas but can also influence the formulation of policies and the implementation of set objectives and goals (Karimi et al., 2021; Schnure, 2016). This approach aligns with the idea that evaluations should be relevant and useful to those they directly affect. Stakeholder theory also suggests that the active participation of beneficiaries can improve the quality of the evaluation process. Including their perspectives and experiences provides a more complete and nuanced view of project impact (Tantalo & Priem, 2016). This is particularly important in contexts where educational interventions are externally funded, as there can be a disconnect between what funders consider success and what benefits, in this case, direct beneficiaries.

Stakeholder theory can be categorized as normative (why stakeholders' interests should be considered), instrumental (the effect stakeholders have on organizational performance), and

descriptive (examining whether stakeholder interests are considered by a firm (Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Freeman, 2004; Pirozzi, 2019; Schnure, 2016). Stakeholder theory is widely used by policymakers, development agencies, and academics.

Identifying stakeholders' expectations and their roles throughout the project process is both essential and necessary to ensure project success because it contributes to a more equitable, effective and sustainable process, as it prevents power imbalances while promoting ownership and empowerment among beneficiaries, facilitate effective communication and enhance evaluation relevance and usefulness (Derakhshan et al., 2019; Pirozzi, 2019; Simister & Smith, 2010). Stakeholders generally have control over project information and resources. This control empowers them and can influence the project's perceived outcomes (Karlsen, 2002). Therefore, stakeholders influence should be considered essential to the project success because of their critical role (Amadi et al., 2018; Rajablu et al., 2014). However, stakeholders often have differing interests, priorities, and levels of influence, which can lead to different priorities and potential conflicts (Karlsen, 2002).

A central aspect of this research is the concept of ownership by direct beneficiaries. Within the context of stakeholder theory, ownership translates into the capacity of beneficiaries to actively participate in the design and evaluation of projects, influence decision-making, and appropriate and transform the knowledge and capacities developed (Fetterman et al., 2014; Fetterman, 1994). This approach implies that direct beneficiaries are not merely recipients of information but should be considered active participants in the evaluation process. The active participation of beneficiaries is essential to ensure that evaluations are relevant and useful, reflecting their specific realities and needs (Smithers, 2011).

As emphasised by Brugha & Varvasovszky (2000), stakeholder analysis is a political and social process that goes beyond the simple identification of actors. This analysis involves understanding power relations, interests, and influence, which is crucial for mobilising

resources and capacities within the educational context. The capacity of beneficiaries to influence the evaluation process is also related to their level of empowerment. When beneficiaries feel they have a voice in the process, they are more likely to take ownership of the results and engage with the actions resulting from the evaluation (Chambers, 1997; Rossi et al., 2003).

Stakeholders can be classified using analysis techniques and categorized from different perspectives. Mitchell et al. (1997) propose a series of characteristics to evaluate potential stakeholders based on their power, legitimacy, and urgency, distinguishing seven different types of stakeholders. Other authors include additional concepts for classification, such as importance, attitude, or impact (Sperry & Jetter, 2019). Some distinctions are simpler, classifying stakeholders as internal or primary stakeholders and external stakeholders (Newcombe, 2003; Winch, 2007; Yamasaki & Gnanaratnam, 2014). Generally, internal or primary stakeholders are formal members of the project and generally support the project, as they are entrusted with resources to achieve its objectives. External stakeholders are not formal members of the project but may affect or be affected by it and may not necessarily support it. In this context, non-business stakeholders or secondary stakeholders are classified as external stakeholders (Cova & Salle, 2005; Harrison & St. John, 1996; Project Management Institute, 2021). Their goals may be more financial, utilitarian, and long-term oriented (Mahr, et al., 2013).

2.1.3.2 Application of Stakeholders Theory in International Capacity Building in Higher Education Projects

Stakeholder theory can be applied to projects, as, despite the differences in goals, objectives, outcomes, and costs, the concept of project stakeholders remains relevant. The idea of project stakeholders has evolved over time from including only those directly involved in a

project to encompassing all groups that have a role or interest in, or may be affected by, the objectives and implementation of a program or project (Pirozzi, 2019).

According to Asiyai (2014), Campbell & Rozsnyai (2002), and Stensaker et al. (2016), stakeholders in higher education (HE) can be classified as internal and external. Despite the fact that the terms “internal” and “external” are identical to those employed in the stakeholders theory classification, the terms bear different meaning. In this research, I adopt the classification and definition of HE as a point of reference for the discussion of these terms. Internal stakeholders include all groups within the higher education system (e.g., the government as the provider of higher education services, students, academics, higher education administrators, and non-academic staff) who are interested in and committed to the quality of education provided to students and the standard of outcomes. External stakeholders are represented by society as a whole and by groups not included as internal stakeholders (e.g., non-governmental organizations, civil society organizations, the private sector, parents, and local or international development agencies).

However, this distinction changes when discussing ICBHE projects. In this context, as in international development projects, three key stakeholder groups can be distinguished: donors, the implementing unit, and beneficiaries (Julian, 2016; Khang & Moe, 2008).

Donors include governments, multilateral agencies, and international foundations. As they provide the financial contribution to the project, they hold overarching power and set strategic objectives, even though they do not directly utilize the project outputs. Donor institutions also establish guidelines for how project evaluations should be conducted.

The implementing unit³ are usually national or international organizations capable of managing multiple projects simultaneously, often as consortia of other higher education institutions. They are responsible for carrying out specific tasks and activities within the project. Some key roles and responsibilities of the implementing unit are project coordination, tasks management, communication, monitoring and evaluation, financial management and reporting. The implementing unit is responsible for maintaining a clear audit trail throughout the project implementation cycle and for providing project information to other stakeholders. The implementing unit oversees the project and must meet both local needs and donor criteria. This unit ensures that the project objectives are met effectively and efficiently.

Beneficiaries are those stakeholders who directly experience the changes resulting from the intervention or project. They can be divided into two categories: direct beneficiaries and indirect beneficiaries. Direct beneficiaries can be split into institutions and individuals. Institutions are the higher education organisations that are the primary recipients and implementers of the project's activities and outcomes. Individuals are the people whose lives (both personal and professional) are directly impacted by their participation in capacity-building projects. They are also tasked with transferring their knowledge and expertise to their own societies. Indirect beneficiaries are members of society who benefit from the project's results through the actions and knowledge shared by direct beneficiaries.

Figure 2

Stakeholders in International Capacity Building in Higher Education Projects

³ In CBHE sometimes the term implementing unit also is referred as legal beneficiaries as they are the recipients of the project funds.

Source: Authors' creation

In this research, I have identified the different stakeholders in both cases (c.f. Figure 5 and Figure 6) and have examined the extent to which direct beneficiaries are involved in the evaluation process.

The stakeholders theory in this study explains the power relations between the different stakeholders, making possible the identification of the direct beneficiaries' expectations and needs, understand the different levels of participation and influence, and analyse the perceived value of evaluations from multiple perspectives. However, implementing stakeholder theory presents a few challenges. One of the main obstacles is the precise identification of all pertinent direct beneficiaries and their interests. Furthermore, there can be considerable discrepancies between the expectations and needs articulated by different groups, rendering the evaluation process more intricate. It is therefore vital to establish effective communication channels and participatory mechanisms to ensure that all voices are heard.

Stakeholder theory offers a valuable framework for understanding and evaluating capacity-building projects in higher education. Considering all stakeholders allows for a more comprehensive and meaningful evaluation, which measures results and contributes to continuous organisational learning facilitates learning. The involvement of direct beneficiaries improves the quality of the evaluation process and ensures that interventions are relevant and effective for whom they are intended to benefit.

2.1.4 Evaluation

2.1.4.1 Evaluation: Definition and Purpose

The word “evaluation” originates from the Latin word “*valere*” (meaning “to be strong or of value”). In the 17th century, the word “*évaluer*” was already in use in France, meaning “to assess the value.” The Latin prefix “ex” was introduced, becoming “è.” Understanding its etymology helps clarify its meaning.

According to Brown et al. (2015), evaluation can be defined as “the holistic assessment of an event through the utilization of a broad range of measures and approaches to determine its value and impacts in an agreed or prescribed context” (p. 136). Evaluation refers to a systematic inquiry that provides a basis for decision-making about a program’s merit, worth, or significance (Al Hudib, 2018).

Evaluation is the most common method to assess and analyse the effectiveness of an activity and provides feedback (Britton, 2010; Norton et al., 2016; Vallejo & Wehn, 2016). The OECD (2023) defines evaluation as the “systematic and objective assessment of a planned, ongoing or completed intervention, its design, implementation and results” (p. 31). Based on this definition, the European Commission (2024) assesses the performance of different types of initiatives, including interventions (projects and programmes) (p. 3). Therefore, I had used this definition throughout this research, although the basis of my study is much more linked to the main purposes of evaluation in relation to the perceptions of direct beneficiaries.

According to Morkel & Ramasobama, (2017), the recognition that development projects need to be informed by strong evidence has led to increased capacity building in monitoring and evaluation (M&E) and the way of performing it (Cavens, 2019). While M&E are often mentioned together, they do not have the same meaning but can be complementary and follow similar steps. Evaluation is periodic while monitoring is continuous. Evaluation is

performed after a project or program is completed, with its ultimate goal being to inform strategic decisions and improve future initiatives. Monitoring, on the other hand, involves the ongoing collection of data on specified indicators to track project progress, and this data is then used for evaluation (UNDP, 2002).

Evaluation also involves formulating judgments about impact and progress, with results used to refine and improve future projects or programs (Fine et al., 2000). In the context of international development programs, evaluation provides accountability to donor constituents and beneficiaries by assessing a program's effectiveness and efficiency. For donors, evaluation demonstrates how resources have been utilized and whether the program has achieved its intended objectives. The evaluation process ensures donors and stakeholders that resources have been used in a responsible and effective way. Accountability is also important for direct beneficiaries to know if resources have been spent on meeting their needs. This transparency also helps to avoid conflicts between donors and beneficiaries (Akanpabada et al., 2016; OECD, 1991). For beneficiaries, evaluation ensures that their needs are met and that the program is efficient and impactful. Thus, the evaluation process involves assessing effectiveness (the ability to achieve the desired outcomes) and efficiency (how resources have been used to achieve the outcomes) (OECD, 1991). Evaluations provide insights into the effectiveness (or lack thereof) of a program, identifying what works and what does not. This information can inform the design of future programs (OECD, 1991; Vallejo & Wehn, 2016). However, establishing and evaluating the relationship between skills development and financial investments can be challenging (Blume et al., 2010).

The latest European Commission Evaluation Handbook (2024) outlines two main purposes of evaluations: learning and accountability. By identifying what works and what doesn't in different situations, learning helps to improve decision-making and institutional

memory. Accountability ensures that work is done to agreed standards and that results are accurately reported. This leads to more timely and informed decisions (p. 3).

2.1.4.2 Types of Evaluations

Evaluations can be categorised according to several aspects. In the context of this research, the moment at which the evaluations were conducted is of particular significance, as is the actors responsible for conducting them.

In relation to time, we can distinguish between evaluations undertaken:

a) *Before the project*: to assess the context, the needs of the beneficiaries and to assess that the design of the project fulfils that needs (Vallejo & Wehn, 2016);

b) *During the project (mid-term evaluations)* to assess the progress of the project and identify possible improvements after evaluating what works and what does not (Rossi et al., 2003);

c) *After the project (final evaluation)* to evaluate if the project has achieved its goals and provide accountability to the stakeholders and inform future projects (OECD, 1991)

In relation to the actors that carry out the evaluation we can distinguish between internal and external evaluations.

The goal of the internal evaluation of a project is to assess what works and what does not, for whom, and to determine whether changes should be made to advance the project's objectives of equity and excellence (Education Review Office, 2016). This type of evaluation is useful for mid-term evaluations, where the focus is on improving the project during its implementation. When conducted properly, internal evaluation aligns organizational processes with the strategic goals of the organization. The OECD (2023) defines internal evaluation as: "Evaluation of an intervention conducted by a unit or individuals internal to the organisation, generally staff of the organisation who report to the management" (p. 39). These types of evaluations are typically carried out by an employee of the same company or organization

where the evaluation is being performed (Mertens & Wilson, 2019). In project settings, it is generally conducted by a senior staff member who analyses data and explains results, which are typically not shared outside the organization (Brown et al., 2015). Internal evaluators, working within a familiar environment, may have been involved in some parts of the program, which can be seen as either an advantage or a disadvantage depending on the circumstances (Weiss, 1972).

The primary purpose of external evaluation is to assess a program or action by analysing and interpreting the results to aid grantees and donors in planning and decision-making. This process allows evaluators to make recommendations for future improvements (Rutnik & Campbell, 2002). These types of evaluations are essential for final assessment of a project, where the focus is on evaluating its overall impact and outcomes. According to the OECD (2023) external evaluation is “the evaluation of an intervention conducted by entities or individuals outside the funding and implementing organisations” (p. 32). These types of evaluations are generally performed by independent evaluators who must remain separate from operational management to ensure freedom and independence. This separation is crucial to obtaining accurate results without stakeholder influence (Perrin, 2019). Independence in evaluation is essential as a lack of it can lead to issues such as coercion, biased decision-making, unethical evaluations, and pursuing vested interests. A common challenge is the pressure evaluators may face from management or stakeholders to misrepresent findings (Pleger et al., 2017). On the other hand, maintaining independence helps eliminate biases and enhances objectivity. As Perrin (2019) notes, independence is as central to the credibility of evaluation as it is to audit, an essential aspect of monitoring & evaluation (M&E).

Regardless of when and by whom is conducting the evaluation, it is essential to consider the context. Environmental and systematic factors that can modify in a substantial

way the inputs of the program, as its implementation and outputs. Thus, can affect the accuracy and relevance of the evaluation findings.

The OECD *Quality Standards for Development Evaluation* (OECD, 2010) and the United Nations Evaluation Group's *Handbook for Conducting Evaluations of Normative Work in the UN System* (UNEG, 2014) emphasize the importance of considering contextual elements when conducting evaluations. Literature suggests that the contextual elements of a program must be defined at the beginning of the evaluation design, as environmental factors can influence not only the inputs of the program but also its implementation and outcomes (Cavens, 2019; Chen, 2005; Conner et al., 2012; Fitzpatrick, 2012; Milzow et al., 2019; Weiss, 1998).

2.1.4.3 Evaluation Theories

Program Evaluation Theory. It focuses on the methods and approaches used to evaluate the effectiveness of various interventions and programmes (Rogers et al., 2000; Weiss, 1972). This theory has evolved over time, incorporating different perspectives and methodologies that allow for a deeper understanding of how the outcomes and impacts of programmes can be measured in specific contexts, such as capacity building in higher education.

An important approach within this theory is theory-based evaluation, which seeks to establish a link between the outcomes of a programme and the underlying theories that support it (Fitz-Gibbon & Morris, 1996). According to Dahler-Larsen (2018), this approach addresses the ambiguity inherent in many programmes and considers Janus *variables*—factors that may have multiple interpretations and effects. This theoretical framework highlights the necessity of understanding both *what* is measured and *how* and *why* it affects outcomes. The application of this approach enables evaluators to more effectively identify the mechanisms that contribute to the success or failure of a programme.

Program evaluation theory offers a valuable framework for understanding and evaluating capacity-building projects in higher education. Through the integration of both theory-based and participatory evaluation methods, a more comprehensive and meaningful evaluation can be achieved as it measures outcomes and contributes to continuous organisational learning.

Participatory Evaluation has emerged as a prominent approach in recent years as an effective way to involve beneficiaries and other stakeholders in the evaluation process (Cousins & Earl, 1992, Morris, 2002, Rutnik & Campbell, 2002). King (2005) defines participatory evaluation as “an overarching term for any evaluation approach that involves program staff or participants actively in decision-making and other activities related to the planning and implementation of evaluation studies” (p. 291). According to Tapella et al. (2021), an evaluation can be considered participatory “when those involved in the project define what will be evaluated, with what objectives, when it will take place, what data collection and analysis methods will be used and how the results will be communicated” (p. 22).

The inclusion of stakeholders in evaluation can be beneficial but also challenging. Some authors argue that involving stakeholders can introduce bias, as stakeholders may influence results (Mercier, 1997; O’Brecht, 1992; Orr, 2010). To avoid undue influence from certain stakeholders, equity in involvement is essential (Brandon, 1998). However, organizations like the Joint Committee on Standards for Educational Evaluation and the UNDP (2017) contend that stakeholder participation ensures not only learning and sustainability of results but also ownership. According to the literature (Bryson et al., 2011; Pahl-Wostl, 2002; Paneque et al., 2009), stakeholder engagement in the evaluation process can make results more credible and valuable, and some authors (Karimi et al., 2021; Odera, 2021) link this to improved project effectiveness. Several authors emphasize involving stakeholders

at the early stages of the evaluation process, particularly at the planning stage (Chen et al., 2024; Espinosa-Fajardo et al., 2024; Morkel & Mangwiro, 2019).

This methodology is not merely concerned with measuring results but also with capturing the added value that comes from the active participation of stakeholders. As Odera (2021) points out, participatory evaluation allows evaluators to gain a richer and more nuanced understanding of programme impact while fostering a sense of ownership among participants.

Utilization-Focused Evaluation, developed by Patton, emphasises the importance of designing evaluations with a clear purpose: to ensure that the results are used by relevant stakeholders. According to Patton (1997), an evaluation is considered successful if its findings are used by those who have the power to make decisions. This approach implies that evaluations should focus on the needs and interests of direct beneficiaries, increasing the likelihood that these results will be perceived as valuable and applied in future decisions.

The effective implementation of UFE requires the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the design of the evaluation process and the assurance of their access to the results and recommendations. This may include creating accessible reports and presentations tailored to different audiences within the stakeholder group (Patton et al., 2016). Doing so ensures that the information is understandable and relevant to each stakeholder group, facilitating the effective utilisation of the findings.

A key aspect of UFE is the clear identification of the primary users of the evaluation at the beginning of the process. This allows evaluators to align their methods and approaches with the specific expectations and needs of these users. The active involvement of stakeholders in all stages of the evaluation process has the dual benefit of increasing the quality of the evaluation and fostering a sense of ownership over the results. This, in turn, motivates beneficiaries to implement the recommendations derived from the evaluation.

In addition, UFE promotes inherent flexibility in the design and conduct of evaluations. This means that evaluators must be willing to adapt their approaches according to the contextual and social dynamics present in the project environment. Adaptability is essential to respond to the changing needs of users and to address any challenges that may arise during the evaluation process.

UFE also focuses on creating an environment conducive to organisational learning. The involvement of beneficiaries in the process encourages a culture of reflection and critical analysis, which can facilitate continuous improvements in practice. This is particularly important in educational contexts, where the ability to learn from experiences is fundamental to sustainable development.

Context-Focused Evaluation. Contextualisation is a critical element in the evaluation of capacity-building projects (Enemark & Williamson, 2004). Each intervention must be analysed considering socio-cultural particularities, specific institutional conditions, and contextual constraints and opportunities. This perspective is fundamental, as capacity-building projects do not operate in isolation; they are immersed in social, political, and economic contexts that influence their design, implementation, and outcomes (Ferraz da Silva, 2022; McNeil & Woolcock, 2004).

According to Fowler (2000), the success of capacity-building projects depends critically on their ability to adapt and respond to local dynamics. This implies that evaluations should be sensitive to the unique characteristics of each context, allowing for the identification not only of challenges but also of opportunities that can be exploited to improve project effectiveness.

Context-focused evaluation also involves engaging local actors in the evaluation process. Beneficiaries' participation provides a valuable source of information about the environment, while also fostering a sense of ownership over the process and the results. When

direct beneficiaries are included in the evaluation, their local knowledge becomes an essential resource for identifying specific needs and priorities. This is particularly pertinent in contexts where interventions are externally funded; the inclusion of local voices can help ensure that project objectives are aligned with community expectations and realities.

Moreover, contextualisation allows for the recognition of interactions between disparate levels of capacity: individual, organisational and systemic. Consequently, an effective evaluation needs to consider how these levels interrelate and influence each other.

The ability to adapt to specific contexts is also related to the long-term sustainability of capacity-building projects. Interventions perceived as relevant and useful by beneficiaries are more likely to be sustained once external funding ends. This highlights the importance of designing evaluations that measure immediate outcomes and consider the long-term impact on the community.

Given the focus of this research, these theories cannot be overstated. These theories provide a general framework for designing and conducting evaluations that are more inclusive, contextually relevant and useful for all stakeholders, not just beneficiaries. By applying these approaches, evaluation results can be more robust, meaningful and impactful of CBHE projects. By involving direct beneficiaries from the outset, evaluations can better reflect the realities of project implementation as well as the needs and expectations of beneficiaries and can lead to more accurate findings and more effective recommendations for improvement. This inclusive approach enhances the validity and reliability of the evaluation and promotes ownership and sustainability of the project outcomes among the beneficiaries.

On the other hand, the exclusion of direct beneficiaries in the drafting of ToR has significant implications. Without their participation, evaluations may not fully reflect their needs and realities, thus reducing the ownership, relevance and effectiveness of evaluation results for beneficiaries. However, the implementation of these theories is challenging, due to

the complexity of CBHE programs and potential conflict among stakeholders. Additionally, ensuring meaningful participation of all stakeholders can be complicated by differences in interests and expectations. It is therefore essential to establish a clear framework for communication and collaboration among them.

In conclusion, the literature seems to suggest that the integration of these evaluation theories is essential for conducting comprehensive and meaningful evaluations. However, the exclusion of direct beneficiaries in the drafting of the ToR undermines the effectiveness of these methodologies. To enhance the value and impact of evaluations in CBHE funded projects, it is necessary to involve direct beneficiaries from the outset, ensuring that their perspectives and needs are adequately represented and addressed.

2.1.4.3 Key Evaluation Methodologies

The methodology used by the evaluator will depend not only on the contracting authority but also on the type of program (sector, project) being evaluated (*Better Evaluation*, 2024). There are various types of evaluations based on timing, who conducts the evaluation, and the techniques or methods used (e.g., process, impact, outcomes, summative, formative, internal, external, participatory, case-based evaluation), making evaluation methods customizable (Kabeyi, 2019). Under some basic premises, the methodology to be used will be specified in the specific ToR; in other cases, it will be proposed by the evaluator (European Commission, 2019; *Better Evaluation*, 2024). There is a wide variety of approaches, including quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods. The most used evaluation methods are described below.

OECD/DAC Criteria. The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, through its Development Assistance Committee, identified five evaluation criteria: relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability (OECD, 1991). More recently, the OECD (2019) reviewed these criteria and added a new one: coherence. The OECD/DAC criteria are

now widely used in the evaluation of funded programs and projects. According to Bartlett (2016), these criteria provide a framework for evaluations but do not specify the methods by which a program or project can be evaluated against each criterion. Programs funded by the EC follow the DAC evaluation criteria, which are closely linked to the program's logframe.

Figure 3

Logical Framework Hierarchy of Objectives and the Related Evaluation Criteria

Source: PCM 2004

Results-Based Management Approach (RBM). The (OECD, 2002) defines the RBM approach as “a management strategy focusing on performance and achievement of outputs, outcomes, and impacts” (p. 33). Based on these definitions, inputs (human and financial resources) are required to produce outputs (actions and activities in the short term), which subsequently generate outcomes in the short or medium term and, ultimately, long-term impacts. According to Bhattarai (2020), RBM emphasizes defining expected results, engaging key stakeholders, evaluating risks that may influence or modify these results, monitoring programs through appropriate indicators, and reporting on performance “. This result chain is at the core of this process.

Logical Framework Approach (LFA). The European Commission (2005) defines LFA as “an analytical and management tool which is now used (in one form or another) by most multilateral and bilateral aid agencies, international NGOs, and many partner governments”. LFA is based on the development of a matrix that enables project designers to list planned project objectives, outputs, and activities, often with expected outcomes and impacts, on one axis, and to identify relevant objectively verifiable indicators of progress, means of verification, and important assumptions or risks on the other axis (Cracknell, 1996; European Commission, 2005). A framework matrix summarizes and analyses qualitative data in a table of rows and columns. According to Bartlett (2016), LFA is often used to report progress and achievements to project funders, and evaluators can use it to assess program or project achievements through verifiable indicators. The logframe provides a convenient overview of the main features of an intervention, as well as the information needed for monitoring and evaluation (Better Evaluation, 2024).

Theory of Change (ToC). According to (UNEG, 2014), a ToC is a model that explains how an intervention is expected to lead to intended or observed impacts. Its main aim is to explain how a specific intervention leads to increased capacities, with assumptions included to clarify the connections between outcomes and expectations (Kruse & Forss, 2014, cited in Escarré, 2015). A good ToC outlines how a program or intervention is understood to work. It acts as a roadmap, facilitating better planning and providing a comprehensive view of how elements are linked and how change is occurring. It also assists in assessing progress toward the long-term achievement of objectives (Karimi et al., 2021). According to Rogers (2004), a ToC should combine information and processes. The absence of a ToC in a program or project can negatively impact the ability to monitor, evaluate, and report on project results, as aspects of the project design structure may be overlooked (Kabeyi, 2019).

2.1.4.4 Terms of Reference of the Evaluation

To conduct a high-quality project evaluation, it is essential to have a precise, accurate, and well-specified Terms of Reference (ToR) for the evaluation (European Commission, 2014; Kabeyi, 2019). The prescriptive nature of the ToR guides the entire evaluation process and ensures that all the aspects of the project have been carefully considered and clearly outlined. Within the EC, “the ToR is the key document in the evaluation process, as it defines all aspects of how an evaluation will be conducted” (European Commission, 2014, p. 2).

Most project funding organizations have their own guidelines on how to write ToRs for an evaluation. The donors or the implementing unit draft specific ToRs for the evaluation (either mid-term or final), as well as for the project audit. These ToRs form the basis for the external evaluator’s work and establish the selection criteria for hiring an evaluator (*Better Evaluation*, 2024). To write a ToR, the project logframe is often considered, as it provides all the information related to the project and a framework for evaluation: results and objectives, indicators and types of verification to measure results, and the key assumptions of the project (European Integration Office, 2011). ToRs may be created at the start of the project, but in some cases, they are developed a few months before the evaluation. Sometimes a single ToR may cover both mid-term and final evaluations.

ToRs can vary depending on the organization, project type, or required evaluation. According to Roberts et al.(2011), ToRs should generally cover four key areas: definition and function (“why do the evaluation”), content (“what are we evaluating”), preparation (“how are we evaluating”), and process (“how will the evaluation be managed”). These areas may be presented in different formats. According to the European Commission (2014) the ToR should capture “the evaluation mandate for the evaluation team that will carry it out, including the context of the evaluation, the work to be performed by the evaluators and its structuring, any

specific methodological requirements any necessary expertise required of the evaluation team, key deadlines and deliverables and further elements” (p. 162)

Several authors and as well as institutions as the EC or the OECD advocate for the participation of stakeholders, including beneficiaries, in the moment of drafting the ToR. Authors such Derakhshan et al., (2019); Pirozzi, (2019); Roberts et al.,(2011); Simister & Smith, (2010); Vallejo & Wehn, (2016) have emphasised that the involvement of stakeholders, in concrete beneficiaries, in early stages of the evaluation process (the drafting of the ToR) is crucial to ensure the relevance and the alignment of the evaluation with to local needs and priorities. This approach promotes transparency, ownership and the alignment between project objectives and evaluation goals. Patton (1997) suggest in his utilization-focused evaluation framework that evaluations are more effective when stakeholders (including beneficiaries) are involved in defining the purpose, scope and questions of the evaluation and this scope augments the probability of using the findings and being context-specific. Funding institutions as the EC or the World Bank and organizations as the OECD also supports the idea of consultation of the stakeholders in the evaluation process. The EC, in its *Toolbox for Capacity Development* (2011), emphasis that stakeholder consultation enhances evaluation relevance and ensures practical results focusing on significant issues for direct beneficiaries fostering ownership and accountability. The OECD, in its *Quality Standards for Development Evaluation* (2010), corroborates this perspective, asserting that stakeholder’s participation during the ToR formulation enhances the clarity, credibility, and usefulness of evaluations, while fostering trust and mutual accountability. The World Bank, has a similar approach, emphasizing that participatory evaluations improve the alignment of evaluation objectives with the needs of beneficiaries and strengthen the overall impact of CB projects (World Bank, 2007). These perspectives emphasise the importance of engaging beneficiaries in the ToR

drafting process to guarantee that evaluations are inclusive, effective, and meaningful for all the stakeholders.

According to the European Commission (2014), the content and format for a ToR will vary based on legal and administrative requirements, local practices, and the type of tasks. The ToR may range from a prescriptive list of tasks and operations to a flexible document indicating the general approach and methods for data collection and analysis. However, ToRs should be as concise as possible, providing the evaluator with all necessary information. A typical length is 5-10 pages, excluding administrative annexes that may accompany the core ToR to facilitate the evaluator's work. These annexes may include a list of documents to be consulted, data on the intervention to be evaluated, and a code of conduct, among other things.

2.1.4.5 Building Capacity in Evaluation

The focus of this research is on CBHE projects and their evaluations. Depending on how the beneficiaries of such projects perceive the value and effectiveness of evaluations, their results will be embedded in their institutions and sustained over time. Conducting evaluations also involves building capacity within the institutions and ensuring that evaluation becomes an integral part of the organisational culture and that these practices are sustained beyond specific projects.

The term evaluation capacity building (ECB) is defined differently by various authors. Some definitions focus on the organizational level (Beere, 2005; Preskill & Boyle, 2008). Others incorporate both the individual and organizational levels, such as (Labin et al., 2012), who “define ECB as “an intentional process designed to increase individual motivation, knowledge, and skills, thereby enhancing a group or organization’s ability to conduct or utilize evaluation” (p. 2). Frey (2018) described ECB as “an approach used to help people learn how to conduct an evaluation and think evaluatively in the process” (p. 626), emphasizing the process itself.

ECB has gained increasing attention in recent years as the demand for program results grows. A review of the literature revealed that ECB is a field of growing interest, with an increasing number of studies due to funders (donors, government agencies, and others) requiring information on the effectiveness of different approaches and the reasons behind these outcomes (Faulk & Stewart, 2017; Norton et al., 2016; Vallejo & Wehn, 2016). Given the rising demand for financial justifications of projects or programs, it is expected that organizations managing such projects, as well as governments and assisting agencies, will demonstrate transparency. ECB aims to modify individual services or programs for optimal delivery and to support higher-level policy decisions (Naccarella et al., 2007).

ECB frameworks address both the capacity to conduct and the capacity to use evaluations, with implications for integrating evaluation into organizational culture (Cousins et al., 2014). Additionally, literature identifies the primary elements contributing to the success of ECB, which includes the rationale for ECB (circumstances and needs), content and methodology (activities, processes, structures, resources), and resulting outcomes (Labin et al., 2012; Norton et al., 2016; Volkov & King, 2007). A recent study by Bourgeois et al. (2023) emphasized the value of learning from past ECB initiatives to enhance future outcomes in evaluation capacity building.

The ECB methodology can vary based on the programs being assessed. The focus of an evaluation depends on the program's purpose and its relevance to stakeholders. However, it is not always straightforward to attribute ECB outcomes to specific inputs due to the influence of other factors (DFID, 2010). Additionally, efforts often centre on general capacity building rather than the specific outcomes of these efforts (Faulk & Stewart, 2017). As ECB evolves, there is an increasing need for standardized measures, robust research designs, and systematic reporting to strengthen ECB practices and achieve both capacity-building and programmatic objectives (Labin et al., 2012).

In this research I adopt a blended definition: on the one hand, there is Labin et al.'s concept of deliberate processes of capacity development at both the individual and organisational levels, and on the other hand, there is Frey's approach to evaluative thinking and in-process learning. My suggested definition is: ECB can be defined as an intentional process designed to facilitate the acquisition of skills and knowledge in the conduct of evaluations and the application of evaluative thinking. The purpose of this process is to enhance individual motivation, knowledge and skills, thereby increasing a group or organisation's ability to conduct, utilise and integrate evaluation into their institutional culture.

This highlights both the practical and participatory dimensions of CBD, establishing how evaluations can empower beneficiaries and lead to meaningful and sustained use of evaluation results in institutional contexts.

2.1.4.6 Evaluation of International Capacity Building in Higher Education

The most common approaches for evaluating ICBHE are the DAC criteria, the LFA, and ToC. Funding agencies and stakeholders recognize the advantages of using the LFA (Bakewell & Garbutt, 2005). However, some authors criticize it for its assumption of linear, causal chains that may overlook the influence of the broader environment (Taylor & Ortiz, 2008) and for not adequately reflecting the multidimensionality of capacity development (McEvoy et al., 2016). According to (Simister & Smith, 2010), outcome mapping (OM), has several technical advantages over the LFA as a planning and reporting tool for general capacity-building work. According to (Earl et al., 2001) OM focuses on behavioural changes in individuals, groups, or organizations directly influenced by a program, rather than just measuring results against predetermined indicators. Bartlett (2016) argues that while the LFA can assist in evaluating achievements and impacts, it cannot determine the relative success of a project or explain why results were achieved.

The involvement of stakeholders throughout the CBHE evaluation process should be considered and consultant or other type of interactions with stakeholders should be done (Roberts et al., 2011). Context also plays an essential role, and the effectiveness of CBHE evaluations depends on the context in which the evaluation is conducted. The evaluation context includes different factors unique to each institution/region, including cultural, political, economic and social elements. This influences how projects are implemented and evaluated. For example, governance structures, funding mechanisms, educational priorities, historical background, local power dynamics and existing institutional capacities. Contextual needs to be known and considered when designing and conducting evaluations to ensure the relevance, significance and ability to accurately measure CBHE initiatives' impact. (Al Hudib & Cousins, 2022a; Edmunds et al., 2018; Minamoto & Nagao, 2006). Moreover, the context of different stakeholders significantly influences the evaluation process and its outcomes. Stakeholders (donors and beneficiaries) can have different perspectives and priorities to the evaluation. Their varied contexts can affect how evaluations are perceived, utilized, and implemented (Morkel & Mangwiro, 2019). For example, the interest of donors can focus on tangible short-term results while beneficiaries can be more interested in long-term investment effects and developmental impact (Minamoto & Nagao, 2006). These contextual factors highlight the importance of adopting adaptive and flexible approaches to CBHE evaluations that can respond to the complex and dynamic environments in which they operate (Al Hudib & Cousins, 2022). Achieving transformational changes and outcomes within a required time frame is often challenging due to the initial level of the capacities targeted for improvement (Edmunds et al., 2018).

2.1.5 *Meta-evaluation*

A fundamental component of the research process entails the meticulous examination of the evaluation reports (interim and final) of the two case studies (c.f. 3.4.2). I systematically assess the quality and completeness of these evaluation reports, examining processes, methodology and adherence to specific criteria. using a structured form with specific questions (EV-Form). Therefore, a meta-evaluation is carried out when analysing the evaluation reports.

Meta-evaluation, or “the evaluation of evaluations” (Scriven, 1991), has many definitions. Some authors describe it as an instrument used to aggregate findings from a series of individual evaluations (Stufflebeam, 2000), while others view it as a systematic tool for quality control, ensuring adherence to established good practices in evaluation (Lamont, 2012; Reboloso et al., 2001). According to (Stufflebeam, 2001) meta-evaluations benefit society by ensuring the integrity and credibility of evaluations. They assure users that the assessment results they receive are relevant, reliable, and unbiased. Meta-evaluation does not focus on the results of the evaluation but on the process by which it was conducted, serving as a quality control mechanism (Bustelo, 2002) and helping organizations improve their evaluations (Qian-Khoo et al., 2022). It also provides evaluators with feedback on their work to ensure quality and make improvements as needed (Stufflebeam, 2000). While not all evaluations require meta-evaluation’, it is recommended to enhance evaluators’ practice (Fitzpatrick et al., 2011).

According to Bustelo (2002), we can classify meta evaluation in four ways:

According to its role: Meta-evaluation can be formative or summative. Formative meta-evaluation aims to improve and ensure the quality of evaluation practice (Harnar et al., 2020), although not all evaluators adopt this approach (Patton, 2018). Generally, formative meta-evaluations are generally internal and inform ongoing evaluations before the summative meta-evaluation (Harnar et al., 2020). They are essential for a successful summative meta-evaluation (Stufflebeam, 1981). In the case of summative meta-evaluation provides

information related to strengths and weaknesses and is the most common type (Cooksy & Caracelli, 2009).

According to timing: when it is done: Meta-evaluations can be conducted before the end of the action to assist evaluators (formative) or post facto—after the completion of the evaluation—to provide feedback to stakeholders once the evaluation is fully completed (Stufflebeam & Shinkfield, 2007). Post facto meta-evaluations may face financial challenges, as funding is often unavailable after the project is finished (Hanssen et al., 2008).

According to the agent: If the same evaluator conducts the meta-evaluation, it is referred to as an internal meta-evaluation. If, on the other hand, it is carried out by another evaluator, it is called an external meta-evaluation. According to Patton (1997), both methods can be combined, allowing the evaluator to conduct the meta-evaluation themselves, which is then reviewed by another evaluator to enhance the credibility of the evaluation methods used.

According to the content: If the focus is on the design, context, or structure of the evaluation, it is referred to as a design meta-evaluation. If the evaluator analyses how the evaluation was conducted, it is called a process meta-evaluation. If the analysis pertains to outcomes or outputs, it is called a result meta-evaluation.

To conduct a meta-evaluation, the process should include (among other steps) the following: create the evaluation team, confirm the meta-evaluation standards, collect and review all relevant information related to the “evaluation subject” (if necessary, the evaluator can collect new information through on-site interviews, observations, or surveys), analyse all the information to assess the previous evaluation, and document the findings (Stufflebeam, 2000).

Standards and criteria are used to analyse all collected information. Several guidelines outline different evaluation standards, such as those by the Joint Committee on Standards for Educational Evaluation (JCSEE), the African Evaluation Association (AfrEA) Standards, the

German Gesellschaft für Evaluation e.V. (DeGEval), the Swiss Evaluation Society (SEVAL), the United Nations Evaluation Group, and the Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD).

The aim of these standards is to ensure and promote the quality of evaluations (Montrosse-Moorhead & Griffith, 2017). The context (national or local) and the objective must be considered for their implementation (OECD, 2010). Stufflebeam (1974) outlined eleven criteria based on technical adequacy, usefulness, and efficiency, which are widely accepted in research. According to Leslie et al. (2014), there are two different models of standards: the quality criteria-based approach (e.g., the JCSEE Program Evaluation Standards, which include utility, feasibility, propriety, accuracy, and evaluation accountability (Yarbrough et al., 2011) or the functional phase-based approach (e.g., the OECD DAC criteria: relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability (OECD, 2019). Cooksy & Caracelli (2009) note that the criteria and methodology used in meta-evaluation are interrelated and depend on the type of meta-evaluation and the aspects being assessed.

According to Oliver (2009), meta-evaluation assesses the effectiveness of an evaluation based on one of four different functions: assessing the value of a program or policy, serving as a mechanism for improvement, contributing to knowledge (research), or guiding the further development of a policy or program (Mark et al., 2000).

Considering the different functions of meta-evaluation, this research, with the analysis of the evaluation reports, can serve as a mechanism for improvement and guidance in relation to evaluation CBHE projects.

2.1.6 Value and Evaluation

The concept of value has been examined from various perspectives, including philosophical, sociological, and economic (Wallstam, 2022). In philosophy, value is explored through axiology, or “the theory of value,” which is further divided into ethics and aesthetics

(Chopra, 2005). In economics, value relates to exchange, encompassing goods, services, or commodities, and implies the idea of pricing or assigning economic worth to an object or desired item (Turner, 1990). In Sociology, Graeber (2001) defined value as “the conception of what is ultimately good, proper, or desirable in human life” (p. 1). This definition aligns with the view that values are principles guiding social behavior (Ponizovskiy et al., 2019).

The concept of “value” is intrinsically linked to evaluation. The importance we attach to an action and its outcome is determined by the value we place on it, influencing how we evaluate its success (or not) of that action or outcome (Nutbeam, 2017). According to Gullickson & Hannum (2019), “No matter how you define evaluation, evaluative judgement is, or should be, part of evaluation” (p. 163). Thus, a theory about what is valuable and why is essential. However, different stakeholders may have diverse values, leading them to view and evaluate the program differently; consequently, their assessments of success may vary significantly (Nutbeam, 2017; van Niekerk, 2016).

The practice of evaluation should be responsive to stakeholders’ values, alongside other criteria, to assess the merits of a program (Hall et al., 2012). This approach, as proposed by Gullickson & Hannum (2019), is beneficial because understanding the varying criteria of stakeholders can lead to a more comprehensive evaluation, enabling nuanced judgments based on diverse value perspectives. Responsive practice evaluation can be conducted from various vantage points, including descriptive evaluation, which aligns with a pluralistic, responsive evaluation approach. In this method, evaluators describe stakeholder values and use them to assess the merit of a program (Stake, 2004). Alternatively, prescriptive valuation, rooted in the democratic evaluation tradition, incorporates stakeholder values as well as broader social values, such as social justice and equity, which the evaluation aims to advance (Greene et al., 2006).

Value and effectiveness are part of the DNA of this research. The values guiding this research are rooted in egalitarian solutions and the empowerment of beneficiaries in the evaluation process of CBHE initiatives. By prioritising equal participation and voice of all stakeholders, including beneficiaries, I am advocating for a more inclusive and representative evaluation. This approach not only enhances the validity and relevance of evaluation results but also fosters a sense of ownership and commitment among participants. The active involvement of beneficiaries in the evaluation process can lead to more meaningful and impactful evaluations, consequently, results can be applied within their respective institutions. This engagement can also enhance the beneficiaries' capacity to exercise influence over the improvement of their own institutions. Furthermore, the research is driven by a commitment to responsibility and coherence, ensuring that the entire evaluation process aligns with the realities of CBHE projects. Evaluations should reflect and respond to the different experiences and needs of stakeholders, including beneficiaries.

By upholding these values, my research promotes inclusive, context-sensitive evaluations ultimately contributing to institutional development.

2.1.7 Effectiveness and Evaluation

The Cambridge Dictionary defines effective as “successful or achieving the results that you want”. Thus, effectiveness, as a standard or criterion, can vary among stakeholders due to their differing aspirations, even within ICBHE programs that have a single stated objective.

In the *Revised Evaluation Criteria Definitions and Principles for Use* (OECD, 2019), effectiveness is defined as: “The extent to which the intervention achieved, or is expected to achieve, its objectives, and its results, including any differential results across groups. Note: Analysis of effectiveness involves taking account of the relative importance of the objectives or results” (p. 9). This definition allows evaluations to better address the points (results and/or objectives) they aim to assess.

The literature (Crawford & Bryce, 2003; Musodza et al., 2021; Smyth et al., 2021) indicates that effective evaluation requires stakeholder involvement during the process design. Greene (2005) defines stakeholders as “people who have a stake or a vested interest in the programme, policy or product being evaluated... and therefore also have a stake in evaluation” (p. 397). Their inclusion in the design phase of the evaluation process can occur at different stages (Musodza et al., 2021). Poor evaluation results can often be attributed to inadequate planning (Smyth et al., 2021).

Given that stakeholders’ interests may differ, and that no evaluation can address all interests, the focus should be on the specific stakeholder group’s interests during the assessment (UNEG, 2017). Therefore, the effectiveness of the evaluation for each stakeholder group depends on how well their interests have been considered during the methodological definition phase. Effectiveness and value are distinct yet interrelated concepts, particularly in the context of evaluation. The effectiveness of an evaluation depends on the criteria used, which are grounded in values. Thus, while value and effectiveness are different, they are interconnected when discussing evaluation.

2.1.8 Conclusion

In this section, I have reviewed concepts and theories relating to CB, stakeholders, evaluation and key concepts for this study as me value and effectiveness.

The body of literature on CB is extensive overall. However, when specifically focusing on ICBHE, the number of studies significantly decreases, and the available cases or studies often only report project results or their evaluations. While there is substantial literature on the importance and role of stakeholders in capacity building, the volume also diminishes when narrowed to ICBHE. Additionally, literature focusing on direct beneficiaries and their perspectives on the concepts of evaluation value and effectiveness is notably scarce.

This section includes different evaluation theories. Stakeholder theory emphasises the importance of involving all stakeholders in the evaluation process, recognising that beneficiaries are not merely passive recipients but active participants who can influence the success of a project. Program Evaluation theory provides a framework for understanding how the results of educational interventions can be measured and, in particular, the Utilization-Focused Evaluation highlights the need to design evaluations that are useful to stakeholders, ensuring that the results are applicable to future decisions. Participatory evaluation emphasises the idea of involving beneficiaries in all the stages of the evaluation, including planning. Context-focused evaluation stresses the idea that each intervention should be analysed with consideration of socio-cultural particularities, specific institutional conditions, and contextual constraints and opportunities. Furthermore, ECB focuses on enhancing the evaluative capabilities of institutions and their beneficiaries, thereby enabling them to conduct their own evaluations and use the findings to improve their practices.

The combination of these theories offers the opportunity to understand the multiplicity of perspectives on the value of evaluations, which is essential for capturing the specific expectations and needs of different stakeholder groups. It also allows for an analysis of the degree of ownership by direct beneficiaries, ensuring that their voices are heard, and their experiences are considered in the evaluation process. The concept of ownership, which is inextricably linked to the power dynamics between the various stakeholders involved in ICBHE projects, has guided my analysis of North-South partnership relations. Additionally, it can identify contextual factors that influence perceptions of effectiveness, which is crucial for adapting interventions to local realities. This approach is essential for understanding the real impact of interventions within the educational context and the evaluations of those interventions.

The extant literature consistently highlights the importance of involving direct beneficiaries in the evaluation process, emphasising that their participation is essential to improve the relevance, ownership and impact of evaluations. Scholars widely agree that participatory approaches empower beneficiaries, enhance the use of evaluation results in their own contexts and contribute to more sustainable and meaningful results. Beneficiary participation fosters transparency and accountability, ensuring that evaluations reflect the needs and realities of those most affected by programmes. Feedback from beneficiaries provides unique perspectives that may not be captured by other evaluation methods. Most researchers agree that beneficiary participation should go beyond data collection to include roles in evaluation design, analysis and dissemination. This broad participation further enhances the depth and authenticity of the evaluation process, leading to more robust and actionable findings.

However, there is a lack of consensus among the scholars regarding the extent and methods of beneficiary participation in different evaluation contexts. Some advocate for deep involvement across all phases of evaluation – from the planning stage through to dissemination – whilst others caution that excess involvement has the capacity to be resource-intensive, to delay the process, or to introduce bias. Furthermore, the question of whether the involvement of beneficiaries in the evaluation process can potentially compromise objectivity or enhance the validity of results remains unresolved for some scholars. Moreover, researchers must address the question of how to balance the input of beneficiaries with the perspectives of other stakeholders, such as funders or policymakers, who may have different priorities. The contested views reflect the complexity of integrating beneficiary participation in a manner that maintains the rigour and efficiency of the evaluation process.

Several questions remain unanswered or require further research in this field: What are the most effective methodologies to involve beneficiaries in diverse cultural and organizational

contexts? How can potential power dynamics be addressed during the evaluation process? What are the most effective methods for involving beneficiaries in different stages of the evaluation process, in concrete in the analysis and dissemination process? How can the feedback provided by the beneficiaries be incorporated into evaluation standards? And in different context? How can ensure ethical participation of beneficiaries throughout the evaluation process?

These gaps highlight the need for further study to refine the participation of beneficiaries in evaluation practices.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Introduction

The literature review shows how North-South partnerships have evolved from paternalistic approaches to more equitable collaborations. However, challenges persist in achieving ownership by direct beneficiaries of ICBHE projects and power imbalances. The literature review guides that one critical factor to achieve ownership is considering direct beneficiaries in the moment of drafting the ToR of the evaluation (Chambers, 1997; Rossi et al., 2003). To address this gap in my research, the agency theory provides a valuable theoretical framework. This theory examines the relationship between principals (donors) and agents (implementing unit) and helps explain the misalignment of interest, information gaps, and conflicts in CB projects.

The application of agency theory to ICBHE projects enables analysis of how power dynamics, knowledge transfer and ownership issues emerged during the implementation of the project and evaluation. This theoretical framework allows me to comprehend the motivations and actions of different stakeholders, especially the role of direct beneficiaries. Moreover, it can shed light on the limitations of evaluation practices that do not capture the needs and perspectives of direct beneficiaries. Agency theory can help me to understand the difficulties in

achieving ownership by direct beneficiaries and consequently sustainable outcome in ICBHE projects. It provides a lens through which I can examine the effectiveness of current evaluation methods and explore ways on how to improve direct beneficiary participation throughout the project life cycle (including evaluation process).

This approach underlines the necessity for more contextualised, participatory evaluation practices that empower direct beneficiaries and result in more meaningful and sustainable outcomes in capacity-building initiatives.

2.2.2 Agency Theory: Definition and Explanations

Agency theory was formalised by Jensen & Meckling in 1976. It is a framework within the disciplines of economics and management that explains the relationship between two parties: a principal (owners) and an agent (managers and employees). According to Eisenhardt (1989) this theory explains the relationship in a company, the principal delegates his work to agents who act on behalf of and in the interest of the principal. This relationship is based on the principles of trust and transparency. However, this relationship can lead to problems in terms of conflict of interest (discrepancies between principal's priorities and those of the agent) or asymmetric information (the agent has more information than the principal enables the agent to assume more risks in certain decision-making without considering all potential consequences) (Ross, 1973)

The key components of agency theory are a) principal-agent problem (the interest of the principal and the agent are different); b) Information asymmetry (the agent has more information than the principal) and c) Agency cost (the principal incur in costs to assure that the agent is acting according to the principal's interests) (Eisenhardt, 1989; Linder & Foss, 2013).

Different control mechanisms are used to mitigate these problems and align interest of principals and agents. Some of these mechanisms include the implementation of monitoring systems, such as regular audits to ensure that agents act in the best interests of principals (Namazi, 2013). Economic incentives, as performance-based compensation and stock options, also serve to align the financial interests of agents with those of principals (Agarwal et al., 2012).

This theory has also been criticised by some scholars, in relation to oversimplification, it is focus on self-interest and limited scope (Bendickson et al., 2016; Payne, G., & Petrenko, O, 2019; Zogning, 2017)

This research proposes that agency theory can serve as a valuable framework for understanding and analysing the complexities involved in the evaluation process of CBHE projects. This process is not limited to a single stakeholder but extends to all stakeholders involved in the project. Agency theory thus provides a robust framework for understanding and analysing the intricate relationships within CBHE projects, particularly during the evaluation phase. By employing agency theory, I can explore the potential conflicts of interest, information asymmetries, and the alignment of objectives among different ICBHE stakeholders. This theoretical lens allows me to explore the different stakeholders' goals in relation to the evaluation process. The application of agency theory to CBHE project evaluation processes could contribute to improving stakeholder collaboration and optimizing the overall effectiveness of these initiatives.

2.2.3 Agency Theory and ICHBE

Agency theory can also be applied to ICBHE projects. In these projects, a relationship is established between the donors and the implementing unit through a contractual agreement between them. According to agency theory, I have identified the principal (donors or funding bodies as the EC) and the agent (the implementing unit in charge of the project management)

(Bendickson et al., 2016). Direct beneficiaries are the end users of the projects as they received its benefits, and the external evaluators are the independent party.

In this context, I have distinguished the following key components of agency theory, including also the end users (direct beneficiaries):

- **Principal-agent problem:** Donors' goals aim to use funds effectively and ensure the sustainability of the project. Implementing unit focus on the successful execution the project and evaluation and direct beneficiaries' interests is long-term impact of the project and practical applicable skills.
- **Information Asymmetry:** Donors may lack contextual information or specific knowledge of the beneficiaries' needs. The implementing unit has a better knowledge of the day-to-day operations. Direct beneficiaries know their needs and context best.

To resolve different goals and information asymmetry, communication and transparency among all stakeholders of the project throughout all the phases of the project are crucial. Reflecting the direct beneficiaries' needs from the project's inception ensures relevance and ownership, ultimately contributing to the project's sustainability.

Evaluation (pre-, during and post-project) can help bridge differences between stakeholders by reflecting their interest. Conducting only one evaluation at the end of the project's end makes it is impossible to address issues related to objectives and asymmetric information effectively.

In ICBHE projects, the donors ask the implementing unit, as I have previously described in this chapter (c.f. p.34) the execution of the external evaluation. The implementing unit is responsible for conducting the projects' evaluations although they often hire external evaluators. These external evaluators act as neutral parties, mitigating the agency problems by reducing information asymmetry. They assess whether project goals and all stakeholders'

expectations are being met, considering all stakeholders' interests and needs and offering recommendations that incorporate all the stakeholders' points of view. External evaluators can carry out all these actions not only due to their position of neutrality but also because of their independence when performing them. For this reason, at ICBHE their role is that of an independent party. However, the agency theory could also be applied to the contractual relationship between the implementing unit (agent) and the direct beneficiaries (as final users).

Figure 4

Agency Theory applied to CBHE projects' external evaluations

Source: Authors' creation

Figure 4 illustrates the relationship between the different stakeholders in ICBHE project and how I can apply the agency theory. Given the object of study, agency theory is the

most relevant model of analysis from my point of view as it allows me to analyse the potential information asymmetries inherent in the relationship between principal- agent and agent-final user that can appear during the evaluation process.

Agency theory emphasises the idea that there is a problem of information asymmetries and possible misalignment of priorities between different stakeholders. An asymmetric information situation may arise between the donor (principal) and the implementing unit (agent), as well as between the implementing unit (agent) and the direct beneficiaries (final users). Although the donor gives priority in the evaluation to meeting the needs of the beneficiaries (according to the EC), the activity is carried out by the implementing unit, which obviously does not have the same priorities and has no incentive to share the. The mechanisms to mitigate such asymmetric information are the contracts signed between them as well as the monitoring and evaluation reports. The relationship between the external evaluator (as an independent party) and the implementing unit is also governed by a service contract. Where the evaluator must present the evaluation of the entire program with findings and recommendations. Direct beneficiaries are the stakeholder that gives great part of the information to the external evaluator in the moment of external evaluation.

The external environment could also influence the agency relationships and the project outcomes and results of the evaluation.

2.2.4 Conclusion

Agency theory can be applied to ICBHE projects. To apply this theory is necessary to identify donors as principals and implementing units as agents. The resolution of principal-agent problems and information asymmetry is achieved through the implementation of clear communication, transparency, and evaluations. It should be considered essential that from the project's inception onwards, the needs of direct beneficiaries are given due consideration, thus enhancing the relevance of the project, fostering a sense of project ownership and promoting

long-term sustainability. The involvement of external evaluators as independent parties presents an opportunity to mitigate agency problems and promote greater alignment of stakeholder interests.

2.3 Conclusion

This chapter, through the literature review and the theoretical framework, provides a comprehensive foundation for exploring the effectiveness of external evaluation processes in ICBHE projects. The literature review shows a substantial body of research addressing CB and stakeholders' involvement, with a particular emphasis on beneficiaries' involvement to enhance relevance, ownership and impact (as outlined in stakeholders theory, program evaluation theory, participatory evaluation, focus-based evaluation) and context consideration (as outlined in context- focused evaluation). However, there is a notable gap in the extant literature focusing specifically on the perspectives of direct beneficiaries on the value and effectiveness of ICBHE evaluations.

The theoretical framework, centred on agency theory, offers a lens through which to examine the relationships between donors (principals), implementing units (agents), and direct beneficiaries, highlighting information asymmetries and potential priorities misalignments. The involvement of external evaluators, acting as independent parties, is identified as a way to mitigate agency problems. However, if the ToR does not consider the needs and contextual realities of the beneficiaries, the evaluations may lack contextual relevance. Thus, this may reduce their practical utility and impact for direct beneficiaries. Addressing these gaps can enhance the ownership, validity, and sustainability of project outcomes.

The chapter illustrates that evaluation effectiveness depends on meaningful beneficiary involvement throughout the evaluation process.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to explain the overall design of my research and the rationale behind the choice of research methods. The chapter is divided into seven sections. The first section introduces the research and the research question. The second section discusses the research strategy adopted for this study. In the third section, I introduce the cases I studied. The fourth section presents the research methodology, and the data used for analysis. The final three sections address limitations, ethics, and the chapter conclusion.

This research aims to explore beneficiaries' perceptions of the effectiveness and value of external evaluations of international capacity building in higher education (ICBHE). This study does not discuss the results or outcomes of the projects but focuses on the effects of their external evaluations.

3.1.1 Research Questions

My research question (RQ) is *How effective is the external evaluation process of international capacity building in higher education projects in meeting the needs of the direct beneficiaries, as perceived by these beneficiaries?*

To answer the research question, this study examines both the evaluation process and the opinions of the direct beneficiaries.

The following sub questions delve deeper in specific factors that might influence the effectiveness of the evaluation process as a whole and can influence the perception of direct beneficiaries in relation to external evaluations:

RSQ1: How does the design of the evaluation process facilitate the participation in the evaluation process of direct beneficiaries?

This sub-question looks at how the ToR can shape engagement with beneficiaries during the evaluation process. As explained in the literature chapter (c.f. 2.1.4.4), the ToR outlines all

the points that the evaluation should cover (not only the methodology). If the ToR requires that the process engage with direct beneficiaries, this could help to ensure that the results are in line with direct beneficiaries' expectations, which could improve their perceptions of the evaluation reports.

RSQ2: How does the external evaluator influence the engagement with direct beneficiaries in the evaluation process?

This sub-question looks at how the role of the external evaluator affects the evaluation methodology and, ultimately, the results and perceptions of the beneficiaries. The methodology used can impact beneficiaries' perceptions of the results' accuracy, reliability and relevance. Understanding this influence allows us to assess whether the evaluator's choices contribute to the perceived value and effectiveness of the results by the direct beneficiaries.

RSQ3: How do the direct beneficiaries perceive the effectiveness of the evaluation process?

This sub-question examines how the ToR and the methodology employed in the evaluation reports influence the perception of the direct beneficiaries.

3.1.2 Operational Questions

The operational questions were concrete questions that allowed me to answer the sub-questions, as they provided the data for this through the examination of documents (ToR and reports), the external evaluators, those responsible for writing the ToR and the opinion of the direct beneficiaries).

- a) *What information is included in the Terms of Reference (ToR) for the external evaluation?* This question allows me in this research, an in-depth analysis of the ToR as it gave a detailed information about it. This information is crucial to understand the design and influence on the evaluation process and results that

might shape the direct beneficiary's perception. This operation question is related to sub-question 1.

b) What is the view of the external evaluators on the ToR and on the ICBHE evaluation?

This question captures the evaluators' views on the ToR and the evaluation, and how they might influence the methodology and results. It also raises potential limitations or strengths. This operational question is related to sub-question 2, as it explains how the external evaluators interpret and implement the ToRs and how their perspective can influence the evaluation.

c) How have the external evaluators compiled their reports?

The focus of this question is on the methods and processes used by the external evaluators in the preparation of the report. This operational question is related to sub-question 2 because the methodology used by the external evaluator and how the external evaluator interprets the ToR, may have an impact on the evaluation results and findings and consequently on the perception of the direct beneficiaries.

d) How do the direct beneficiaries perceive the evaluation of ICBHE project?

This last question focuses on the perception of the direct beneficiaries in relation to the ICBHE evaluation. This operational question is linked directly to the research question and therefore to sub-question 3. The perception of the direct beneficiaries in relation of the evaluation is linked to the evaluation outcomes, considering that the outcomes are result of the ToR design and to the process and methodology used by the external evaluator.

To answer this operational questions, I focused and analysed four concrete aspects: a) the importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries; b) the impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project; c) the opinion of the

direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out and d) the value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries.

This structure provides a comprehensive approach for analysing the effectiveness of the evaluation in meeting the beneficiaries' needs.

3.2 Research Strategy

To explore and understand the evaluation procedures and methodologies used in external evaluations and how the evaluations had been perceived by the different stakeholders of the project, I decided to adopt a case study approach. Through detailed analysis of specific capacity building projects, I was able to explore the relationship between the different parts of the project experience: the relationship between the evaluation and the ToR, the way the evaluation was conducted, and the views of the different participants.

The case study format had been chosen because my research question is a “how” question and these types of questions are more explanatory, as suggested by Yin : “In contrast, “how” and “why” questions are more explanatory and likely to lead to the use of a case study, history or experiment as the preferred research method. This is because such questions deal with operational links needed to be traced over time, rather than mere frequencies or incidence” (2009, p. 10).

Based on my research question (*How effective is the external evaluation process of International Capacity Building in Higher Education projects in meeting the needs of the direct beneficiaries, as perceived by these beneficiaries?*), I have analysed the evaluation procedures used by the external evaluators in the evaluations of two ICBHE programmes to understand the value that these evaluations had for direct stakeholders. This analysis considers the stakeholders’ experience both as participants in the project and in the evaluation process, and as recipients of the evaluation results. I needed to examine all documents related to the

evaluation process (ToR) and the reports produced by the evaluators, as well as understand the opinions of the direct beneficiaries of the projects.

In addition to analysing the procedures, I also examined the contexts (geographical, cultural, and economic) in which the projects were conducted, the department or unit within the universities responsible for the project, and the internal structure of these institutions. This analysis helped me to understand the aspirations, motivations, and experiences of the beneficiaries (in this case, universities) and, more specifically, the direct beneficiaries involved.

The project involves two case studies, with the number determined primarily by practical reasons.

I adopted a comparative case study (CCS) approach, following the work of Bartlett & Vavrus (2016). Bartlett & Vavrus (2016, p.42) CCS approach draws on Burawoy's (1998) extended case method, which is based on four principles: extending observer to participant (join people in their eyes to study them), extending observations over time and space (spend long periods of time with the people you study), extending from micro processes to macro forces and finally extended theory (in which your own theory evolves in response to findings). Bartlett & Vavrus (2016) advocate following the extended case method as it considers not only the cases studied but also the context and environment in which they are located. This supports the researcher in formulating theories from the micro processes of observation to the macro levels.

Bartlett & Vavrus (2016) emphasise the importance of context and environment in understanding cases. Their later work (2017) highlights how globalisation is affecting comparisons in CCS. Bartlett & Vavrus (2017) argue that the reconceptualization of culture, in terms of multiculturalism and power dynamics, is shaped by globalisation, which has an impact not only on geography but also on social interactions, political processes and economic

development. They also suggest that comparison in CCS take place within, and are influenced by, this context. Context can be relevant at the local level even though it is influenced by global trends (do Amaral, 2022). In the selection of my case studies, I have paid attention to the context taking into consideration the location of the universities (regional universities vs. universities located in the capital of the country) and universities of different countries, with cultural and economic differences. I have also paid attention to the power relationship between the external evaluator and the direct beneficiaries in relation to the external evaluations, which had been considered in this study through the opinions of both stakeholders.

Thus, at the beginning of the research and according to Goodrick (2014), I described and compared the two different cases to find similarities or differences between them considering that cases' objectives and goals can be common or not. This approach allowed me to formulate generalizations between the two cases identifying common elements of capacity building initiatives, as well as the recognition of their uniqueness.

According to Bartlett & Vavrus (2016), CCS can use three different axes to make comparisons, but it is not necessary to use all of them: horizontal (comparing cases considering different locations, social actors or influences between the cases), vertical (comparing cases considering levels or scales, from the local to regional or global) and transversal (comparing over time). Both qualitative and quantitative methods are often used (interviews, observation or document analysis are the most common methods of data collection). In this study only two different axes had been used (horizontal and transversal). This means that in my research had not only analysed semi-structured interviews but also documents related to the external evaluation of the projects and the context and cultural differences between the three different countries where the projects were implemented. By comparing non-simultaneous projects, I can also see if they have been affected by time factors, which aligns with the transversal axis.

3.3 Cases do be Studied

The cases to be studied in this research are ICBHE projects in the sense that they are donor-funded international projects, aiming to improve capacities of those working in higher education systems (Valle Casanovas, 2021) and typically involve collaboration between local universities and international partners or international IHE. These projects promote global connections, encourage mobility, and bring international perspectives to teaching and learning. However, in the HE environment, institutions in the “north” often overlook these connections and opportunities (Martin & Wyness, 2013).

The two cases chosen for investigation in this project are:

- Fortalecimiento de las Capacidades de Gestión de Entidades Cubanas / Consolidating and Strengthening Managerial Capabilities in Cuban Entities (FORGEC), which aimed to improve the efficiency of Cuban companies by providing training in European management techniques.
- Strengthening Impact of Latin American Universities (IMPALA), which aimed to design and implement a quality referential (framework, tools, methodology) for impact assessment related to the third mission, complementing the current Quality Assurance (QA) mechanisms of universities in Colombia, Cuba, and Panama.

Both cases share two main characteristics: their geographical region, suggesting potential cultural similarities, and the intended level of capacity of the programmes (individual and meso- levels), according to the ultimate goals of the initiatives. The final objective of both projects was capacity building, though each focused on different aspects: development and transfer of management techniques and entrepreneurship (FORGEC) and measuring the impact of the third mission of universities (IMPALA). As my research explores the value of external evaluations of ICBHE programmes for direct stakeholders, without considering the

main objective of each programme, these similarities helped me identify the most important criteria for demonstrating that value. The following points were considered when selecting these cases:

- *Interest from the EU and other European countries:* According to the European Commission (2015), “HE is considered one of the pillars for regional cooperation with partner countries in Latin America, in order to stimulate a more balanced and inclusive economic and social development of the region.” The continuous exchange of knowledge benefits all programme participants.
- *Funding Institution:* The European Commission (EC)
- *Beneficiary countries:* According to the United Nations (2021), the four beneficiary countries are classified as developing economies, and their governments are fully committed to recognising the importance of Higher Education (HE) and Institutions of Higher Education (IHE) in their national development strategies.

Each year, the EC allocates substantial funding to these programmes through initiatives such as Erasmus+. The total budget for Capacity Building in Higher Education (CBHE) under the Erasmus+ initiative for the 2022 call for proposals was estimated at €104 million, with €11 million allocated to projects in Latin America and the Caribbean (European Commission, 2024b).

While extensive literature exists on ICBHE projects and their outcomes, little attention has been given to direct beneficiaries’ perceptions—not of the projects or their results, but of the evaluation process itself. Additionally, limited discussion exists on the value of ICBHE evaluations. For these reasons, I focused my research on ICBHE projects, the evaluation process, and the perspectives of direct beneficiaries. My decision to study two Latin American

projects is based on my knowledge of the region, my language proficiency (as Spanish is my native language, which made interviews more comfortable), and my interest in the region.

Table 3

Cases Studied: Number of Beneficiaries

Case	Donor	Number of Beneficiaries Countries	Number of Beneficiaries Institutions	Number Members Implementing Unit
FORGEC	EU Commission	1	8	3
IMPALA	EU Commission	3	13	6

3.3.1 Description of the Case Studies

3.3.1.1 Case Study 1: FORGEC

FORGEC was a 42-month programme funded by a grant from the EC, through the 2009 Annual Action Programme for Non-State Actors and Local Authorities in Development. The programme was approved in 2013 and carried out between 2014 and 2016.

The EC supported this initiative as part of its collaborative programme with Cuba, aiming to establish long-term cooperation in the field of management education between Cuba and Europe. The primary aim of the FORGEC programme was to enhance the efficiency of Cuban companies by providing high-quality training in modern European management techniques. This objective encompassed several outcomes, including:

- developing highly skilled managers to benefit the Cuban economy
- fostering long-term collaboration in management education between Cuba and Europe
- improving the standards of Cuban educational institutions offering management programmes
- streamlining accreditation processes and

- promoting knowledge renewal and collaborative support among the 550 graduates of the *Diploma Europeo en Administración y Dirección de Empresas (DEADE)*⁴ (*European Diploma in Business and Management Administration*) and *Diploma en Dirección de Empresas (DADE)* (*Diploma in Business and Management Administration*) programmes.

The project involved three main components: the Consolidation Programme, the PEEG Programme, and the methodological centres. The Consolidation Programme included three annual workshops on different topics, specifically aimed at alumni from previous projects and the current programme. The PEEG Programme involved eight editions of six intensive modules, with each module lasting 2.5 days, followed by three days of individual study per month for six months. The *gabinetes metodológicos* (methodological assistance centres) were created in eight Cuban universities to help establish QA mechanisms aligned with internationally recognised quality standards. These centres served as repositories of experience, where good practices could be shared among teachers, and teachers could be provided with methods or models to apply to entrepreneurs.

The stakeholders of the project were and according to the description of the literature chapter (cf. 2.1.3.2)

- a) Donor as the organization that provide financial resources
 - European Commission

⁴ Programs under the auspices of the European Commission, implemented between 1994 and 2004, whose focus was on the training and capacity building of Cuban company managers (CUB/B7-3011/94/150 Programa de Formación para Directivos de Empresas, CUB/B7-3011/96/054: Programa de Formación para Directivos de Empresas, DEADE – Fase II) and training of Cuban managers (CUB/RELEX/2001/0084 Programa de Formación de Dirigentes Cubanos)

b) Legal Beneficiary of the project and who signed the contract of the project that in that case was a slightly different form the implementing unit:

- European Foundation for Management Development (EFMD), Brussels, Belgium.
- *Ministerio de Educación Superior (MES)*, Cuba.
- Delegation of the European Commission in Cuba

c) Implementing Unit responsible for managing the project was composed by:

- EFMD (as legal beneficiary)
- *Universitat Ramon Llull (URL)*, Barcelona, Spain. (as European academic director of the project)
- MES, Cuba (as Cuban academic director of the project)

d) Beneficiaries: I have distinguished between direct (individuals or institutions) and indirect.

- Direct beneficiaries – Organizations: In this research, these refer to the universities where the project was implemented: eight Cuban HEIs
 - *Universidad de la Habana (UH)*
 - *Universidad Agraria de la Habana “Fructuoso Rodríguez Pérez” (UNAH)*
 - *Universidad Central “Marta Abreu” de Las Villas (UCLV)*
 - *Universidad de Camagüey “Ignacio Agramonte Loynaz”*
 - *Universidad de Holguín “Oscar Lucero Moya” (UHo)*
 - *Universidad de Matanzas “Camilo Cienfuegos”*
 - *Universidad de Pinar del Río “Hnos Saíz Montes de Oca”*
 - *Universidad de Oriente (UO)*

- **Direct beneficiaries – Individuals:** These are participants in the activities carried out throughout the programme or project, such as training courses, mentoring, and meetings. Direct beneficiaries experience significant, long-lasting impacts—whether positive or negative, expected or unforeseen—on their personal and professional lives, such as gaining new knowledge or developing personal skills. These individuals are responsible for transferring their knowledge and expertise within their own institutions (in this case, universities) and to society at large.
- **Indirect beneficiaries:** In this research, it refers to Cuban economic sector, including entrepreneur, cooperatives and public or mix (with Cuban and foreign capital) companies.
- **Country:** This refers to the location where the programme took place, in that case Cuba.

Figure 5

FORGEC Program Stakeholders

Source: Authors' creation

3.3.1.2. Case Study 2: IMPALA.

The IMPALA project was a 48-month programme funded by a grant from the EC, through the Erasmus+ KA2⁵ (Cooperation for Innovation and the Exchange of Good Practices – Capacity Building in the Field of Higher Education). The programme was approved in 2018 and carried out between 2018 and 2022 in Colombia, Cuba, and Panama.

The main objective of the IMPALA programme was to elevate the quality of universities by crafting and implementing a quality framework, tools, and methodology focused on impact assessment of all the university's activities, in particular, the services the universities provide to the community (“third mission”). This framework complements the existing quality assurance systems, which traditionally focus on the quality of teaching and research. Additionally, the programme aims to equip Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with the capabilities to apply this quality framework to their specific circumstances, promoting a shift towards a culture driven by impact assessment. In the IMPALA project, impact was understood as all the mid- and long-term changes brought by the results of an activity on its local environment, such as educational and intellectual, financial, business development, social and visibility results. Ultimately, this transition enhances the quality and relevance of the services offered by HEIs to their communities.

Under this overarching goal, the programme sought to develop and implement a quality framework, along with tools and methodology based on impact assessment, which complements the current quality assessment mechanisms. It aimed to provide HEIs with the

⁵ The Erasmus+ KA2 (Key Action 2) programme focuses on cooperation among organizations and institutions. It supports various types of partnerships and projects aimed at fostering innovation, exchange of good practices, and capacity building across different sectors.

skills to apply this quality framework to their unique situations and enhance the quality and relevance of services offered to the community as an integral part of the university's mission.

The project involves three key pillars:

- establishing a new evaluation tool known as the “Impact Assessment Framework (IAF)” and validate it.
- enabling the evaluation and improvement of all facets of university operations, with a specific emphasis on the services provided to the community, often referred to as the “third mission”
- training senior leaders and managers to measure impact and carry out institutional assessments; and training faculties and specialised staff to develop high-impact activities and projects for the local community.

The project also culminated in the publication of a book titled Best Practices in Impact Assessment in HEIs and a case study book called Creating Impact in HEIs.

The stakeholders of the IMPALA project were:

- a) Donor as the organization that provide financial resources
 - European Commission
- b) Legal beneficiary: In that case the legal beneficiary and the Implementing Unit are the same, although one institution (EFMD) was the one that signed the contract as coordinator of the Consortium.
- c) Implementing Unit that managed the project and all the activities was composed by 6 European Higher Institutions:
 - *Universidade Nova de Lisboa (UNL), Portugal*
 - *Universidade do Porto (UP), Portugal*
 - *Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain*

- Universitat Ramon Llull (URL), Spain
- *Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSS), Italy*
- EFMD, Belgium

d) Beneficiaries: I have distinguished between direct (individuals or institutions) and indirect (recipients of the activities related to third mission).

- Direct beneficiaries – Universities or HEIs where the project was implemented:
 - Six Colombian universities or institutions
 - *Asociación Colombiana de Facultades de Administración (ASCOLFA)*
 - *Universidad de Antioquía (UA)*
 - *Universidad Católica de Colombia (UCC)*
 - *Universidad del Valle (UniValle)*
 - *Universidad de la Sabana (UniSabana)*
 - *Pontificia Universidad Javeriana (UPJ)*
 - Five Cuban universities or institutions:
 - Ministerio de Educación Superior de Cuba (MES)
 - Universidad Agraria de la Habana “Fructuoso Rodríguez Pérez” (UNAH)
 - *Universidad Central “Marta Abreu” de Las Villas (UCLV)*
 - *Universidad de Camagüey “Ignacio Agramonte Loynaz” (UC)*
 - *Universidad de Holguín “Oscar Lucero Moya” (UHo)*
 - Two Panamanian universities:
 - *Universidad Especializada de las Américas (UDELAS)*

- *Universidad de Panamá (UP)*
- Direct beneficiaries – Individuals: Direct participants of the different activities: Specifically, for each activity, different profiles include university managers, teachers, and administrative staff.
- Indirect beneficiaries: In this research, recipients of the activities of third mission
- Country: This refers to the location where the programme took place, in that case Colombia, Cuba and Panamá.

Figure 6

IMPALA Program Stakeholders

Source: Authors' creation

3.3.1.3. Selection of universities

The number of HEIs that are direct beneficiaries varies between the projects (the FORGEC project involves eight universities from the same country, while the IMPALA project involves 13 universities from three different countries). Two direct beneficiaries (universities) were selected from each project. The factors that have determined the number of universities to participate in this research are:

- **Comparison:** If only one university per project was chosen, it would not have been possible to compare results between universities within the same project. In this research, I aim to compare both the outcomes of universities within the same project and the results between projects.
- **Manageability:** Each participating centre requires interviews with a minimum of six and a maximum of nine people. Increasing the number of universities involved would have made the research unmanageable.
- **Accessibility:** Accessibility to the universities and to the individuals to be interviewed was also considered, as it is essential for obtaining data.

The following factors influenced the type of universities selected for this research:

- **Type of institution:** Only universities were chosen, as all the direct beneficiaries in one of the projects were universities. Since no other types of organisations were involved, a comparison between different types of institutions would not have been possible.
- **Context of the university:** In the first project, all the universities are from the same country (Cuba). In the second project, the universities are from three countries (Cuba, Colombia, and Panama). To explore whether universities from the same

country value evaluations differently than those from other countries, I selected one university from Cuba and one from Colombia.

- Size of the university: A university located in the capital of a country is generally larger and offers a wider range of academic programmes than one in a province. Therefore, in both projects, I selected one capital-based university and one regional university to assess whether size influences the value placed on evaluations.
- Location of the university: Universities were categorised as either located in the capital of the country or in the capital of a region (regional universities). Regional universities often have closer relationships with local governments and play more active roles in regional innovation processes and policymaking (Fonseca & Nieth, 2021). In contrast, universities in the national capital are more connected to the national government, which holds decision-making authority. For this reason, I selected one university of each type for each project.
- Status of the university: Rankings are often used to measure the status of a university. For each project, I chose one university represented in the QS World University Rankings and the Times Higher Education University Rankings, and another that was not listed in these rankings.

The universities chosen for the FORGEC project were the Universidad de la Habana and the Universidad de Camagüey 'Ignacio Agramonte Loynaz'.

The Universidad de la Habana⁶ was founded in 1728 in la Habana. It is the oldest university in Cuba and one of the earliest universities in the Americas. Initially named the “Real y Pontificia Universidad de San Gerónimo de la Habana” (Royal and Pontifical

⁶ <https://www.uh.cu/inicio/>

University of Saint Jerome of Havana), it was originally housed in the Dominican convent of Santo Domingo in Old Havana. In 1842, it became a secular institution, no longer under religious authority. The Universidad de la Habana is considered the cradle of advanced Cuban thought and action. It is often referred to as the Alma Mater of Cuban higher education, continually striving for academic excellence and social relevance with strong national and international engagement. Located in Havana, the capital of Cuba, the university has 16 faculties, four institutes, and 18 research centres covering various fields, including humanities, natural sciences, economics, and social sciences. It offers 38 undergraduate programmes and a wide range of postgraduate activities, including doctoral and master's programmes, as well as professional development courses, conferences, and workshops promoting lifelong learning for graduates. As of the most recent academic year, the total enrolment stood at 16,123 students, with 4,081 faculty members, including 693 PhDs and 340 master's degree holders. The Universidad de la Habana is ranked 467th in the QS World University Rankings 2023, 251–300 in QS WUR by Subject, and 27th in the LatAm University Ranking.

The Universidad de Camagüey “Ignacio Agramonte Loynaz” is the first centre of higher education (HE) founded in Cuba in 1967 after the revolutionary triumph of 1 January 1959. Its creation marks the beginning of higher education in Camagüey and is closely linked to the further human and social development of the city. The university comprises ten faculties and offers 52 degree courses in two modalities: presential and semi-presential. It also provides a wide range of postgraduate, doctoral, master's, and speciality courses across different fields. In the academic year 2020–2021, the number of enrolled students exceeded 15,000. The university is located in the capital of the province of Camagüey. This province has 13 municipalities, a population of more than 774,100 inhabitants, and a territorial area of 15,990 square kilometres, making it the largest province in the country.

For the IMPALA project, the two selected universities are Pontificia Universidad Javeriana (Colombia) and Universidad Agraria de la Habana “Fructuoso Rodríguez Pérez” (Cuba).

Pontificia Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá is a private university founded in 1623. It is one of the oldest and most traditional Colombian universities, directed by the Society of Jesus, with its main facilities in Bogotá and a sectional division in Cali. It is one of 31 universities entrusted to the Society of Jesus in Latin America and one of 114 worldwide. The university was the first higher education institution in Colombia to receive institutional accreditation through Resolution No. 1320, issued on 12 June 2003, by the Colombian Ministry of Education.

In Bogotá, the university has 18 colleges comprising 62 departments and 191 academic programmes across different areas of knowledge. It offers 38 undergraduate programmes, 73 specialised professional study programmes, 39 medical and surgical specialisations, 33 master’s degrees, and 8 PhD programmes. The university in Bogotá has 18,962 undergraduate students and 4,307 graduate students. The faculty includes 1,364 professors and 2,702 adjunct professors. The university also employs 1,506 administrative staff. Its campus consists of 45 buildings across 44.5 acres in a strategically located and easily accessible part of the city. The university selects applicants with the highest academic credentials. Its graduates are recognised for their professional excellence, teamwork skills, and value-centred human leadership. Pontificia Universidad Javeriana is ranked 382nd in the QS World University Rankings 2023, 205th in QS WUR by Subject, and 18th in the LatAm University Ranking.

Universidad Agraria de la Habana “Fructuoso Rodríguez Pérez” was founded on 7 September 1976, originally under the name Higher Institute of Agricultural Sciences of Havana. It is located in San José de las Lajas, just 23 km from Havana. It is the oldest of the Cuban agricultural universities, with roots in the University of Havana, specifically in the

School of Agricultural Sciences at Quinta de los Molinos, which housed the Schools of Agronomy and Veterinary Science. The university currently has seven faculties and offers 28 degree programmes. It maintains academic and scientific-technical cooperation with 23 countries and holds 131 agreements with universities across all continents. The total enrolment in the 2020–2021 academic year was 12,948 students.

In both projects, one university located in the capital of the country (metropolitan) and one university located in a province (regional) have been chosen. Both metropolitan universities are listed in international and accredited university rankings and are older than their regional counterparts. Through this selection, I aim to assess whether the responses to the same questions are similar or vary, and whether factors such as location, size, ownership, or international recognition influence their responses—or whether these variables do not affect their perceptions of the value of ICBHE project evaluations. Initially, it can be assumed that the value placed on such assessments may differ depending on these variables. However, this assumption will be tested through data analysis, specifically via semi-structured interviews.

Table 4

Universities in the Research Project

University	Type of University	Country	City	Province	Population City of University	Area of Influence	Nº Faculties	Nº of Students (Degree + Master+PhD)
U. de la Habana	Public	Cuba	La Habana	La Habana	2 132 394*	2 132 394*	16	18 359
U. de Camagüey	Public	Cuba	Camagüey	Camagüey	332 427*	764 794*	10	17000
U. Agraria de la Habana	Public	Cuba	San Jose de las Lajas	Mayabeque	80 305*	383 869*	7	12 948
U. Pontificia Javeriana de Bogotá	Private	Colombia	Ciudad de Bogotá	Bogota, D.C.	7 181 469**	7 181 469**	18	21 740

Source: * Estudios y Datos sobre la Población Cubana. Centro de Estudios de Población y Desarrollo. Marzo 2020. <http://www.onei.gob.cu/>

** DANE. Sistema Estadístico Nacional (Colombia). <https://www.dane.gov.co/>

3.4 Method

3.4.1 Approach to the Case Studies

I had adopted a comprehensive approach to comparative case studies combining document analysis with stakeholders semi-structured interviews. The study and analysis of existing documents (ToR and external evaluation reports) had provided a solid foundation of information. Semi-structured interviews with different types of project stakeholders complement document analysis with personal perceptions and different perspectives that may reveal information not available in formal documents.

Each case was analysed separately by using the same method for both. The data from each case were later compared to identify similarities and differences. The results of this comparison allowed me to assess the value of the ToR in the evaluation process, the role of the evaluator in adhering to the ToR, and the current value that ICBHE assessments provide to the direct beneficiaries. This evidence-based analysis underpins my conclusions and recommendations for potential improvements to the evaluation process.

Figure 7

Research strategy

	WHAT	WHY	HOW
Documents Analysis	Terms of Reference of the Evaluation	Prescriptiveness of the ToR	Q-ToR: Checklist (13 q.) with system of scales. Individual analysis of the ToR
	Evaluation Reports (Mid-Term and Final)	To what extent the information requested in the ToR appear in the Evaluation Reports Level of information on the topics that appear in the Evaluation Reports	EV-Form: Meta-evaluation (82q)
Semi Structured Interviews Analysis	Direct Beneficiaries of the cases	Determine the perception that direct beneficiaries have in relation to External Evaluation	Thematic Analysis
	External Evaluators of the cases	Determine the perception that external evaluators have in relation to ToR and External Evaluation	
	Implementing Unit (responsible of writing the ToR of the External Evaluation)	Determine the perception that implementing unit has in relation to ToR and External Evaluation	

Source: Authors' creation

3.4.2 Document Analysis

The ToR of an evaluation serves as the foundational document for carrying out the process (*Better Evaluation, 2024*). Therefore, the ToRs of both projects were analysed to determine whether their conceptualisation followed a consistent pattern and whether the external evaluators were required to adhere to specific methodologies during the assessment. Additionally, the external evaluation reports (both interim and final) for both cases were reviewed and analysed. Through this analysis, I identified the methodologies employed by the external evaluators and how they interacted with the direct beneficiaries during the external evaluation process. The analysis of these documents was conducted through the Q-ToR checklist (in case of the ToR) and a meta-evaluation form (EV-Form) specifically designed for this purpose (c.f. Appendix 1 and Appendix 2). This meta-evaluation assessed the criteria of

impartiality, equity, and quality. These criteria are the used by the Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation, and they also fulfil all the aspects to analyse in relation to the evaluation reports. numerical questionnaire was used for this meta-evaluation, which was employed to collect data and evaluate the original external evaluation. Consequently, a quantitative approach was used for this meta-evaluation.

The selection of these documents has helped me answer two research sub-question: RSQ1 related to the ToR and RSQ2 concerning how the external evaluators conducted the reports.

3.4.2.1 Data Collection.

Terms of Reference of the Evaluation: All ToR documents were available through open sources, as the external evaluator was hired through a public tender. The ToR serve as the foundation of the evaluation, making their analysis essential to understanding the evaluation process. The ToR drafting process starts with the implementing unit as the legal beneficiary, followed by the ToR publication on various websites (typically the project's website and that of the consortium leader) to attract proposals from external evaluators, which are then reviewed to select the external evaluator for the project.

- i. ToR Case FORGEC
- ii. ToR Case IMPALA

The FORGEC Programme was part of the 2009 Annual Action Programme for Non-State Actors and Local Authorities in Development, run under the Directorate-General for Development and Cooperation (EuropeAid). In 2011, a new Directorate-General (DG DEVCO – EuropeAid) was created, but after internal restructuring in 2015 and 2021, DG DEVCO was formally dissolved, and DG INTPA was established. Due to these organisational changes, it has been challenging to find information about evaluation procedures for the period and for the projects done under the umbrella of the Directorate-General for Development and Cooperation

(EuropeAid) as the FORGEC programme that was active from 2013 to 2016. To address this issue, I made direct inquiries to those responsible for drafting the ToR to understand the documents they had used. Additionally, I asked the external evaluator whether they had received not only the ToR for the evaluation but also some templates from the programme management for conducting the evaluation, to which they responded that they received only the ToR. I also searched for other DG evaluation procedures from that period to gather more information and used them to for this study.

Reports produced by the evaluators of the projects: Some reports were publicly accessible, while others had to be requested directly from the evaluators or the ICBHE project managers. Informed consent to use internal documents was obtained from the document owners. Through these reports, I identified the methodologies employed by the evaluators and determined whether they adhered strictly to the ToR or included elements not defined in the ToR.

- i. MidTerm Report Case FORGEC
- ii. Final Report Case FORGEC
- iii. MidTerm Report Case IMPALA
- iv. Final Report Case IMPALA

Context. I conducted comparisons to establish potential relationships between the interviewees and the type or geographic location of the university involved. This information helped me to interpret and analyse my findings.

3.4.2.2 Data Analysis.

I conducted two different analyses: one focused on the Terms of Reference (ToR) and the other on the Evaluation Reports (ER), using a quantitative approach.

Terms of Reference Analysis: I reviewed and analysed the ToR of each case individually because of their importance to the report-writing process as the ToR determine the

evaluation process and the information that should appear in the reports. To support this analysis, I developed a specific evaluation tool called Q-ToR. This tool consists of a checklist with 13 questions (c.f. Table 5), which includes the five key issues identified by the European Commission (2004) as essential for inclusion in the ToR (marked in blue), along with new questions related to the contextualization of the evaluation according to the European Commission (2014) and the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the process of the evaluation (Roberts et al., 2011) to improve the ownership not only of the project but also of the ToR of the project.

The Q-ToR uses a scale to grade the level of prescriptiveness (c.f. Table 6), ranging from 1 (non-prescriptive) to 4 (prescriptive) considering that ToR is the key document guides the entire evaluation process (c.f. 2.1.4.4). However, the response options for these questions possess only ordinal properties, limiting the variability needed for robust data analysis. While comparing the median scores between the two ToRs is theoretically possible, such a comparison presents challenges. It requires assuming that all 13 criteria are equally relevant, resulting in a small sample size ($n=13$). Additionally, using a non-parametric test with such a small sample (2 cases, 2 ToRs) would yield very low statistical power, reducing the likelihood of detecting significant differences. Given these limitations, I concluded that statistical analysis would not be appropriate. Instead, I evaluated each ToR individually and compared the results. The same considerations applied to the analysis of the evaluation reports.

This approach allowed me to assess the prescriptiveness of the ToR. According to Kabeyi, (2019), a high-quality project evaluation requires precise and well-defined ToR. Following this logic, the more prescriptive the ToR, the less flexibility the external evaluator has when producing the evaluation reports.

In this research, I focused on two questions that were particularly relevant among the five key points described by the European Commission. The first is question 8: *“Do the Terms*

of Reference indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation?” This question is crucial because the methodology determines the methods the external evaluator will use, making it a primary indicator of whether the ToR are prescriptive. Other information in the ToR provides general insights about the project or specifies the evaluator's profile but does not dictate the methodology to be followed.

The second relevant question is question 12: *“Has the interests of the direct beneficiaries (no other stakeholders) of the programme been taken into account in the ToR?”* This question concerns the participation of direct beneficiaries during the drafting of the ToR by the funding institution or the project’s legal beneficiary. The answer to this question has helped me address my research question, and I interviewed the individuals responsible for writing the ToR to gather further insights.

Table 5

Q-ToR Checklist

1. Have the Terms of Reference been formulated in a clear and understandable manner?
2. Do the Terms of Reference contain the objective and scope of the programme?
3. Do the Terms of Reference contextualize the programme?
4. Do the Terms of Reference outline the activities and the work plan of the programmes?
5. Do the Terms of Reference outline the expected results of the programme?
6. Do the Terms of Reference indicate the stakeholders of the programme?
7. Do the Terms of Reference indicate the beneficiaries of the programme?
8. Do the Terms of Reference indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation?
9. Do the Terms of Reference identify the resources (personal) and timing for the evaluation to be carried out?
10. Have the Terms of Reference specified the deliverables to be produced after the evaluation?
11. Do the Terms of Reference contain the budget allocated to the evaluation, and is it in accordance with the evaluation?
12. Has the interest of the direct beneficiaries (no other stakeholders) of the programme been taken into account in the Terms of Reference?
13. To what extent do the Terms or Reference focus on the assessment of (unintended) outcomes and impacts?

Blue Color used to recognise the five key issues identified by the European Commission (2004) as essential for inclusion in the ToR
 Black Color used to recognise the new questions

Source: Authors' creation

Table 6

Grade of Prescriptiveness of the ToR

Scores	Definition Scores
1 – Non-prescriptive	In the ToR, the information detailed in the Q-ToR checklist does not appear in any form.
2 – Open	In the ToR, the information requested in the Q-ToR checklist appears in a non-explicit form.
3 – Semi-prescriptive	In the ToR, the information requested in the Q-ToR checklist appears explicitly but not in its totality.
4 – Prescriptive	In the ToR, the information requested in the Q-ToR checklist appears explicitly in its totality.

Source: Authors' creation

Based on the findings from the analysis the ToR were categorised depending on the grade of prescriptiveness. Through this categorisation we also knew if external evaluators had more freedom to use the method, they considered most appropriate. I also determined through the type of information that appear in the ToR whether the interest of the direct beneficiaries (no other stakeholders) of the project had been taken into consideration at that stage of the project. To confirm that aspect I also asked it to the responsible of writing the ToR of both cases during the interviews I had with them. The responsibility for drafting the ToR lies with the implementing unit of the project, thus a Northern stakeholder of the project. In the case of FORGEC, the project coordinator institution, was responsible for drafting the ToR. In the case of IMPALA, the project quality manager institution, who was responsible for it.

Evaluation Reports Analysis. To analyse the Evaluation Reports (ER) (mid-term and final), I created a meta-evaluation form (EV-Form) containing 3 different criteria split in 82 questions in total (c.f. Appendix 2) to determine whether the objectives, questions, and methods specified in the ToR were considered during the external evaluators' reports, regardless of the outcome of those reports.

The amount of data was too limited to apply statistical analysis, so I only compared the results of the EV-Form. The 82 questions of the EV-Form were divided into three main criteria, with one criterion (quality) further divided into nine categories. These categories and their associated questions are also primarily based on those used by the Spanish (Ministerio de Asuntos Exteriores y de Cooperación, 2007) / Ministry of External Affairs and Cooperation (2007) and adopted by the Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation. I have included more detail e new questions in relation to the quality criteria.

Table 7

Criteria of the EV-Form

Criteria	Meaning	Number of questions related to these criteria
Impartiality	Depends on the type of evaluation carried out: internal or external	1
Equity	Refers to ensure evaluation inclusivity, stakeholders' involvement, context relevance, and accessibility of the evaluation.	3
Quality	Verifies the established processing guidelines of the evaluation impartiality	78 questions split into 9 different categories

Source: Authors' creation

In the initial analysis, the answers to these questions were limited to “yes” or “no”. “Yes” indicates that the document contains information relevant to the question and provides a positive answer, while “no” indicates that the document does not contain or clearly describe information relating to the question.

However, to obtain more precise answers, all questions were re-analysed, this time with five possible responses depending on the level of information required. In some cases, the information might not be required in the ToR but must be included in the ER, such as in a cover page or annexes (if necessary). In such cases, although the score for the question should

be 5, I applied logical reasoning and scored the question based on how the information appears in the document.

Table 8

Grades of the Results of the Meta-Analysis of the Mid-Term Evaluation Report: Level of Information in the Mid-Term Evaluation Report in Relation to the ToR

Scores	Definition Scores
1	The evaluation report does not contain the information specified in the EV-Form question in any form
2	The evaluation report contains the information specified in the EV-Form question but not in its totality
3	The evaluation report contains the information specified in the EV-Form question explicitly in its totality
4	The evaluation report contains the information specified in the EV-Form question and include complementary data.
5	The evaluation report provides more information than required by the Terms of Reference.

Source: Authors' creation

My research sub-question number 2 (RSQ2), c.f. 3.1.1, is to understand the role of the external evaluators. The way external evaluators interpret the ToR will shape the type of evaluation they carry out and the resulting outcomes. Although external evaluators may follow the ToR, their personal views on what an evaluation should contain and focus on also influence the type of evaluation conducted if the ToR are not enough detail (*Better Evaluation*, 2024). Could it be that direct beneficiaries perceive the value of the evaluation reports not only based on the outcomes but also on the questions that were or were not posed during the process? Thus, external evaluators act as the link between the ToR and the external reports of the projects, and their interpretation of the ToR functions as a mediator variable.

Figure 8

Interrelation between the Terms of Reference and the Report of the Projects

Source: Authors' creation

I tested the ToRs twice within three months of each other to see if there were differences by carrying out the same exercise, with a sufficient time lag to verify that the initial results were consistent. Moreover, and following Saldaña's idea of reliability (2012), I used a consensus-based approach to establish the reliability of the ToR evaluation, ensuring consistent and unbiased results. To accomplish this purpose, an external person was asked to analyse the ToR and the ER.. The results of the external analysis and my own were very similar, with only minor differences identified in the ToR analysis. In two questions, the indicated degree of prescriptiveness varied between a grade of 2 or 3, but the overall result of the analysis did not change significantly.

Thus, after analysing both the ToR and the evaluation reports, I was able to observe the relationship between the type of ToR (prescriptive or non-prescriptive), the final reports, and the role of the external evaluator in bridging the ToR and the evaluation reports.

3.4.3 Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with different stakeholders (direct beneficiaries, ToR's writers, and external evaluators) involved in both cases. Stakeholders with different roles often hold varying assumptions and expectations about the external evaluation, as individuals perceive the evaluation differently (Julian, 2016). This diversity of perspectives was crucial for analysing the interview results. Direct beneficiaries' interviews provided me with insights into what participants of the intervention truly think and expect about the evaluations. Interviewing the external evaluators enabled me to gain insight into their views on external evaluations in general and how they approached the FORGEC and IMPALA evaluations specifically. The interviews with the ToR writers provided information about the basis of the ToR, what content it should include, and their perspectives on it. These interviews formed the data for the qualitative analysis.

The purpose of the interviews was to explore the process of the evaluations from the perspective of the stakeholders, their expectations, and the importance they assigned to the evaluations. The interviews helped me answer operational research questions 2 and 3, concerning the opinions of the external evaluators and those responsible for writing the ToR, and question 4, regarding the perceptions of direct beneficiaries in relation to the evaluation methodology. For this purpose, I conducted semi-structured interviews with:

- Individuals responsible for writing the ToR: These individuals belong to the implementing unit. The ToR are crucial to the evaluation process, as they provide the basis for the evaluators' work. It was essential to speak with those who drafted the ToR to gain insights into their perspectives on project evaluation and their views on how ToR should be structured.
- External evaluators: Since this research focuses on evaluation, the evaluators' perspectives are integral. External evaluators are not considered beneficiaries of

the project; they are part of the evaluation process and were therefore interviewed. Their involvement was essential, as their work made this research possible. This research does not aim to critique their work or the project results. Only the methodological aspects of the reports were analysed. External evaluators for both projects were selected through public calls.

- Direct beneficiaries of the programme: These include participants in the programme activities, such as training courses, mentoring sessions, and meetings. They experienced significant personal and professional impact through the acquisition of new knowledge or skills. They are responsible for sharing their expertise not only within their own institutions (universities) but also with the broader society.

3.4.3.1 Data Collection.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted either face-to-face or online. All interviews were conducted in Spanish, except for two which were conducted in English.

I prepared two different interview protocols: one for the direct beneficiaries and another for the external evaluators and those responsible for writing the ToR (c.f. Appendix 3). As shown in Table 9, the direct beneficiaries of the FORGEC project were divided into three groups based on their roles within the project, as identified in the project's ToR. For the IMPALA programme, two groups were defined using the same criteria. Although I divided the FORGEC beneficiaries into three groups, only two different types of interviews (Q1 and Q2) were used, as two groups shared similar characteristics and were not involved in project management. Despite these distinctions, some questions were common to all groups.

Table 9

Interviewees

Type of interview done	Category of direct beneficiaires interviewed (all of them have been participating as “students” in the projects)	Number of people interviewed (FORGEC Project)	Number of people interviewed (IMPALA Project)
Q1	Faculty, professors and trainers in HEI	4	3 These three professors and trainers are also university administrators
Q1	Local actors in charge of the economic and social development (training)	2	
Q2	University senior leaders /senior faculty members / university administrators	4	9
Q3	Evaluators	1	1
Q3	Writers of the ToRs	1	1

I used snowball sampling (Naderifar et al., 2017) to select interviewees. I first contacted the programme or consortium leadership to obtain the contact information of the direct beneficiaries and project management staff who were involved. These individuals were key informants, as they knew the participants and could help me reach them. With their assistance, I contacted university managers, explained the research, and collaborated to identify potential interviewees, including university senior leaders and managers, faculty members, researchers, PhD students, project staff, local actors, and small business representatives.

During the interview process, I encountered two significant challenges. The first was difficulty contacting some local actors due to relocation and labour mobility in the countries where the programmes were implemented. To address this, I interviewed other participants from the same programmes to meet the planned number of interviews. The second challenge involved technological or communication issues. Initially, all interviews were intended to be

conducted online, given that the cases involved two Latin American countries, and the research was conducted in Europe. I conducted as many interviews as possible in person but some of them must be conducted online.

3.4.3.2 Data Analysis.

I analysed the data from each interview. All interviews were recorded and transcribed for qualitative analysis. I asked participants if they wished to review their transcripts, but none requested to do so. Participants did not contribute to the composition or editing of the analysis or results. No individual participant had access to interviews conducted with others, nor were they able to offer insights into similarities or differences within the group. This ensured that the participants' opinions were not influenced by others, allowing them to express themselves freely. This approach also facilitated comparison of the interview results.

Analysis of the interviews with external evaluators: I compared the two interviews, focusing on the importance of the evaluations, the role of the ToR, and the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the evaluation process.

Analysis of the interviews with the ToR writers (implementing unit): I compared the interviews to assess the importance of the ToR, the essential elements to include, and whether the direct beneficiaries were involved in drafting them.

Analysis of the interviews with direct beneficiaries: I conducted a thematic analysis following the six-step process established by Braun & Clarke (2006): becoming familiar with the data (reading and re-reading the interview transcripts), coding (generating initial codes related to my research question), generating themes (based on the initial codes), reviewing themes to structure my observations, defining and naming themes, and finally, conducting the analysis and writing the report.

The initial coding was done manually. I then used Atlas.TI software to complete the analysis. The analysis followed an inductive approach, although I remained mindful of the definitions and concepts introduced in the literature review to minimise bias.

During manual coding, I used structural coding (Saldaña, 2012) to identify large sections of text on broad topics related to my research questions. Later, I applied evaluation coding (Patton, 2002), which allowed me to identify patterns, themes, and insights that could inform decision-making and improve the evaluation process.

Creating a codebook was essential for consistency and transparency in the coding process. After structural coding, I developed a codebook (c.f. Appendix 4) with definitions and examples of each code. I reviewed and expanded the codebook during the evaluation coding process, adding new codes as needed. To minimise bias, and following Saldaña (2012), consensus between coders enriches the research results. I sent the first version of my codebook, along with four interviews (one from each university, representing university managers and other direct beneficiaries), to an external coder. After a meeting with the external coder, I modified my codebook by reducing the number of themes, linking them to my operational questions, merging two codes, and including one code in another thematic category. Following this consensus, as shown in Figure 9, the codebook organises codes by themes, using a hierarchical coding scheme. Some codes encompass related concepts, providing a more comprehensive view of themes. The final analysis identified five themes and 22 codes.

Figure 9

Thematic and Coding of the Direct Beneficiaries' Interviews of this Research

THEMES	SUB-THEME	CODES
Personal Context	Roles and responsibilities	Involvement in the program
		Knowledge of the program
Evaluation and Measurement	Importance of the evaluation	Knowledge
		Importance
	External evaluation	Attitude
		Participation
		Methodology
		Improvement
		Planification
Contextualisation		
Development and Improvement	Results	Communication
	Changes	Positive changes
	Individual improvement	Growth
		Decision-making
		Job change
Institutional improvement	Reflexion	
Collaboration and Interaction	Diversity of perspectives	Exchange of Knowledge
		Empowerment
	Recommendations	Involvement
		Impact measurement
Perception and valuation	Viewpoint	Value
		Effectiveness

Source: Authors' creation

After coding the interviews, I compared the results: first within each institution according to the role of the direct beneficiary, then between institutions participating in the same programme (considering that, in the IMPALA case, the institutions belong to different

countries, so their perceptions could differ). Finally, I compared both cases to determine whether their opinions were similar or different.

Based on the results of these analyses, I created an overview of the evaluations (from their conception to their realisation). This allowed me to assess whether the prescriptiveness of the ToR and in consequence the methodology used the external evaluator influenced the outcome of the evaluations and the perceptions of the direct beneficiaries, and consequently the value they assigned to them. In this research, I have defined “value” as the way direct beneficiaries evaluate the usefulness of the mid-term and final evaluation reports of the ICBHE projects for their institutions and themselves. Thus, this definition is rooted in the historical and sociological context of evaluation, as it integrates how the process of determining value is influenced by different stakeholders (c.f. 2.1.6) and the historical context (c.f. 2.1.4.1). I also considered that the effectiveness of the evaluation could vary between beneficiary institutions or individual beneficiaries, as it would depend on their personal values, which may differ significantly.

3.5 Limitations

1. The number of case studies in the research: A large number of case studies increases the reliability of findings and supports generalization across diverse contexts.
 - It reduces bias by incorporating a wide range of perspectives and scenarios.
 - It can limit the level of detail in the analysis and make it more complex.
 - There’s also a risk of over-generalizing, potentially leading to inaccurate conclusions.

I have chosen to focus on two comprehensive cases rather than a large number of less detailed cases. This approach allowed me to compare and contrast them in detail.

However, the limitation of researching only two case studies means that it may be

difficult to generalise the findings to other comparable capacity building projects. To mitigate that risk, I have compared my findings with the literature on the topic and I have also consulted with experts in the field of capacity building.

2. The number of universities involved in this research. This research is based only on two case studies, involving only four universities. The decision to conduct the study in only four universities and not in all the higher education institutions (HEI) participants in the projects was primarily due to practical considerations in terms of time and resources to support travel.
3. The context of the case studies in the research: Although my interest is in CBHE in general, this research focuses only on two case studies, where the donors are European, and the beneficiaries are from Latin America. Therefore, if the donors or beneficiaries were from other regions or geographical areas, we do not know if the results would be the same or different. This makes it difficult to generalise the findings to similar projects in other areas.
4. Language of the interviews: The official language in both cases was Spanish, and all interviews were conducted in Spanish, except for two (one ToR writer and one external evaluator). For this reason, literal translations of their answers have been included in the text, bearing in mind that some Spanish expressions are difficult to translate.

These limitations significantly impact the study's findings, and a detailed discussion of these limitations will follow in the discussion chapter (c.f. 7.2.4.)

3.6 Ethical Considerations

To conduct this research, I obtained approval from the Ethics Committee of the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore⁷ (Italy) and the Ministerio de Relaciones Internacionales⁸ (Republic of Cuba). Each participant was informed in relation to the topic of the research⁹ and gave their informed consent¹⁰ completed, signed and emailed or hand-delivered to me.

Due to my job position, I was involved in both ICBHE programmes studied. My role in this research is therefore influenced by my self-location, which inevitably shaped some methodological decisions and affected the study's overall outcome (Bukamal, 2022; Darwin Holmes, 2020). Following Merton (1972), I consider myself an insider in this research due to my professional involvement in both case studies. I have personal relationships with several people involved in the projects and possess in-depth knowledge of the programmes and their contexts.

Being an insider researcher offers advantages, such as easier access to information and a better understanding of the context. However, this position also carries risks, such as potential bias or a lack of objectivity (Bukamal, 2022; Darwin Holmes, 2020). In this case, my insider position allowed me to secure authorisation from the Ministry of Higher Education of Cuba to conduct the research and facilitated access to university representatives for interviews.

At the same time, I can also be considered an outsider, as I come from a different country and cultural background. According to Savin-Baden & Howell Major (2013), positionality depends on the researcher's relationship to the investigation, participants, and

⁷ See Appendix 5: Approval from the Ethics Committee of Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

⁸ See Appendix 6: Approval from the Ministerio de Relaciones Internacionales (República de Cuba).

⁹ See Appendix 7: Project information for the participants in the research

¹⁰ See Appendix 8: Consent form of the participants in the research

context. For these reasons, I needed to distinguish clearly between my professional role and my research position. I managed the tension between being critical and supportive of my colleagues and maintained a neutral stance to mitigate the risk of bias.

In this research I have adopted a pragmatic approach, using my unique positionality of being both an insider and an outsider to address the research questions effectively. This approach allowed me to combine two different types of knowledge – first my knowledge of the projects and people; and second my perspective as an individual from a different cultural background. This combination of insider and outsider perspective potentially can lead to a more comprehensive and nuanced insights (Htong Kham, 2024). By adopting a pragmatic stance, I could flexibly choose the most appropriate research methods and adapt my approach as needed (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018; Kaushik & Walsh, 2019; Ponterotto, 2005), recognizing the complexity of my research.

I was aware that some participants might hesitate to express their opinions about the projects or evaluation processes for various reasons. First, they may view me as an outsider representing the implementing unit or donors, and they might fear jeopardising future funding by being candid. Second, they may be reluctant to criticise colleagues or their institutions, given the potential impact on their careers.

To mitigate these risks, I assured participants that their responses would remain anonymous and coded, or pseudonyms would be used to prevent identification. This approach ensured participant anonymity and helped them feel comfortable expressing their views freely. Given the small number of cases and interviews, as explained earlier, all interviews were coded to maintain anonymity, with only the relevant project indicated (FG: FORGEC and IM: IMPALA), without reference to the university or professional profile.

3.7 Conclusion

This chapter has outlined the methodology and methods used in this research. To answer my research question (*How effective is the external evaluation process of International Capacity Building in Higher Education projects in meeting the needs of the direct beneficiaries as perceived by these beneficiaries?*), I based my study on a comparative case study of two CBHE programmes: the IMPALA case and the FORGEC case. Both programmes were funded by European funds and implemented in Latin America

I adopted a comparative case study approach for this research, analysing the ToR and external evaluation reports for both programmes and conducting interviews with various stakeholders, including direct beneficiaries, those responsible for drafting the ToR, and the external evaluators.

From the literature review (c.f. 2.1.4.6) the importance of external evaluations in capacity-building projects is evident for both donors and recipients. This study, however, focuses on direct beneficiaries, seeking to understand the value they assign to these external evaluations. This perspective is distinct from the typical focus in the literature, which tends to consider only project outcomes, without incorporating the views of direct beneficiaries on the evaluation process itself.

Through this research, I aim to fill some of the gaps related to the evaluation process in capacity building in higher education, particularly within the Latin American context.

Chapter 4: Case Study 1. FORGEC

4.1 Introduction

This and the following chapter will set out the two case studies. Each will follow the same format providing an overview of the program, then analysing the evaluation terms of reference, process, external reports, and the views of direct beneficiaries. I apply the methodology described in chapter 3 to each case. The subsequent chapters will be devoted to the comparison of the analyses and presentation of the findings (c.f. Chapter 6 and Chapter 7) that help me to answer the research question of this study.

In this chapter 4, I analysed the Terms of Reference (ToR) of the mid-term and final external evaluations of the FORGEC programme. I also analysed the mid-term and final external evaluation reports and the interviews with direct beneficiaries (programme participants from Universidad de la Habana and Universidad de Camagüey). Finally, I compared the results between participants from the two selected universities for the FORGEC program.

The purpose of these analyses is twofold: to establish the relationship between the ToR and the external evaluation reports, and to determine how the direct beneficiaries perceive the external evaluations.

The findings show how the ToR shape the approach of the external evaluation, although the external evaluator plays a decisive role in determining it. The data also reveal that direct beneficiaries were not involved in the evaluation design process. However, the findings suggest that direct beneficiaries would be willing to participate and involving them in the process would allow the external evaluations to align more closely with their objectives, improving their perception of the evaluations.

4.2 Program Description

FORGEC was a programme under the Annual Action Programme for Non-State Actors and Local Authorities in Development, funded by the European Commission (EC) carried out from 2014 to 2016. The EC supported this initiative as part of its collaborative programme with Cuba, aimed at fostering long-term cooperation in the field of management education between Europe and Cuba. EU development cooperation with Cuba resumed in 2008.

The objective of the FORGEC programme was to enhance the efficiency of Cuban companies by providing high-quality training in European management techniques. At the time the project was approved, new economic operators in Cuba, such as the self-employed and small private cooperatives, were beginning to emerge (European Commission, 2013).

The project was developed in response to rapid and significant changes in the Cuban workforce. Between 2010 and 2022, the workforce grew by 13% due to policies implemented by the Cuban government. These new business operators required training, particularly on their new rights and obligations within the evolving economic context, preparing business models, adhering to new fiscal rules and financial reporting standards, accessing credit, and managing businesses responsibly from social and environmental perspectives. However, there were not enough skilled Cuban trainers available to provide this training.

The Cuban Ministry of Higher Education (MES) addressed this need by implementing the FORGEC programme. As outlined in the methodology chapter, the programme focused on three main pillars: the consolidation alumni programme, the *Programa Eurocubano de enseñanza de gestión* / Euro-Cuban Programme in Management Education (PEEG) programme, and the establishment of methodological offices. These pillars were designed to engage all stakeholders, including university professors responsible for disseminating knowledge, as well as self-employed individuals and cooperative members. Additionally, the

programme ensured that universities would continue to support these actors through the methodological assistance centres.

alumni, university teachers, local actors and university managers.

According to the program (HOME | Forgec-Cuba), the target groups of the program were: “Cuban managers and professors of management, Cuban local actors in charge of the economic and social development, university administrators from Cuban higher education sector, deans, vice-deans and senior representatives of the MES, Cuban universities and other Cuban institutions, Escuelas ramales and Cuban/mixed enterprises, cooperatives, etc.”

Considering the classification of stakeholders in ICBHE projects (c.f. 2.1.3.2), I split beneficiaries in two main categories:

1. *Direct beneficiaries - Institutions.*

The eight Cuban universities where the programme was implemented, and according to the provisions of the contract between the EC and the implementing unit, aimed to develop and strengthen their links with the Cuban local economic environment (state and not state-sectors) through centres that served as bridges between local economic actors in charge of the economic and social development as small business, cooperatives, entrepreneurship) and the HEIs. In line with the project’s objectives, and according to the provisions of the contract, universities benefited from increased communication and the exchange of experiences with other participating universities regarding international cooperation programmes, quality improvement, pedagogical innovations, and the modernisation of higher education.

2. *Direct beneficiaries - Individuals.*

- Managers, professors, and trainers in Cuban universities and *escuelas ramales* (branch schools, specific capacity-building institutions located in university

campuses or in government ministries) enhanced their ability to design and deliver higher-quality lectures by applying the latest management theories and sharing experiences with European counterparts to improve the efficiency of the Cuban companies that will support the transition and modernisation of the Cuban economy. This training provided access to updated materials and improved collaboration opportunities, including the exchange of best practices and innovations, the development of methodologies, and the creation of pedagogical resources and more engaging teaching environments. They also benefited from enhanced support from university staff with deeper expertise in their respective fields. University administrators, after receiving training in university management and support for establishing quality assurance systems, became more aware of the importance of such systems in higher education. They improved both the overall and day-to-day management of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and ensured better resource allocation, including teachers, lecturers, managers, and administrators. This training also supported representatives of the MES and local actors responsible for economic and social development, along with managers from both state and non-state sectors.

- Cuban local actors: They are the persons directly in charge of the development and the support of the emerging non-state sector at the local level. These participants gained a better understanding of the requirements for economic and social development and the needs of non-state actors. They became more aware of the importance of sound resource management, which helped improve their efficiency and professional development. Small enterprises, cooperatives, self-employed individuals, usufruct holders, and business associations benefited from better-trained staff with access to up-to-date management knowledge. They also

gained exposure to innovative pedagogical methods used internationally, such as case studies, simulations, and other resources, as well as access to national and international counterparts sharing similar competencies, skills, and management practices. Through closer ties with HEIs, facilitated by the methodological offices, these actors had access to tailored cooperation on specific programmes or training designed to meet their needs.

4.3 Analysis of the Terms of Reference (ToR) of the external evaluation

As explained in the literature review (c.f. 2.1.4.4) and methodology chapters (c.f. 3.4.2), the ToR form the foundation of external evaluations. While the ToR may specify the methodology to be used, in some cases, the external evaluator is free to choose the most appropriate approach, depending on the nature of the project and the issues to be analysed.

To address my evaluation question, I focused on two aspects of the ToR: how prescriptive they were and whether they stipulated engagement with the direct beneficiaries.

The ToR for the evaluation of the FORGEC programme were written by the implementing unit. During my interview with the person responsible for writing the ToR, they explained that they had used the “Guidance for the Terms of Reference for Impact Evaluation” (European Commission, 2014) as a basis for drafting the TOR for both the mid-term and final evaluations. According to this guidance, the ToR, as a crucial document in the evaluation process, should outline all aspects of the evaluation, including the objectives, the roles and responsibilities of both the evaluator and the evaluation client, and the resources allocated for the evaluation. The ToR should also include “background and context, evaluation purpose and target audience, evaluation objective and scope, evaluation questions and tasks, approach and methodology, timing and deliverables, evaluation team composition and required competencies, management arrangements, budget and payment, and proposal submission”

(European Commission, 2014, p. 3). The guidelines make no reference to beneficiaries in terms of how they're involved in developing the ToR or the evaluation methodology.

4.3.1 ToR Mid-Term Evaluation (MTE) and Final Evaluation (FE)

The ToRs for the MTE FE of the FORGEC programme were both similarly structured around six sections:

1. Background
2. Description of the assignment
3. Expert's profile and expertise required
4. Location and duration
5. Reports
6. Administrative information

When comparing the structure of the FORGEC ToR with the EC's (2014) Guidance for the Terms of Reference for Impact Evaluation, I found that two sections were missing – evaluation questions and tasks and approach and methodology – but some additional information was included.

In **Section 1** (Background), the ToR summarised the programme, outlined the specific project objectives, listed the expected results, and described the project activities and the current status of implementation. A slight difference was found between the MTE and FE in the sub-section "Current Status of Implementation," as the FE referred to specific actions taken between the MTE and the FE.

Section 2 (Description of the Assignment) covered the global objective, the requested services, other mission conditions, and the required outputs. A notable difference was found between the MTE and the FE in the global objective. The FE addressed the results achieved between the MTE and the FE, assessing the progress made in implementing the FORGEC project and documenting lessons learned from the first part of the project. The FE also

evaluated whether the recommendations from the MTE had been implemented. The methodology of the evaluation is clearly stated under “Other conditions of the mission”. Thus, the “approach and methodology” section of the guidelines is included in this section.

In this section I can also find how and what the external evaluator should do in detail: “Ensure the smooth implementation of the evaluation mission, assess, and evaluate the implementation of the FORGEC project, and draw conclusions from the assessment and analyses and reporting”. Thus, according to the EC’s (2014) Guidance for the Terms of Reference for Impact Evaluation, the only aspect that is not included in this section of the ToR is the one related to “target audience”.

Sections 3, 4, 5, and 6 (expert’s profile and expertise required, location and duration, reports, and administrative information) are correctly explained as formal requirements of any ToR. There is also a slight difference between MTE and the FE in Section 5, specifically in the sub-section on content. In this case, the ToR explicitly states that the “final report will present the detailed results of the evaluation and the recommendations for the long-term sustainability of the project’s interventions and its achievements”.

The analysis of the ToR of the MTE of both the FORGEC and IMPALA programs is based on a checklist of 13 questions (Q-ToR) (c.f. Table 5). Most of them refer to specific sections indicated in the guidelines document. However, I included two additional questions: Question 1: *“Have the Terms of Reference been formulated in a clear and understandable manner?”* and Question 12: *“Has the interest of the direct beneficiaries of the program been taken into account in the Terms of Reference?”* With the introduction of the first question (number 1), I try to find out whether the overall structure of the ToR follows a logical order so that it can be easily understood by potential external evaluators. The second question (number 12) refers specifically to the involvement of stakeholders, especially direct beneficiaries in the process of writing the ToR. The reason for introducing this question is to know whether the

funding institution has considered the point of view of the direct beneficiaries and their expectations regarding the evaluation. Note that the interest of the funding institution in the evaluation of the project may differ in some points from the expectations of the direct beneficiaries, and this difference may be a determining factor in the expectations that the direct beneficiaries have of them and the value they ultimately place on them. Question number 8, “*Do the terms of reference indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation?*”, is also prominent as I have explained in the methodology chapter (c.f. 3.4.2.2). The answer to question number 8 will determine the methodology to be used throughout the evaluation and, therefore, the methodology to be followed by the external evaluator. The results of the analysis in both the MTE and the FE are the same. Table 10 illustrates the grade of prescriptiveness of the FORGEC ToR. This categorisation, as explained in the methodology chapter (c.f., p. 96) allows me to know the level of freedom of the external evaluator to use the method the evaluator considered most appropriate.

Table 10

FORGEC. Results of the MTE and the FE Prescriptiveness Analysis

Score	Total number of questions	Answers with that score
1 Non-prescriptive	2	11: Do the Terms of Reference contain the budget allocated to the evaluation and is it in accordance with the evaluation? 12: Has the interest of the direct beneficiaries (no other stakeholders) of the programme been taken into account in the Terms of Reference?
2 Open	0	
3 Semi-prescriptive	6	2: Do the Terms of Reference contain the objective and scope of the programme? 3: Do the Terms of Reference contextualize the programme? 4: Do the Terms of Reference outline the activities and the work plan of the programme? 6: Do the Terms of Reference indicate the stakeholders of the programme?

		8: Do the Terms of Reference indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation? 13: To what extent do the Terms of Reference focus on the assessment of (unintended) outcomes and impacts?
4 Prescriptive	5	1: Have the Terms of Reference been formulated in a clear and understandable manner? 5: Do the Terms of Reference outline the expected results of the programme? 7: Do the Terms of Reference indicate the beneficiaries of the programme? 9: Do the Terms of Reference identify the resources (personal) and timing for the evaluation to be carried out? 10: Do the Terms of Reference specify the deliverables to be produced after the evaluation?

Source: Authors' creation

In total, 11 responses (85%) were rated as semi-prescriptive or prescriptive, and only two responses (15%) were rated as non-prescriptive. These were related to the evaluation budget and the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the evaluation.

I can see that the ToR are highly prescriptive in some aspects, but not in all. Only questions 11 and 12 were rated as non-prescriptive. What I found after analysing the ToR is that the expectations of the direct beneficiaries were not considered when writing the ToR; only the interests of the funding institution were reflected. The person responsible for writing the ToR confirmed this in the interview I had with him: “We don't have some special discussion with the direct beneficiaries when drafting these things.” The ToR clearly follows the mandate of the *Guidance for the Terms of Reference for Impact Evaluation* (European Commission, 2014), which contains no reference to the interests of direct beneficiaries.

4.3.2 Summary of the Analysis of the ToR of the evaluation

These ToR are specific and based on the guidelines of the European Commission. The methodology to be followed by the external evaluator is clearly indicated, as are the specific questions to be answered, considering the large number of prescriptive and semi-prescriptive

answers revealed by the analysis. However, the way in which this methodology is applied is up to the external evaluator, as is the way in which the reports should be presented, although the main points that the evaluation must cover are clearly defined in the ToR.

The analysis of the ToR for the mid-term and final evaluation reveals a significant omission: the opinion and experiences of direct beneficiaries have not been incorporated into the evaluation process. While the ToR explicitly delineates the main objectives of the project and the beneficiaries (section 2, 'Background'), there is no indication of the beneficiaries' involvement in the design phase (the person responsible for writing them confirmed this to me). This gap suggests a prescriptive, top-down approach that lacks participatory engagement with direct beneficiaries impacted by the project.

This approach can have methodological limitations to the evaluation because it can restrict the depth and authenticity of the data collected. This gap can introduce bias and limit the knowledge and impact of the project making the evaluation less nuanced. To avoid this gap, interviews with direct beneficiaries would be essential to understand the project and its context, as their experiences, needs and expectations of the evaluation. This engagement would improve the validity of the evaluation and the ownership of the beneficiaries.

Additionally, in the ToR there is no reference to any structured feedback mechanism or disseminating results to beneficiaries. This point is important for fostering transparency, accountability and empowerment of the beneficiaries. A dissemination plan of the results should be provided to allow the beneficiaries to the results to avoid evaluation being only extractive rather than reciprocal.

Therefore, at this stage, I was only able to answer my research question through interviews with direct beneficiaries.

4.4 Analysis of the Evaluation Process

This section draws on interviews with both the evaluator and the person responsible for writing the ToR to understand how the evaluation was carried out. The external evaluator provided valuable insights into their interpretation of the ToR, their approach to the evaluation process, and their reflections on both the FORGEC project and ICBHE evaluations. The positioning of the external evaluator during the evaluation, as well as his interaction with the direct beneficiaries in their own context and language, led him not only to follow the ToR but also to reflect the interests of the direct beneficiaries in the mid-term and final reports—a point not described in the ToR. Meanwhile, the conversation with the person responsible for writing the ToR provided the context on how the evaluation framework had been developed and insights into the rationale behind certain decisions that had been taken, as well as the intended scope of the evaluations. The combination of both perspectives provides an analysis of how the evaluation process was carried out and the interpretation and implementation of the ToR.

The external evaluator hired to carry out the MTE and FE was someone who was not associated with the program or its stakeholders. The external evaluator used a qualitative approach because the internal project reporting provided significant quantitative data. The research was divided into two phases: (1) documentary analysis of project papers, websites, and relevant materials, and (2) in-depth interviews, focus groups, and questionnaires with a range of stakeholders, institutional visits, and participation in two project events.

To help the reader understand the evaluation report, the external evaluator has used a logical sequence and structure.

The MTE is structured in 5 sections. The **first section** provides background information, and the framework used for the evaluation. The **second section** considers the overall objective of the project “to support the transition of the Cuban economy and improve the efficiency of its companies by providing excellent training in the management techniques

used in Europe”. The **third section** analyses this overall objective via the four key results identified for the different target groups: alumni, university teachers, local actors and university managers. Although the alumni group was formed by university teachers, local actors and university managers, alumni of previous programs as DEADE or DADE. In my research I have only made the distinction between local actors and the ones that works in HEIs (university teachers, managers and trainers) because their profile is totally different. The **fourth section** summarises the achievements according to the project’s evaluation criteria of relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, impact and sustainability, and the fifth section looks to the future and proposes a possible way forward. Each section ends with a set of recommendations which are presented in a unified list following this executive summary (MTE, p. 5).

Thus, the choice of methodology used by the external evaluator was appropriate to meet the requirements of the ToR and the guidelines of the European Commission (2014) Logic Framework.

In fact, the external evaluator set up the report in a way that reflected exactly the expectations of the logic framework. And then integrated into that, that project objectives as well. So formally, the way the report was set up in its structure reflected both the logic framework guidelines from EC and the project objectives themselves.

According to the FORGEC external evaluator, the success of an evaluation is based on four key elements: the knowledge of the cultural context by the external evaluator, the formal evaluation carried out, the identification of the value of the evaluation for the different interests of the stakeholders of the programme, and, finally, the role of the evaluator and importance of the evaluation from the evaluator’s perspective.

1. *Knowledge of the context.* The external evaluator was conscious of the limitations of conducting an evaluation in an unfamiliar context: “I was aware of my own

limitations in undertaking this evaluation”. The external evaluator faced also different challenges in relation to the context of the evaluation:

a) Limited prior knowledge: the lack of knowledge of the Cuban institutions and or people involved in the project and that the external evaluator has never been before to Cuba. This required extensive preparation in comparison with typical evaluation work. “I had no knowledge. Not only I had no knowledge of the institutions, or the people involved, but I, it was also my first trip to Cuba I had to do a lot of preparation more than I would normally do ... So, this for me was like entering a new world”

b) Cultural and contextual barriers: The evaluator noticed cultural context and differences in communication that can influence the evaluation process, and the evaluator had to adapt to them: “So, it's one thing if I'm listening to people talking in Europe, or I'm listening to people talking in Cuba....you start to learn, you're in a different culture, things are happening differently.”

c) Lack of diversity perspectives: Despite the total amount of interviews done by the evaluator (more than 200), all the answers were quite similar, and it raised concerns about the diverse perspectives of beneficiaries: “I probably heard, you know, about 200 people talking, I only really got one message, I only got one set of information, there was no diversity in the group”.

2. *The formal evaluation:* The external evaluator emphasised the formal aspect of the evaluation. For the external evaluator follow the guidelines of the evaluation process is necessary to fulfil the contractual obligations between the evaluator and the donors. The evaluation must align with the formal requirements and meets the stakeholders' expectations (European Commission, 2006). Considering the answer of the external

evaluator, he is the responsible to choose to fulfil only this requirement or guidelines or expand them with the needs of the non-representant stakeholders in them.

“From a formal perspective, they're very important because you're signing a contract with the project management, they have expectations..., they have a set of expectations around what kind of evaluation they want, and they are paying me to do this evaluation. So, at one level for me, it's very important that, the evaluation report itself reflects exactly what the guidelines aims are both from the funder, and from the projects, let's say learning outcomes or its goal objective. (External Evaluator interview)

3. The value of the evaluation for the different interests of the evaluation users: In my research I discovered that different stakeholders could have different interest in relation to the evaluation (European Commission 2006). In this case the external evaluator recognize not only the interests and needs of direct beneficiaries in relation to the evaluation but also the different value of the project for different stakeholders: “Sometimes the project set out to do certain things, but did it align or not with needs, but perhaps the learning the value they saw was different from what the project had intended”.

In the case of the FORGEC program, the external evaluator perceived the interest and the concern of the direct beneficiaries and tried to build a report not only based in the guidelines of the funding institution but also incorporating the needs of the beneficiaries. The way to know these perceptions is through the external evaluator’s own methodology: “making people feel comfortable and letting them tell their own stories ... Looking at the difference between rhetoric and reality, “looking at what are people saying and what are people not saying?”

4. *The role of the evaluator and importance of the evaluation from the evaluator's*

perspective: The external evaluator describes from his or her point of view that is the role of the evaluator, stressing again the idea of reflecting the needs of the direct beneficiaries: “ So, I am here to extract the value that you have perceived in this project, what has been the value the learning of the project for you, on your terms, according to your needs”

The external evaluator, and according to the MTE and FE reports, used a qualitative approach as the internal project reporting already provided a significant amount of quantitative data. The external evaluator divided the research into two phases for each report:

1) documentary analysis: review of project papers, websites and relevant materials; review of materials produced as part of the project (proposal, logframe, interim reports), review of materials produced by participants (researcher reports), review of materials produced by trainers (final conference report, expert visit reports).

2) in-depth interviews: 2 semi-structured interviews in Brussels (6 people), semi-structured interviews, focus groups and institutional visits at the MES and two project participant institutions in Cuba (80 people), visits (2) to the European Delegation in Havana, participation at launch of PEEG (7th Edition) in Havana, semi structured interviews and focus groups during the study tour in Barcelona (15 people), questionnaires to heads of the *gabinetes* (methodological assistance centres) (6 people), questionnaires to trainers of workshops, seminars and PEEG (15 people), half-day/full day visits to the 6 key universities in Cuba (around 120 people), visit to a Municipal University Centre (around 15 people), meetings with local actors (around 15 people), telephone interview with the European Delegation in Havana (1 person).

With all the information collected, the external evaluator can draft their reports, along with recommendations and conclusions. The euphoria of receiving a positive evaluation can

act as an accelerator, allowing the direct beneficiaries to take ownership of the project. In section 4.6 of this research I will consider whether beneficiaries agreed with this idea. In this way, the evaluation ceases to be a mere formality and can potentially become an agenda for change. For the external evaluator, evaluation is an opportunity to encourage beneficiaries to continue working in such type of initiatives:

An evaluation that is just a formal evaluation is a requirement, of course, you have to meet the requirements of the project, but it's missing an opportunity. Because if the people have a very, very positive experience of the project, then there's energy there, to do more that you can really build on. And if you don't do it immediately, then probably that value gets lost, because nothing happens after the project. And people maybe become disillusioned, disinterested, or whatever, and then you don't get the real value.

In the evaluation of the FORGEC program, we find not only the results expected by the policymakers or the managers of the program but also the value of the project for the direct beneficiaries if they carefully read all the report and the recommendations of the external evaluator. Thus, as the external evaluator said: "...the value of the evaluation process depends very much on the evaluator, and the evaluators' own philosophy", "the evaluation can be a change agent".

An evaluator's approach and beliefs can influence the effectiveness of the evaluation process. Their own philosophy shapes the way in which the evaluation is conducted, the interpretation of data, and the beneficiaries' engagement. When an evaluation is conducted with attention to all the details and stakeholders (including beneficiaries), it can drive meaningful changes by highlighting areas for improvement and fostering a deeper understanding of the project's impact.

4.4.1 Summary of the Analysis of the Evaluation Process

In this case study, it can be argued that the reason why the MTE and FE evaluation could be a success for all stakeholders (including beneficiaries) depends on the role of the evaluator and not only on the methodology used by the evaluator. In particular, the interaction between the external evaluator and the direct beneficiaries facilitated the inclusion of specific information in the external evaluator's reports that addressed the interests of the direct beneficiaries without forgetting the guidelines to be followed by the evaluator and provided by the donors' institution. The external evaluator's role in understanding the context of the project and their relationship with the direct beneficiaries was crucial to the finalisation of the project evaluation reports and their findings.

4.5 Analysis of the Evaluation Reports (ERs)

The analysis of the ERs is another key point of this research. These reports are the only tangible documents assessing the FORGEC programme, and initially, all stakeholders should receive them. The implementing unit and the donors always receive the evaluation reports, as the direct beneficiaries' institutions, but not in some cases the participants of those institutions. According to the interviews with beneficiaries of the FORGEC program, not all of them received them. The 3 participants who have no recollection of the evaluation results are part of the 3 different respondent groups (university administrators, professors, and self-employed individual). So, I can see that it did not depend on the profile, it was just a result of the communication process inside the institutions. The programme's performance was evaluated through the analysis of documents and the interviews, focus groups and visits to all the stakeholders of the program (donors, implementing unit and beneficiaries). The external evaluator must analyse and interpret data to make judgments and inform decision-making. The perception of the direct beneficiaries regarding the evaluation will depend on these reports—not only on the results but also on the questions or topics analysed, the methodology used, and

their own experiences. For these reasons, it is essential to analyse the evaluation reports to understand how the evaluation represented direct beneficiaries' interests and inputs.

To analyse the MTE and FE reports, I conducted two different meta-analysis of both evaluations' reports. In both cases, I divided the questions into three main categories: impartiality (one question regarding the type of evaluation conducted: internal or external), equity (three questions regarding how the evaluation was formulated and its accessibility), and quality (78 questions split into nine different categories aimed at verifying the established processing guidelines). In both cases, I only analysed the quality category, as the first two categories relate to the general approach or accessibility of the reports but do not address specific quality issues. I conducted both analyses using the EV-Form (see Appendix 2)

In the first analysis (question analysis), I examined whether the questions appear in the ToR. This analysis does not show the extent to which they appear, but it reveals which questions are not included in the ToR but are reflected in the external evaluators' reports. In the second analysis, I conducted a meta-analysis by scoring the answers based on the degree of information requested in the questions that appear in the MTE or FE reports (1: does not appear, 2: partially appears, 3: fully appears, 4: requested information appears with additional data, 5: exceeds the required information in the ToR). The comparison between the two cases shows slight differences between the answers, making it impossible to draw definitive conclusions. For this reason, I focused my research only on the results obtained in the meta-analysis that allowed me to know whether the external evaluators strictly followed the ToR or added more information than required when writing their reports and not the meta-analysis that scores the answers based on the degree of information requested in the questions that appear in the MTE or FE reports.

4.5.1 Analysis of the Mid-Term Evaluation Report (MTER)

The MTER was conducted by an impartial external evaluator, following the publication of a public tender on the websites of the implementing unit and the programme. To meet the evaluation requirements defined in the ToR and conduct an efficient evaluation, as indicated by Thomas (cited in Fitzpatrick, 2012), the evaluator first needed to understand the context of the programme and the country where it was being implemented, as the characteristics of each context, in this case, country, can determine specific actions. The external evaluator reflected this prior work:

... For me personally, it was very important to read the documents, all the documents I could get. And I asked the implementation unit for additional documents”. “I had to do a lot of preparation more than I would normally do, perhaps, or an evaluation. I even received the guidelines from the Cuban government around the principles that guide education, but the country, its development and so on.

To achieve the requirements of the ToR and cover all the concrete questions that appear in them the external evaluator divided the evaluation in different sections:

The MTE is structured in 5 sections. The **first section** provides background information, and the framework used for the evaluation. The **second section** considers the overall objective of the project “to support the transition of the Cuban economy and improve the efficiency of its companies by providing excellent training in the management techniques used in Europe”. The **third section** analyses this overall objective via the four key results identified for the different target groups: alumni, university teachers, local actors and university managers. The **fourth section** summarises the achievements according to the project’s evaluation criteria of relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, impact and sustainability, and the fifth section looks to the future and proposes a possible way forward. Each section

ends with a set of recommendations which are presented in a unified list following this executive summary (MTER FORGEC, page 5).

In the first section of the MTER, the external evaluator reflects not only the temporal and geographic dimensions of the project but also its regulatory dimension (p. 9 of the MTER).

The methodology used by the external evaluator is also explained on p. 9 of the MTER: a qualitative approach divided into two phases (documentary analysis and in-depth interviews). The evaluation criteria are split into two parts based on these phases. The first relates to “achieving change and making impact” through the programme’s different actions (p. 10 of the MTER), and the second is based on the DAC criteria (p. 28 of the MTER). This section considers the project’s overall objectives and the four expected results according to five criteria: relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, impact, and sustainability. Although the external evaluator explains the rationale for choosing this methodology (p. 10 of MTER: “The different methods allowed for a cross-checking of the quantitative and qualitative data, which showed a high level of alignment, and also of the different stakeholder experiences, which showed a high level of consistency in terms of perceptions of progress made and recognition of successes and challenges”), we could not find any reference to critiques, risks, or limitations inherent to the chosen method.

On p. 15 of the MTER, the external evaluator included the “Institutionalisation of Activities in Universities” framework (adapted from Davies, 1995), providing insights into the institutions' current positions and offering ways forward, including how this project could help them progress.

The data collection methods and associated individuals are listed on pp. 9 and 10 of the MTER: “Review of materials produced as part of the project (proposal, log frame, interim reports); review of websites (public website and restricted website for project participants);

Semi-structured interviews in Brussels conducted via Skype (4 people); Semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and institutional visits at the Ministry for Higher Education (MES) and two project participant institutions in Cuba (80 people); Visits (2) to the European Delegation in Havana (7th Participation at launch of PEEG Edition); Semi-structured interviews and focus groups during the study tour in Barcelona (15 people); Questionnaires to heads of methodological assistance centres (6 people) and trainers of workshops, seminars, and PEEG (15 people).” However, no reference is made to the coding used for qualitative analysis or the indicators applied during the evaluation.

The external evaluator distinguished the different actions and the audiences they targeted: *jornadas* (alumni), the PEEG programme (university teachers and local actors), and methodological assistance centres (training institutions). This distinction allowed the evaluator to describe the achievements, areas of reflection, recommendations, and conclusions. Thus, the MTER offers recommendations for both the project as a whole and the individual actors but lacks an overall conclusion for the project.

In my view, since this project involves three distinct pillars, the external evaluator chose the most appropriate way to analyse them separately, given that each pillar serves different purposes and involves different actors. With the comprehensive information provided by the external evaluation, supplemented by the evaluator’s additional inquiries, interviews, and data collection methods, the evaluator gained a broad understanding of the project, its activities, outputs, outcomes, and impact. In my opinion, this is a clear and effective way to conduct an external evaluation for a project with multiple objectives across distinct pillars, all connected to the project's overarching goal.

After analysing the MTER, I observed that the external evaluator added new aspects not included or detailed in the ToR. In this analysis, I treated impartiality and equity questions as general matters unrelated to the specific information in the reports.

Reviewing the results of the meta-evaluation, conducted using the EV-Form and focused on specific aspects—such as whether the DAC matrix is provided—I found that most topics required by the MTE ToR are addressed in the MTER, with some areas receiving additional information beyond the ToR’s specifications. In instances where certain information was absent from the MTE report but reviewed in my meta-evaluation, it was often related to two themes: the methodology (e.g., precision of methods, critiques, risks, and limitations) and data reliability (e.g., avoiding duplication and ensuring appropriate data selection). However, other quality criteria, such as data solidity and the credibility of findings, conclusions, and recommendations, were well detailed in the MTER.

It can therefore be concluded that while the external evaluator followed the ToR closely, they did not include more technical details in their analysis but did address additional issues.

4.5.2 Analysis of the Final Evaluation Report

As the FER was conducted by the same external evaluator, the logic remained consistent. The content of the FER is divided into the following sections: background and framework, achieving change – making impact, results, evaluation criteria, and a feasible way forward.

Key achievements and lessons learned across the different universities are outlined in each section, with examples presented as testimonials from the universities involved in the project. Only one or two examples are provided from each university to showcase the diversity of achievements. While these are not fully representative of the individual universities' accomplishments, it would be impractical to mention all activities undertaken. Each university achieved more than is highlighted in the examples. The outcomes are then consolidated in the final section, which presents conclusions and suggests a feasible way forward beyond the project's conclusion.

In this evaluation, the external evaluator focused on the learning outcomes and how these were transferred to benefit both the universities and the local economy. The FER “examines to what extent these recommendations have been integrated and concludes with reflections for the future, given that it is now known that the universities will continue working with MES and EFMD on two new European projects—one on entrepreneurship and another on internationalisation” (FER, p. 9).

Thus, the aim was to evaluate how well the project goals were achieved, how the recommendations from the MTER were incorporated to guide the project's focus, and whether the outcomes were sustainable. Additionally, the evaluation assessed the extent to which acquired knowledge was practically implemented and how individual learning was embedded in institutional structures and processes, providing a solid foundation for future activities aimed at enhancing Cuban managerial capabilities.

The methodology used by the external evaluator is explained on pp. 8 and 9 of the FER: “The approach was qualitative, as the internal project reporting already contained substantial quantitative data on activities and participation levels. The research was divided into two phases: 1) documentary analysis of project reports and relevant materials; interviews with implementing unit; 2) institutional visits to Cuba, including in-depth interviews, focus groups, and presentations with various university stakeholders and local actors, as well as interviews with the European delegation in Cuba.”

I believe that visiting Cuba and meeting with the programme’s participants, along with the EC delegation and MES, enabled the external evaluator to better contextualise the programme and understand both the programme itself and the direct beneficiaries’ needs.

The external evaluator followed the same structure as in the MTER, focusing on the actions undertaken across the four key result areas for different target groups, while also

highlighting short-term impacts, long-term recommendations, and testimonials. The inclusion of testimonials provided tangible examples of various achievements.

In Section 5, “A possible way forward,” the external evaluator not only offers final recommendations but also consolidates outcomes with indications for potential future steps beyond the project’s conclusion.

Including this final section was especially valuable, as it demonstrates how an external evaluator can adhere to the ToR while also introducing new perspectives to enhance the evaluation's relevance for all stakeholders, including direct beneficiaries.

My analysis of the FER mirrors the process used for the MTER. The data shows that the required ToR information is present, with additional insights provided. The EV-Form analysis further reveals that, although the FER does not contain a formal conclusions section, it does include future recommendations and suggestions for next steps.

4.5.3 Summary of the evaluation reports

The data shows that there was an evolution between the MTE and FE reports. The ToR were followed, and all the specific questions that appeared were answered. However, each report focused on different aspects, and it was in the FER that I saw the external evaluator go one step further by presenting not only the required findings but also additional information that could change the perception that the direct beneficiaries might initially have had of an external evaluation. This additional information was the result of discussions and interactions between the external evaluator and the direct beneficiaries. In this case, therefore, the informal involvement of the direct beneficiaries influenced the FER.

4.6 Analysis of the Direct Beneficiaries’ Perceptions

To analyse the perception of direct beneficiaries regarding the external evaluation of the FORGEC project, I conducted 10 semi-structured interviews (face-to-face or online) with direct beneficiaries of the programme. These interviewees were members of two different

universities, and all of them participated in various activities within the FORGEC programme (training courses, meetings, conferences) as explained in the methodology chapter. Three distinct types of profiles were interviewed: university representatives (senior leaders), professors and trainers, and self-employed individuals (known as *cuentapropistas* / entrepreneurs).

To answer the operational questions of my research (c.f. 3.1.2), I focused and analysed four concrete aspects: a) the importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries; b) the impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project; c) the opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out and d) the value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries.

4.6.1 Universidad de la Habana

The interviewees at Universidad de la Habana included two university managers, two professors or trainers, and one self-employed individual. These profiles were selected to represent participants across the three pillars of the project, ensuring a range of perspectives rather than just one type of participant profile.

4.6.1.1. Importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries

To know the importance of the external evaluation for direct beneficiaries I analysed the knowledge that beneficiaries had in relation to the program (personal context) and the knowledge they have in relation to evaluation practices and their relation and position in relation to evaluations (evaluation and measurement)

- Personal Context: All the participants had extensive knowledge of the project, as it was explained to them at the outset and were involved from the beginning, each contributing in different ways based on their professional roles.
- Evaluation and Measurement: All participants were generally familiar with evaluations, though some had only experienced internal evaluations. They defined evaluation

using terms like “objectives,” “results,” and sometimes “impact.” All interviewees agreed that external evaluations are crucial for assessing project outcomes, ensuring appropriate fund allocation, and providing an external perspective.

Es una visión de alguien que no ha estado involucrado directamente dentro en la ejecución, en la realización de ese proyecto, que lo ve, debe ser, por supuesto, como una mirada imparcial a partir de resultados esperados, realmente impactos obtenidos y cómo se han utilizado los recursos que se han puesto en función de ese. Eso lo puede ver un evaluador externo. (FG1).

It is a perspective of someone who has not been directly involved in the execution or implementation of that project, viewing it, of course, with an impartial outlook based on expected results, actual impacts achieved, and how the resources allocated for it have been utilized. This can be seen from the standpoint of an external evaluator.

(FG1)

The participants, despite differing experiences with external evaluations, agree that such evaluations are beneficial for several reasons. These include the assessment of whether the intended results of a project have been achieved, the assurance that funds have been allocated correctly, and the provision of an objective, external perspective on the project. The participants believe that external evaluations, in general and in particular in this project, are of benefit not only to funding institutions, but also to the direct beneficiaries and to the external evaluators themselves. Although their needs have not been considered at the beginning of the process of the evaluation.

The participants demonstrated an overall positive attitude towards this concrete external evaluation. They acknowledged that external evaluators can often identify issues that those directly involved in the project may not perceive or may not prioritise. All the

participants except one professor recalled their involvement in the external evaluation and expressed interest in further engagement with such evaluations.

During the interviews, participants raised several concerns about external evaluations. However, in no case the participants criticised the work done by the external evaluator in this case. First, two of the participants (senior leaders) indicated that the evaluation methodology is frequently pre-established by the external evaluator, as it was in that concrete case, with little or no input from those being evaluated. While the methodology is shared with them during the process, they felt it should be discussed more openly and in advance with them. “La metodología la trae el evaluador. Los evaluadores en los dos casos [MTE y FE] compartieron con nosotros en su momento esa metodología que iban a utilizar. Y después compartieron con nosotros cómo la iban aplicando y el resultado que se obtenía”; “The methodology is provided by the evaluator. The evaluators in both cases [MTER and FER] informed us about the methodology they were going to use at that particular time. And then they told us how they applied it and what the results were” (FG1).

Secondly, three participants (senior leaders and the entrepreneur) emphasised the necessity for a clear understanding of the evaluation criteria. There was a need to establish whether the external evaluation would be limited to the actions undertaken or if a broader consideration of outcomes and impacts would also be incorporated. A clear understanding of the indicators to be measured was essential for effective preparation. “Tengo que saber exactamente qué me viene: cuáles son los indicadores que están siendo objetos de medición”; “I have to know exactly what is coming to me: which indicators are being measured” (FG3). Some participants (a senior leader and a trainer) raised concerns about the time required for evaluations and the necessity of clear guidelines on the involvement of appropriate personnel in the process.

Lastly, three participants (senior leaders and the entrepreneur) emphasised the importance of the external evaluator demonstrating a high level of understanding of both the project and the specific context in which it was implemented. They believe that an external evaluator's familiarity with the local context and circumstances can significantly impact on the fairness and accuracy of the evaluation process. In this evaluation, as I had explained before (c.f. 4.4) the external evaluator had no previous knowledge of the context and as the evaluator explains he/she makes an effort to understand the context and also the beneficiaries.

Tendría que razonar un poco mejor, profundizar un poco mejor a partir de que se tenga en cuenta las circunstancias, los escenarios en los que se produce, en los que se implementa un proyecto, porque hay metodologías muy buenas internacionalmente reconocidas de evaluación de proyectos de cooperación internacional que deben ser adecuados a las características, a las condiciones, a las circunstancias donde se está aplicando. No son las mismas las condiciones de mi país que las condiciones de un país de Asia o de África o de otro lugar. En ese sentido, creo que quizás se pudiera matizar, en cierto sentido, las metodologías (FG1).

The evaluator must reason a bit better, go a bit deeper, consider the circumstances, the scenarios in which a project is produced, in which it is implemented, because there are very good internationally recognised methodologies for evaluating international cooperation projects that have to be adapted to the characteristics, conditions and circumstances in which they are applied. The conditions in my country are not the same as the conditions in a country in Asia or Africa or elsewhere. In this sense, I think that perhaps the methodologies could be nuanced to some extent. (FG1).

This opinion is significant, as beneficiaries are aware from the outset of the degree of knowledge an evaluator has about their context and how this can influence an evaluation. In

recent years and to address this gap, some initiatives have emerged to train evaluators in developing countries.

4.6.1.2. Impact of the External Evaluation Results at Institutions and Individuals

I based my analysis on the answers that participants gave to the topic related to development and improvement, at both institutional and individual level and how the evaluation can provoke changes at both levels.

- Development and improvement: The external evaluation process revealed gaps in the internal institutional communication. Only two out of five participants (one senior leader and a professor) received the evaluation results, recalling feedback sessions or formal documents. This lack of access to the results, which were not linked to specific participants' profiles, could affect those interested in understanding the evaluation and the execution of new projects, which could benefit from lessons learned.

Despite these communication issues, participants observed positive changes because of the evaluation process. When we talk about personal changes, we must differentiate between changes that can occur as a direct consequence of participation in a programme and changes that can occur because of the evaluation results. These changes included shifts in attitudes, perspectives, and mindsets that influenced both personal growth and institutional dynamics.

According to three participants (one senior leader, one trainer and the entrepreneur), in general, personal growth influenced professional development and was reflected in their behaviours and approaches to work (professional growth and decision-making improvements). “Yo creo que sí. Yo creo que todos, por lo menos lo que yo vi y aprecié en muchos actores directo, incluido yo mismo, nos mejora, nos mejora sobre todo el tema de la evaluación.”; “I think that everyone, at least what I saw and appreciated in many direct actors, including myself, improves us, especially the issue of evaluation” (FG2). Two of the five participants

(one senior leader and one trainer) experienced job changes within their institutions, although it was unclear if the changes were directly related to the evaluation.

Finally, three participants (one senior leader and the two trainers) also considered that the evaluation, in general, stimulated a period of institutional reflection, leading to gradual internal policy changes or adjustments. They also recognised the interrelated nature of personal and institutional change, with improvements flowing in both directions. “Hay cambios de todo tipo. Hay cambios institucionales, hay cambios personales, hay cambios de todo tipo. De todo tipo porque realmente es, yo diría, un desarrollo de institución a persona y de persona a institución.”; “There are all kinds of changes. There are institutional changes, there are personal changes, there are changes of all sorts. All kinds, because it's really, I would say, going from institution to person and from person to institution” (FG4).

4.6.1.3. Opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out

This topic is quite important, because direct beneficiaries are the ones that receive the action and its impact. Therefore, their opinion is crucial to know their position and ideas in relation to that topic. To answer that topic, I have focused on different aspects that I have included under the title collaboration and interaction.

- Collaboration and interaction.: Some participants highlight the importance of incorporate diverse perspectives in the design of external evaluations in general and also in this concrete evaluation. Participants stress that sharing knowledge is essential to achieve this diversity, and they can provide the external evaluators with information and insights related to the program that the external evaluator may not have had access to. Three participants (senior leaders and a trainer) share the idea that during this exchange, actual objectives of the evaluation and the indicators that will be used shall be clarified. “Como te dije, ser

preguntados y chequear nuestros objetivos o los objetivos que debe tener la evaluación.”; “Be asked and check our objectives or the objectives that the evaluation must have” (FG2).

For some participants (senior leaders and one trainer), the relationship between those interviewed and those evaluating should be based on fairness and empathy. Empathy between them enhance evaluation process. Some participants agree that being involved from the very beginning of the external evaluation, as it was not the case, allows them to take ownership of the project and of the evaluation itself.

Si los beneficiarios participan en el diseño, yo creo que el diseño es más rico, es más preciso, además es más atractivo, hay más compromiso. Porque no es lo mismo construir el proyecto y decirle a alguien esto te va a ser bueno y esa persona tiene que empezar a creer, a confiar en el proyecto, que si participó en el diseño sabe todo lo que le puede brindar y además te facilita todo el proceso (FG3).

If the beneficiaries participate in the design, I believe the design is richer, more precise, and more attractive. There is more commitment because it is different to build the project and tell someone this will be good for you, and that person has to start believing and trusting in the project, than if they participated in the design and know everything it can offer them. Additionally, it facilitates the entire process (FG3).

All the participants agree that being involved in the design of the evaluation ensure that their needs will be reflected in the external evaluation and to include any relevant issues that may have been overlooked. This collaboration can lead to a more specific and accurate evaluations, as it helps external evaluators to better understand the context of the project and the specific interests of the direct beneficiaries. “Como ya te he dicho debe haber una conversación entre todas la partes. Por lo tanto la metodología, aunque venga dada, debe ser variable... Es decir, que también se refleje nuestras necesidades en ella. Ser preguntados, hablar desde un inicio.”; “As I have already mentioned, there must be a conversation between

all parties. Therefore, the methodology, even if predetermined, must be variable... That is, it should also reflect our needs. Being asked, speaking from the beginning” (FG2). Two participants (one senior leader and one trainer) suggest that external evaluations also need to include the impact not only on the higher education institutions involved in the project, but also on the broader societal context.

4.6.1.4. Value and Effectiveness of External Evaluation for Direct Beneficiaries

This point is the main question of this study, and the concepts of value and effectiveness are the ones discussed in the semi-structured interviews with the direct beneficiaries.

Perception and Valuation: Three of the participants (one senior leader, one trainer and the entrepreneur) perceive the value of an evaluation as its capacity to reflect the successes and the unachieved objectives of the programme. For them, the value is positive if the external evaluation shows positive results and negative if it shows failures. However, for the self-employed individual, evaluation has a different meaning as a tool to assess the current state of their business—positive results indicate that the business is working well, while negative results suggest otherwise. Similarly, in all three cases, the value of the external evaluation is associated with its role in fostering improvement by providing a reference point for further progress.

Una evaluación de un proyecto, la importancia o el valor que debe tener sobre todo es ver qué cosas no han salido bien, o qué cosas aún son insuficientes en lo que el proyecto ha podido alcanzar, para sobre esa base seguir generando proyectos que permitan elevar el nivel de calidad (FG3).

The importance or value of a project evaluation lies primarily in identifying what has not gone well or what remains insufficient in what the project has achieved. This

provides a basis for generating new projects that aim to elevate the level of quality (FG3).

For all the interviewees except the entrepreneur emphasised that an effective external evaluation should demonstrate the achievement of the programme's objectives, the efficient use of resources, and incorporate feedback from participants and beneficiaries.

Para que sea eficaz, bueno, tienes que primero preguntarles a los beneficiarios, a los actores, a la gente que recibió el servicio. Segundo, también a los que participaron, para qué tal, cómo fue la experiencia. Y sin duda, un proyecto tiene que contar innecesariamente, aunque tenga mucha voluntad y deseos, tiene que tener recursos porque realmente moviliza un grupo de cosas importantes (FG3).

To be effective, well, you first have to ask the beneficiaries, the stakeholders, the people who received the service. Second, also those who participated, how it went, what the experience was like. And undoubtedly, a project must necessarily, even if it has a lot of will and desire, have resources because it really mobilizes a group of important things (FG3).

In this concrete case some participants explained that this exchange of information was done during the interviews.

4.6.1.5. Summary of the Results Universidad de la Habana

If I compare the interviews between the three different profiles of interviewees, I can see that the answers of the senior leaders are quite similar; both talk about the same topics and have similar opinions. We find fewer similarities between the professors or trainers and their reflections, and finally, the self-employed person has a different point of view on some concrete topics, with his answers referring more to his own business experience and its improvement through the results of the evaluation. In this case, his profile, which is completely different from the others, is responsible for his answers.

After the analysis of the interviews, I can summary the aspects that helped me to answer the operational questions saying that all participants are aware of the importance of the external evaluation and its results as a means of improvement. The results of external evaluations can, after a process of reflection, have a gradual impact on the institution and on individuals (changing the way of thinking or acting). Before the evaluation, the external evaluator has to know the context in which the programme takes place, because of the cultural differences and other context issues that can influence both the project and the evaluation. The needs of the direct beneficiaries should be considered when designing the evaluation, and the impact of the results should be part of the evaluation. External evaluations are valuable for direct beneficiaries because they help them know the results and impact of the project and, in some cases, what needs to be changed or improved in the future at the level of project implementation. However, they could be much more valuable if they included the needs of direct beneficiaries in relation to these evaluations.

4.6.2 Universidad de Camagüey

In this analysis, the same logic was followed as at the University of Havana. Three different profiles were chosen to obtain the opinions of the three groups of direct beneficiaries of the project: two senior leaders, two professors or trainers, and one self-employed individual. In the same way, the same four operational questions have been answered based on the same issues.

4.6.2.1 Importance of External Evaluation for Direct Beneficiaries

- Personal Context: All the participants interviewed at the University of Camagüey were well-informed about the project and its objectives from the very beginning. Additionally, all of them participated in some activities related to the programme.
- Evaluation and Measurement: All participants were familiar with evaluations, although some had never been involved in an external project evaluation, only in internal

evaluations within their own institution. Their definitions of evaluation varied but consistently included 'objectives' and 'results', with some also mentioning 'impact'.

When asked specifically about the importance of external evaluations, all the participants agreed on their necessity. All the participants except the entrepreneur stressed the importance of knowing the results and impact of project implementation, and the senior leaders emphasised the justification of the funds received. Some participants (a senior leader, a trainer and the entrepreneur) also highlighted how the evaluation results could impact future actions.

Evidentemente las evaluaciones son útiles. Porque le permiten al evaluador identificar lo positivo y lo negativo en la, en la gestión del proyecto, sobre todo cuando es un grupo o una entidad externa incluso al país, le permite saber si se está utilizando correctamente todos los fondos, pero también en un momento para mí tan importante como ese, si ha habido un pacto en relación con lo que se pretendió al inicio ... Por lo tanto, a mi juicio, la evaluación siempre es importantísima tanto para los que evalúan como para los evaluados (FG6).

Obviously, evaluations are useful. Because they allow the evaluator to identify the positives and negatives in the management of the project, especially when it is a group or an entity external to the country, it allows them to know if all the funds are being used correctly, but also at a moment as important as that, if there has been an agreement regarding what was intended at the beginning ... Therefore, in my opinion, evaluation is always very important both for those who evaluate and those who are evaluated (FG6).

Three out of five participants (senior leaders and one trainer) had a positive attitude towards external evaluations. Only one participant (one trainer) had not been involved in an external evaluation but expressed an interest in learning from the experience. All of them have

a positive view of the external evaluation done in this project by the external evaluator as it explains if the objectives have been achieved and the accountability of the project, although the impact of the project has not been evaluated, and it was one of their expectations.

Regarding evaluation methodology, three of them (senior leaders and one trainer) noted that it is typically pre-determined by the external evaluator, as it was the case in this project: “Viene con idea y metodología ya cerradas: vamos, la metodología propia.”; “The evaluator comes with a pre-established idea and methodology: well, his own methodology” (FG7). In this case, for example, the use of theory of change in the evaluation process surprised the senior leaders. According to all the participants except the entrepreneur, the external evaluation (with the participation and opinion of the beneficiaries) should measure the progress of project objectives, and the impact achieved: “En la evaluación ex post, yo creo que es donde se debe referir es al cumplimiento de los objetivos. Y ahí se debe hacer, yo creo, una indagación bastante seria de verificar, sobre todo, que los objetivos realmente se hayan alcanzado.”; “In the ex-post evaluation, I believe that it should refer to the fulfilment of the objectives. And there, I think, a very serious enquiry should be made to verify, above all, that the objectives were really achieved” (FG9).

Three participants emphasised the importance of feedback as a tool for implementing improvement projects, with internal evaluations particularly important to them. “Es importante conocer esos resultados porque se nos identifican los puntos fuertes de los puntos débiles. Sobre todo, nos interesan los puntos débiles para tratar de mejorar.”; “It is crucial to know these results because they identify both the strengths and weaknesses. Particularly, they are interested in the weaknesses to work on improvements” (FG6).

Two participants (one senior leader and one trainer) were concerned about the planning of the evaluation and stressed the need for clarity about how the evaluation would be carried out and the indicators that would be used. Although there was no mention of logistics

concerns, two participants (senior leaders) discussed the importance of contextualising the project during the evaluation. They stressed that the evaluation should be based on objective reality but should also consider the specific context in which the project is implemented.

Yo sé que excelencia es excelencia en cualquier lugar del mundo, pero en principio tenemos que adecuarnos o debemos adecuarnos primero a las características del país y para hacerlo a veces en algunos indicadores deben ser rejuntados, vamos a decir así, o criterios en el día deben ser rejuntados. (FG6).

I know that excellence is excellence anywhere in the world, but in principle we have to adapt ourselves or we must first adapt ourselves to the characteristics of (the country) and in order to do so sometimes some indicators must be brought together, let's put it this way, or criteria must be brought together on a daily basis (FG6).

4.6.2.2. Impact of the External Evaluation Results on Institutions and Individuals

- **Development and Improvement:** All participants, including the one not involved in the external evaluation, confirmed that they had access to the results of the evaluation. This means that the communication process was carried out correctly and influenced all the direct beneficiaries.

In general, participants have a positive view of change at both personal and institutional levels, seeing it as a means of improvement.

At an individual level, external evaluations help individuals learn and adopt new work practices. Two participants (one senior leader and one trainer) noted that evaluations introduced them to new methodologies that could be applied in future professional contexts. The entrepreneur highlighted that these experiences could influence not only personal practices but also institutional ones. Three of the five interviewees (one senior leader and the two trainers) from this university changed their roles between the time of the evaluation and

the present. However, it remains unclear whether these changes were due to their participation in the project, the evaluation, or structural changes within the university.

Institutional changes often follow a period of reflection after evaluations, as observed by three participants (one senior leader, a trainer and the entrepreneur) in their institution. Overall, evaluation promotes growth at several levels, from individual learning to institutional improvement.

...un cambio significativo, no sólo a nivel de personal o de infraestructura, infraestructura no, sino la forma de asumir el trabajo con los directivos, la preparación de los directivos, los nuevos métodos, trabajar con profesores europeos diversos, tecnología, ayudó mucho al colectivo. O sea, yo lo veo a nivel personal, a nivel de grupo y a nivel de universidad. En todos los casos ayudó (FG7).

...a significant change, not only at the personal level or infrastructure, not infrastructure, but the way of working with the directors, the preparation of the directors, the new methods, working with different European teachers, technology, helped the collective a lot. In other words, I see it on a personal level, on a group level and on a university level. In all cases it helped (FG7).

Only one participant (a trainer) pointed out that changes may depend on the context (in this case the country), as he did not see any changes in his country's institutions, but he did see changes after carrying out evaluations in other countries.

4.6.2.3. Opinion of the Direct Beneficiaries in how the Evaluation Should be carried out

- Collaboration and Interaction: Some participants (senior leader and trainers) emphasized that exchanging ideas at the start of the project and during the evaluation design could clarify key issues, aligning everyone with the same definitions and expectations. “Para saber, en hasta qué punto estamos o no estamos desviados de lo que debía obtenerse o la

aspiración de esos evaluadores externos, o los criterios de esos evaluadores externos.”; “To understand to what extent we are or are not deviating from what should be achieved or the aspiration of those external evaluators, or the criteria of those external evaluators” (FG8).

The empowerment of direct beneficiaries becomes evident when they express their views on co-creating the external evaluation. All the participants except one trainer suggest changes or additions to the evaluation criteria, with one specifically pointing out that they are a stakeholder in the project's ecosystem. This sense of involvement and empowerment also serves as a driver of motivation, especially when beneficiaries see the first results of the project, according to another participant. However, all agreed that it was important to be more involved in both the programme and the evaluation process although in this case they miss this involvement in the moment of planning the evaluation.

All the participants except one trainer, strongly supported the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the creative process of designing the evaluation, believing that it could help adapt and complement the evaluation criteria to better reflect the beneficiaries' interests and circumstances. One trainer noted that this collaborative approach could lead to innovative ideas, improving both project development and evaluation effectiveness. Similarly, a senior leader suggested that in order to make the evaluation more comprehensive and relevant, the process could be enriched by adding new elements or adjusting the evaluation criteria.

“Pudiese enriquecerse el proceso si le damos la posibilidad. No de pactar totalmente los objetivos de la evaluación, pero sí de incorporar nuevos ítems o de quizás modificar algún elemento, alguna pregunta, algún criterio de evaluación.”; “The process could be enriched if we give the it the opportunity. Not to agree completely on the objectives of the evaluation, but to include new elements or perhaps to modify some element, some question, some evaluation criterion" (FG6).

According to three participants (senior leaders and one trainer), the external evaluation of the FORGEC program must be a reflection of the real impact the programme has had on society. Without this data, the results of the evaluation were incomplete. It was difficult to truly assess the effectiveness of the programme.

4.6.2.4. Value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries

- Perception and Valuation: Apart from the self-employed participant, who did not express an opinion, the other participants were generally positive about evaluations in general. A positive evaluation is seen as proof that a project has been carried out successfully and highlights the strengths of the university. Therefore, external evaluations are highly valued. For two participants, the value of this concrete evaluation lies in learning new evaluation methods that can be applied in their own contexts.

All participants stressed the importance of external evaluations. Their effectiveness depends on how well they reflect the project's ability to achieve results. One senior leader noted that external evaluations should confirm the outcomes set at the project's outset and assess beneficiary satisfaction, as it was done in this evaluation.

O sea, en esencia, que transformaciones ocurrieron para ver la eficacia, y sobre todo ver cuáles fueron las transformaciones: que ocurrió dentro de ese proceso y si realmente esas transformaciones estaban acordes con las esperadas, fueron superiores y el nivel de satisfacción de los beneficiarios con esas transformaciones es lo que realmente a mi entender determina si un proyecto fue eficaz si valió la pena verlo ejecutado (FG7).

That is, in essence, what transformations occurred to see the effectiveness, and above all to see what the transformations were: what happened within that process and whether those transformations were really in line with what was expected, whether they were superior and the level of satisfaction of the beneficiaries with those transformations is

what really determines, in my opinion, whether a project was effective, whether it was worth seeing it implemented (FG7).

4.6.2.5. *Summary of the Results Universidad de Camagüey*

In this case, for all but one of the topics, I can see that the senior leaders gave similar answers. However, there is a noticeable difference between the trainers or professors, as they expressed different ideas and answers. The self-employed participant also gave distinct responses, likely due to his unique profile.

After analysing these five interviews, I can say that external evaluation is important for all the interviewees always, including the evaluation of this program although some participants miss some criteria, or the impact has not been evaluated. They all received the results, although not all of them participated in the evaluation, and for them, the objectives of the evaluation must be clear: whether the objectives of the project have been achieved or not. The results of the external evaluation impact the institutional level (changes or modifications can be made, e.g., the creation of new infrastructure related to capacity building for self-employed persons after the programme) and the individual level (interrelation between the personal and professional levels). There is also a great consensus in the idea of involving the direct beneficiaries in the design of the evaluation. Although the evaluations currently have a positive value, in my opinion, this value can be increased if the evaluations have a more precise criterion in defining their objectives. The external evaluator's knowledge of the context is key to such evaluations.

The effectiveness of the evaluation is linked to the objectives defined in the methodology, and the value of the evaluation is linked to its outcome and impact. It can be seen as an example to be followed. By involving direct beneficiaries not only in the evaluation but also in its design, evaluations can be made more accurate and effective for them.

4.6.3 *Summary of the Analysis of the Direct Beneficiaries' Perception*

If we compare the answers of the senior leaders of both universities, I can see that they are quite similar. Their answers are focused on strategic and administrative approaches. In the case of professors or trainers, their answers are not so similar—some align with the perspectives of the university managers, while others offer different views. The self-employed participant's insight diverges from those of the internal university stakeholders and is based more on his own practical experience.

All interviewees recognised the importance of external evaluation to determine whether the project's objectives, outcomes, and impacts have been achieved and to ensure accountability. In both cases (but not to the same extent), direct beneficiaries assume that external evaluations are conceived in a closed manner. However, empathising with the external evaluator can make the evaluation process smoother and allow new ideas to emerge. In the case of the FORGEC program I can observe how the external evaluator although his unknowledge of the context, try to understand the context through the conversations and discussions with direct stakeholders. In both cases, direct beneficiaries explain the potential benefits of involving them in the evaluation design phase. This idea suggests that evaluations could become more accurate and relevant to direct beneficiaries.

In both universities, the effectiveness of the evaluation was intricately linked to the outcomes and whether they met clearly defined objectives, impacts, and improvement goals. Value is perceived as either positive or negative, depending on the evaluation results. In both cases, the idea of value is more related to the impact the evaluation can have on their institution than to their perceived value.

4.7 *Summary of the Results*

To answer my research question (How effective is the external evaluation process of International Capacity Building in Higher Education projects in meeting the needs of the direct

beneficiaries, as perceived by these beneficiaries?), I analysed the ToR, the evaluation process, and the evaluation reports of the FORGEC programme. I also conducted 10 semi-structured interviews with direct beneficiaries from two different universities involved in the FORGEC programme.

After analysing the ToR of the external evaluation, the data show that these ToR are very prescriptive and follow the EC guidelines. The methodology is clearly defined, but the external evaluators have flexibility in its application and the presentation of the report. There is no reference to direct beneficiaries in terms of their involvement in the design of the ToR; they are only mentioned in the project background section. Thus, both the MTE and FE ToRs do not consider the expectations of direct beneficiaries in their design.

In my opinion, the interaction between the external evaluator and the direct beneficiaries has played a key role in including specific information in the evaluation reports that addresses the interests of the beneficiaries. The external evaluator's interest in understanding the project's context and his relationship with the direct beneficiaries—developed through conversations and interactions—was crucial to completing the evaluation reports and achieving meaningful results. Including not only the results required by the EC but also additional information made the reports more tailored to the needs of the direct beneficiaries. For this reason, the success of an evaluation does not depend solely on the methodology used by the external evaluator.

The opinions of direct beneficiaries regarding their participation in the evaluation design confirm that evaluation results can be more accurate when beneficiaries are involved. Direct beneficiaries will perceive the external evaluation as more closely aligned with their reality and not merely as a formal requirement.

Direct beneficiaries measure the effectiveness of external evaluations based on whether the project's objectives and results have been achieved. The value of the evaluation depends

on the results—whether positive or negative. In my opinion, the effectiveness of evaluations could be significantly improved if the needs of the direct beneficiaries regarding the evaluation were considered during the process of writing the ToR.

Chapter 5: Case Study 2 – IMPALA

5.1 Introduction

This chapter follows the same format that the previous one. As in Chapter 4, the purpose of this analysis is double: to establish the relationship between the ToR and the external evaluation reports, and to determine how the direct beneficiaries perceive the external evaluations. Therefore, I have analysed the Terms of Reference (ToR) of the mid-term and final external evaluations of the IMPALA programme. I also analysed the mid-term and final external evaluation reports and the interviews with direct beneficiaries (programme participants from Universidad Agraria de la Habana and Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá).

The data show that, in this evaluation process, the external evaluator was given the opportunity to propose the methodology. As in the FORGEC case, direct beneficiaries were not involved in the design of the evaluation. Although the evaluation seems to be highly effective according to the European Commission's guidelines, its perceived value among direct beneficiaries may be lower.

5.2 Program Description

The IMPALA project (c.f. 3.3.1.2) was a capacity-building programme funded by the European Commission (EC) and it was carried out between 2018 and 2022. Its objective was the implementation of a quality framework for measuring the impact of Higher Education Institutions in three Latin American countries (Colombia, Cuba, and Panama) as direct beneficiaries of the action. The purpose of this initiative was to enhance the Quality Assurance (QA) systems that these institutions already had and to promote a greater culture of impact within them. In total, 13 institutions benefited from this programme for five years (as the programme lasted one year longer than initially planned due to the Covid situation).

It is noteworthy that the participating institutions were not homogeneous, including both public and private institutions, those affiliated with religious orders, as well as secular ones. Similarly, I can differentiate two groups of countries: Colombia, representing Latin America, with a population of over 51 million inhabitants¹¹, versus two Central American countries, Panama and Cuba, with populations exceeding 4¹² and 11¹³ million inhabitants each.

However, in all three countries, the concept of the “third mission” and Higher Education (HE) or university is closely intertwined. It not only appears in the mission of all universities but also manifests in their offering of services to the community as part of their core mission (Hunter et al., 2022). The measurement of the impact of these actions aimed to modify, correct, and enhance these services through the training of responsible individuals in these institutions (senior leaders), as well as faculty and staff specialists in the Third Mission. Thus, in this programme, I can differentiate, according to the classification of stakeholders in ICBHE projects (c.f., p. 33), two main categories of beneficiaries:

1. Direct beneficiaries - Institutions

The thirteen Latin American HEI where the program was implemented. HEIs can considerably enhance their impact on their local environment by understanding and addressing local needs while engaging in innovative and effective activities. Initially focused on the third mission of universities, these insights can also enhance the quality of teaching and research, benefiting the wider educational community with the support of regulatory bodies. The introduction of new tools, methodologies, and

¹¹ <https://datosmacro.expansion.com/paises/colombia>

¹² <https://datosmacro.expansion.com/paises/panama>

¹³ <https://datosmacro.expansion.com/paises/cuba>

guidelines enables more effective impact measurement (impact was not incorporated previously) and strategic adaptation. Staff training in impact assessment and maximisation enhances institutional efficiency and relevance in social and economic contexts. Institutions can benefit from this programme by improving their existing quality assessment system. The uptake of impact measurement concepts is driven not only by regulatory bodies and top management but also by other staff categories who experience its benefits in their daily activities. Involvement in capacity-building initiatives has been demonstrated to enhance individual capabilities and institutional performance, thereby facilitating cultural transformation. Furthermore, institutions that demonstrate the impact of their actions are more likely to attract funding from a variety of donors, which, in turn, supports the implementation of new activities related to the third mission and enhances the institution's societal contribution and positioning (DFID, 2010; Groot and Molen, 2001 cited in Enemark & Williamson, 2012).

2. Direct beneficiaries - Individuals

HEIs staff who participated in the programme included members of the regulatory bodies responsible for the assessment and accreditation of universities, as well as senior management, faculty, and specialist staff involved in programme management, project units, and external relations. Some of these individuals were involved in the design and implementation of specific aspects of the programme. The courses have enabled all participants to gain insights into the ways in which their institution's activities can be evaluated and to identify a greater number of activities/projects that can be targeted at local communities and their impact. They have also acquired the knowledge required to launch new ventures and to disseminate information.

5.3 Analysis of the Terms of Reference (ToR) of the Evaluation

The ToR, as I explained in the literature review (c.f. 2.1.4.4) and methodology chapters (c.f. 3.4.2), is the guiding document for the project evaluation. In the case of the IMPALA programme, there was only one set of ToR that applied to both the Mid-Term Evaluation (MTE) and the Final Evaluation (FE) of the programme. Therefore, the same external evaluator was selected for both evaluations. This ensured that the evaluation criteria remained consistent. It is also worth noting that these ToR were written in Spanish. My understanding is that although Spanish is not a requirement for the evaluator in the ToR, it may be a decisive factor in the selection of one evaluator over another. The reason for this is that if the evaluator travels to the direct beneficiary countries, they can carry out their work in Spanish and speak the same language as the direct beneficiaries, making communication and interaction easier. In this evaluation, the direct beneficiaries perhaps would not see the evaluator as a representative of power, of the North, but as someone more equal to them, that speak the same language and perhaps share some common cultural characteristics. The relationship between evaluator and beneficiaries could be seen more equal by beneficiaries, and the idea of equal partnership of stakeholders of a program (Nossum, 2016) could be glimpsed in this case.

According to the interview with the person responsible for writing the IMPALA ToR, these ToR were based on the generic guidelines suggested in the EC, Project Cycle Management Guidelines (2004), which outline the following sections: background to the assignment, objectives of the study/mission, issues to be investigated, methodology, expertise required, reporting requirements, and work plan and schedule.

5.3.1. ToR Mid-Term and Final Evaluation

The ToR for the MTE and FE of the IMPALA project were drafted by Universitat Ramon Llull, as co-responsible for WP6 (Quality) of the IMPALA project. These ToR were structured in a total of seven sections:

1. Background
2. Context and project description
3. Evaluation description: Duration of the evaluation, content of the evaluation report
4. Expert's profile
5. Budget
6. Intellectual property
7. Proposal submission

I observed that there are very few subsections in the ToR. Therefore, it was only through this analysis that I can determine whether these ToR are prescriptive or not for carrying out the assessment.

In **sections 1 and 2** (background and context and project details), I found the details of the project (administrative and descriptive aspects) and the focus of the evaluation (general and specific aspects), which will help the evaluator make recommendations for future actions.

In **section 3** (evaluation description), I found not only the schedule and location of the evaluation but also the main points that the reports must include. All the information was included in only one sentence, but there was no reference to any type of methodology to be followed by the evaluator, although some of the DAC criteria are included: “The evaluation report should include an executive summary, evaluation objectives, evaluation typology, a brief description of the assessed intervention, the methodological approach and techniques used, an analysis of the context in which the intervention takes place, and conclusions

regarding effectiveness, efficiency, social and economic impact, technical and financial viability, and sustainability after monitoring has been conducted”.

The **sections 4, 5, 6, and 7** (expert’s profile, budget, intellectual property, and proposal submission) although concise, contain all the information required in the EC, Project Cycle Management Guidelines (2004).

From the analysis of the ToR and the data obtained, I could say that the evaluator was dealing with a non-prescriptive ToR. The external evaluator was given complete freedom to use the methodology that he considered most appropriate to achieve the objective of the evaluation. However, I wanted to compare these results with the ToR of the FORGEC project. Therefore, I need a numerical form to make the comparison.

I used the Q-ToR checklist (c.f. Table 5) with the same thirteen questions I applied I to analyse the ToR of the FORGEC programme, to analyse the ToR of both the MTE and FE of the IMPALA programme. Looking at the thirteen questions of the checklist, I made a first classification of them. I divided them into two main categories. In the first category (questions 1 to 7), we find programme-related questions mentioned in the ToR. The second category focuses on more formal aspects of the evaluation (questions 8 to 13). As explained in chapter 4 (c.f., p.117) I included question 12 (*Has the interest of the direct beneficiaries of the program been taken into account in the Terms of Reference?*) in relation to the participation of the direct beneficiaries in the process of drafting the ToR. After the analysis of the MTE and FE, the results are found to be the same. In Table 11, I analysed the grade of prescriptiveness of the ToR that helps me to determine the level of freedom of the external evaluator to conduct that evaluation.

Table 11

IMPALA. Results of MTE and the FE Prescriptiveness Analysis

Score	Total number of questions	Answers with that score
1 Non-prescriptive	3	6: Do the ToR indicate the stakeholders of the programme? 8: Do the ToR indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation? 12: Has the interest of the direct beneficiaries (no other stakeholders) of the programme been taken into account?
2 Open	2	7: Do the ToR indicate the beneficiaries of the programme? 10: Have the ToR specified the deliverables to be produced after the evaluation?
3 Semi prescriptive	4	1: Have the ToR been formulated in a clear and understandable manner? 2: Do the ToR contain the objective and scope of the programme? 4: Do the ToR outline the activities and the work plan of the programme? 13: To what extent do the ToR focus on the assessment of (unintended) outcomes and impacts?
4 Prescriptive	4	3: Do the ToR contextualize the programme? 5: Do the ToR outline the expected results of the programme? 9: Do the ToR identify the resources (personal) and timing for the evaluation to be carried out? 11: Do the ToR contain the budget allocated to the evaluation, and is it in accordance with the evaluation?

Source: Authors' creation

After reviewing the responses, 8 responses (62%) were classified as semi-prescriptive or prescriptive, so the information that appears is requested in the ToR. Of these 8 responses, 5 were responses to programme-related questions. Only 3 of them were related to the formal aspects of the evaluation.

One of the points I would also like to highlight is the questions that received a score of 1 (non-prescriptive), particularly question number 8, which refers directly to the methodology (*“Do the Terms of Reference indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation?”*). The ToR stated that the reports should explain the methodological approach and the techniques used but did not detail how to conduct the evaluation. According

to the ToR, the evaluator did not know who the stakeholders and the beneficiaries of the project were—only the countries to which they belonged. As a result, the evaluator should have asked the consortium or the implementing unit for more information and details about the project.

The data from this analysis show that many questions related to the programme can be considered semi-prescriptive or prescriptive because the information that appeared in the ToR aligns with the requirements in the EC guidelines (2004).

5.3.2 Summary of the Analysis

The data show that these ToR are concise and clear in some sections but incomplete. There is no reference to the stakeholders or the direct beneficiaries of the project, nor does it include any kind of document with information about the project.

The result of our checklist to analyse the ToR of this external evaluation shows at first glance that the evaluator is dealing with a restrictive ToR. However, if I analyse the answers given to all the questions, I can say that contrary to what one might think, these ToR are open-ended. The specific reason for this is the answer to question number 8 (*“Do the ToR indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation?”*), which has only a score of 1. The answer to this question tells me whether I can consider the ToR to be prescriptive or not. It indicates concisely and concretely whether the ToR define a specific methodology to be used by the external evaluators or whether the evaluators are free to use the methodology they prefer or consider more appropriate to the type of project being evaluated.

I can conclude by saying that these ToR are open-ended and not very prescriptive. It will ultimately be the evaluator who decides which methods and methodology to use to carry out the external evaluation.

5.4 Analysis of the Evaluation Process

As in the previous chapter, this section relies on interviews with both the evaluator and the individual responsible for drafting the ToR to gain insight into how the evaluation was conducted.

After the formal process of hiring the external evaluator, the evaluator had the freedom to carry out their work within a timeframe of three months and to choose the methodology and methods they considered most appropriate, as long as they covered all the points indicated in **section 3** (Evaluation Description) of the ToR. As I have seen in the previous section, the ToR of the IMPALA external evaluation can be considered open-ended and not very prescriptive.

Some evaluators prefer the methodological freedom to carry out an external evaluation so they can apply the criteria they consider most appropriate. However, others do not. In the case of the IMPALA evaluation, the external evaluator pointed out his preference to prescriptive ToR and the advantages of prescriptive ToR:

For me the terms of reference must be as detailed as possible, the more detailed the terms of reference are the closer the evaluator is going to get to the objective pursued in this exercise....For me, those terms of reference that are more detailed and concrete, facilitate the evaluator's task and then you get evaluations of higher quality.

This position is perfectly in line with the European Commission (2014) idea of the importance of the prescriptiveness of the ToR.

The methodology chosen by the evaluator to carry out this evaluation is based on the one hand, on the DAC criteria and, on the other hand, on the analysis of the horizontal activities of the programme (quality, dissemination and exploitation, and project management). Thus, the evaluator makes a detailed evaluation of all the different aspects of the programme. The evaluator applied the methodology and methods they believed were most appropriate,

considering the type of evaluation he was asked for and that the chosen methodology could modify the results of the evaluation:

Approaches vary, of course. Even though they have the same objectives (evaluations), it's going to depend a bit on the type of project. There are projects where the quantitative approach, which is the most, let's say, fashionable right now in any type of research, is more applicable. And in others, you'll ultimately lean towards a qualitative approach because you don't have any other option, right? So, of course, that's going to influence your results.

Having the freedom to choose the methodology and methods, the external evaluator was also able to explore or evaluate specific aspects of the project they believed to be important, even if these were not mandatory or described in the ToR. In this case, the external evaluator introduced the horizontal analysis:

So, this relationship between what the program pursues and what the project proposes, I believe that we have to find a balance there to find which areas are more important to evaluate, and which may often be the areas that the Commission cannot reach with the existing activities because it is not going to be able to do so. And that are somewhat masked or behind everything that exists. For me it is important to try to go a little further and look for the impact at the individual and institutional level, that training is worthwhile and that is what it is.

With the introduction of that analysis, the evaluator goes one step further. His interest in the impact of the project on the beneficiaries could indicate the idea of taking them into account when carrying out the evaluation. Evaluate not only the results of the project, but also how it has affected the beneficiaries of the project.

The external evaluator also introduced the intervention logic and causal pathway to understand the background and context of the programme (type of programme, stakeholders,

and beneficiaries), as he had considered that understanding the context and background of the programme was necessary to apply the right methodology: “For me it is very important when you are going to define the methodology to understand the coming program. Explain the program, in this case capacity building in Higher Education, explain a little bit the theory of change”

The external evaluator considers the following aspects to achieve a good evaluation:

1. Implication of the different stakeholders and beneficiaries of the program during the evaluation process: the external evaluator of the IMPALA project shares the same idea, although sometimes it is not easy to obtain the implication of the different stakeholders and beneficiaries of the projects:

Beneficiaries often conduct evaluations, “honestly out of obligation”, in quotation marks, because the program requires it, or because they believe they will have more success in a proposal where there is a methodology that includes an evaluation. I think it's very important to get the involvement of the partners. Many times, it's not the case; I mean, it takes a lot of time to get them to respond to the questionnaires. Scheduling an interview is a nightmare. Sometimes, it's very complicated. Obviously, you have to have the support of the coordinator; if you don't have the coordinator's support, there's nothing you can do because you have to chase after them. It also depends a lot on the level of involvement that the partners have, even for conducting visits, because sometimes you find that they either don't want you to visit them, or they're not prepared.

In my view, this lack of interest on the part of beneficiaries in participating in evaluations is entirely linked to their participation in the drafting of the ToRs, when they can be empowered and develop the sense of ownership not only of the program but also of the evaluation, and enhance its effectiveness and efficiency, as they are experts in the project and

can help in identifying the areas where the project should be improved. Their view of evaluation can influence their commitment to it, and therefore, also influence the evaluator at the time of the evaluation (Kingston et al. 2023).

2. The importance of communicating the evaluation results: The external evaluator expresses the idea of dissemination the results of the evaluation to many people as possible because is a way to improve the activities of the program (in mid-term evaluations results and if it needed) and evaluations serves as models to other actors or initiatives:

I believe that it has to be spread as much as possible. I believe that it is crucial for the beneficiaries, especially when there is an interim report. Theoretically, you have to influence the project to pay attention to certain recommendations. Clearly, this applies to the European Commission because the European Commission often requests external evaluations to confirm the quality of those activities. I also believe it applies to other actors, especially when there are good practices. I think it is interesting that this information is also disseminated.

The external evaluator implicitly explains the importance of evaluations and the concept of transparency. Assessment and improvements are intended for project activities and as reference points. Results must be communicated to beneficiaries and the rest of the stakeholders of the project and other actors to be effective. Absence of communication makes the evaluation redundant and unimportant for the ones that do not receive the results. The OECD (2009) states that the results of an evaluation must be communicated in an accessible format, and the findings must be distributed internally and externally to learn, follow up on actions, and ensure transparency.

According to the MTER and FE the external evaluator used a methodology for this evaluation was agreed with the IMPALA Consortium, which incorporated: IMPALA Causal

Pathways & Evaluation Elements and Evaluation Matrix, including Evaluation Questions, sub-questions, indicators. The external evaluator distinguished the following stages:

- Desk review of all the documents produced by the project: deliverables, reports, surveys, minutes (etc.), the ToR and other documents that help to contextualize the program.
- Data collection using the following methods: In-depth and semi-structured interviews with project coordinators and work packages project leader; focus group discussions and/or in-depth interviews with other stakeholders; online questionnaires; on site visit; case studies.

In relation to data collection, the external evaluator did not mention the total number of participants in the different procedures.

5.4.1 *Summary of the Analysis of the Evaluation Process*

In this case, the evaluator had the freedom to choose the methodology he considered most appropriate to carry out the external evaluation. The external evaluator introduced new topics to be analysed that were not described in the ToR. Data show that, for the evaluator, the relationship with the direct beneficiaries is fundamental to carrying out an evaluation, and that communicating the results is crucial to increasing the impact of the project and the evaluation itself.

Therefore, as in the case of FORGEC, data indicate the importance of the role of the evaluator, especially in projects with non-prescriptive evaluation ToR.

5.5 Analysis of the Evaluation Reports (ERs)

The evaluation reports are the only documents that assess the project, and feedback on the entire project is given to all the stakeholders through the evaluation reports. Therefore, the programme's results are of crucial importance for the funding organisation (whether the programme met its goals, whether it was a good use of financial resources, whether the

programme can be reproduced in other organisations, or whether it should be changed), for the direct beneficiaries (whether their learning can improve their organisation, actions, or staff), and finally, for the indirect beneficiaries (whether the programme can serve as a model to be followed in other organisations).

This research is based on evaluation reports. The perceptions of the direct beneficiaries are based on their own experiences (if they were directly involved in the project evaluation) and on the external evaluation reports (whether they were directly involved or not). In this chapter, I used the same evaluation method used for the FORGEC programme reports, this allows for a direct comparison of the results of both projects. Therefore, I carried out a meta-evaluation of the IMPALA programme reports using a framework I called EV-Form (c.f. Appendix 2).

5.5.1 Analysis of the Mid-Term Evaluation Report (MTER)

In the MTER, the external evaluator focuses on desk research, interviews, and online questionnaires with members of the IMPALA consortium. With all this information, the external evaluator made recommendations for the consortium to follow to improve the final part of the programme. This can sometimes be difficult due to a lack of time. According to the external evaluator, more than one MTE should be carried out, depending on the total duration of the project: “I like the evaluations that go in 3-year projects, one every year instead of one half and one at the end. Because the recommendations that you make in the middle are difficult to change the orientation of the project. So, I like to do one evaluation a year”.

The evaluator is impartial, having been selected through a public tender. The methodology used by the evaluator was agreed upon with the IMPALA consortium, so the evaluator had the consortium's approval of the methodology before carrying out the evaluation. However, this approval does not mean that the evaluation was designed as a

participatory process. There is no reference in the evaluation to the participation of the direct beneficiaries of the project.

The evaluator divided the MTER into the following parts: introduction, executive summary, objective of the evaluation, consortium, methodology, evaluation results, DAC criteria, evaluation of horizontal activities, recommendations, and conclusions. In this way, the evaluator adequately addresses the questions set out in the ToR (page 3).

In the first part of the evaluation, the evaluator also reflects on the temporal and geographical dimensions of the project (page 11 of the MTER), but the regulatory dimension of the project is not described in concrete terms, although I can infer it from the evaluator's reflections on the DAC criteria (pages 18 to 20 of the MTER). As this is an interim report, the evaluator has not examined the final objective of the intervention in its entirety, and only the dissemination part has been included in this report, so there is no explicit reference to the sustainability, ownership, coherence, and impact of the project.

Analysing the design of the methodology used by the evaluator, I can see that the evaluator first explains the context and requirements of the evaluation, what a capacity project is, and its evaluation workflow. The evaluator then explains the methodology used and its rationale: "Intervention Logic and Causal Pathways are provided to understand how the project works, and which are the main relations between their activities, results, outputs, outcome and expected impact. The methodology is based on the following: The application of the standard DAC Criteria (relevance, efficiency, effectiveness, sustainability and Impact) and a specific analysis of the horizontal activities of the project (quality, dissemination & exploitation and project management)" (MTER, p.30), which includes an evaluation matrix developed on the basis of the desk review and some interviews with IMPALA participants (including evaluation questions, sub-questions, indicators/judgement criteria). The inclusion of

the evaluation workflow on page 10 of the MTER allows us to follow the entire evaluation process.

The evaluator also explains to us the data collection methods and who will be involved: “The Methodology is based on desk review of all the documents produced by the project: deliverables, reports, surveys, minutes, etc. Data collection used mainly the following methods: a) In-depth and semi-structure interviews with project coordinators and work package project leaders; Focus group discussions and/or in-depth interviews with other stakeholders; Online questionnaires; Participation in the final conference; and Case studies (if needed)” (MTER, p.15). About the analysis of the documents produced by the project, I cannot find the coding used for this qualitative analysis. Although the methodology chosen by the evaluator is the most appropriate for this type of project, we do not see the risks and limitations associated with this methodology.

The evaluator presents some conclusions relating to the actions carried out during this first part of the project, based on their analysis. They also present a series of recommendations aimed at achieving the final objectives of the programme. These recommendations are specific, detailed, and clearly based on the analyses carried out during the evaluation.

One notable aspect of this evaluation that I would like to highlight is the organisation and readability facilitated by the inclusion of graphics. For example, for each of the DAC criteria and cross-cutting measures evaluated, the evaluator first presents the questions and indicators, followed by the corresponding results for these questions, and comments on each item in a concluding diagram.

According to the data, the evaluation report is efficient because the evaluator explains what a CBHE project is and what is expected of it. The evaluator systematically analyses all relevant issues for the evaluation of a project. In doing so, the evaluator includes information that is not required by the ToR. With the methodology used, the evaluator not only fulfils the

requirements of the ToR for the evaluation but also extends the scope of the areas to be evaluated. As a result, both project managers and direct beneficiaries can use the evaluator's recommendations to redirect their actions, if necessary, to realistically achieve the project's ultimate goal.

When analysing the results of the meta-evaluation carried out by means of the EV-Form I focused my analysis on two different issues of the MTER. The first point of analysis is whether all the requirements of the ToR are included in the MTER. Through this analysis, I can see that the external evaluator has not only fulfilled all the requirements and topics of the ToR but has also added new topics or expanded some topics in the evaluation report. The second point of analysis is the level of information on the topics that I can find in the MTER.

As a result, in the quality subsection, the external evaluator followed the ToR and included solid data, findings, conclusions, recommendations, and clear evaluations in the MTER. The DAC criteria subsection on impact, sustainability, and project coherence has not been assessed, as this is an interim report.

It is worth noting that in the MTER, the evaluator addressed more than two-thirds of the questions in our EV form, either fully, partially, or in more detail. In a similar way, the evaluator has also included information that appears in our EV-Form but not in the ToR. In this MTER, the evaluator explains what a capacity-building project is, the types of capacity-building projects, the process of designing the evaluation, and how this design was approved by the stakeholders -aspects that are not required in the ToR.

5.5.2. Analysis of the Final Evaluation Report (FER)

The FER of IMPALA was conducted during the Covid-19 outbreak, which had an impact on the project activities and the way the evaluation was conducted.

In the Final Evaluation Report (FER), the evaluator focused (following the same logic as in the MTER) on the activities carried out from the MTER to the end of the project and on

the results and impacts of all the activities of the whole project. In this case, the evaluator did not make any recommendations but referred to them in the conclusions section and assessed whether they had been taken into account in the second part of the project. The evaluator also used the case study method. The report included one case study/good practice per participating country (Colombia, Cuba, and Panama).

In the FER, the evaluator divided the evaluation into the following parts: introduction, aim of the evaluation, intervention logic/causal pathways, methodology, evaluation results, DAC criteria, evaluation of horizontal activities, case studies and good practices by country, conclusions, and annexes. From a methodological point of view, it is noteworthy that for each of the DAC criteria analysed, the evaluator not only provides the results but also his general comments on these results and an individualised perspective by country with ad hoc conclusions. In this report, all DAC criteria can be assessed, as all actions have been implemented, and the project has been completed. Thus, according to the evaluator, this FE “measure the scope of the actions and the impact of the activities carried out during the implementation of the project, determining the achievement of the expected results, the degree of achievement of the specific objectives and its contribution to the achievement of the general objective as it was provided for in the project formulation document” (FE, p. 11). In the analysis of the horizontal actions (quality, dissemination, project management), the evaluator's comments are general, as these actions are the same for all countries.

The evaluator also presents the three case studies/good practices and possible deviations, which are not required by the ToR. The inclusion of the cases is due to the evaluator's belief that they are needed to provide recommendations for future activities. They also provide a basis for materialising the impact of the project at the country level and serve as a way to show tangible effects that have been achieved at different levels. Although, as the

evaluator pointed out, it is difficult to generalise a methodology proposed for different universities in different countries based on only three cases.

The evaluator presents the conclusions in two different sections. In the first, the evaluator compares in a table the recommendations made in the MTER and whether these recommendations have been implemented during the period of activity between the MTER and the FE. In the second section, the evaluator draws the conclusions individually for each of the DAC criteria as well as for the three horizontal actions of the project in a narrative form. The evaluator also assigns them a value between excellent, good, low, or poor and includes a diagram to make the conclusions easier to understand.

According to the results of my meta-analysis, this FER is as efficient as the MTER. The way in which the evaluator has structured the whole FER, as well as the methodology used, covers all the aspects required in the ToR. In my opinion, the inclusion of three concrete cases helps not only to have a clearer view of the objective of the project but also of the results of the project. To understand this FER, it is not necessary to have read the previous report, as the evaluator explains again the objective of the project and the evaluation, what a capacity-building project is and how it is evaluated, and the methodology used.

In this case, the implementing unit simply drafted a single ToR, which was used by the external evaluator as a basis for both the MTER and the FER. Therefore, the degree of prescriptiveness of the ToR has already been analysed earlier in this chapter (c.f., p.160). I have therefore only analysed whether, and to what extent, the external evaluator has followed the guidelines that appear as recommendations or not.

There are a few differences between the analysis of the MTER and the FER. In this case, the external evaluator again follows the ToR in the quality subsection. All questions related to the DAC criteria have been answered. As all the actions have been carried out, it is now possible to assess the impact, sustainability, and coherence of the project, and the way it

has been carried out exceeds expectations or the way it is usually carried out. Some questions have the same score in the MTER and FER because the reports are done in a similar way. Thus, both evaluation reports contain common parts, while some elements, such as the coding used in qualitative analysis, do not appear in either.

The data show that all the answers contain information related to the questions of the EV-Form in the sections on compliance, context analysis, data solidity, credibility of findings, conclusions, and clarity of the evaluation. On the contrary, the questions of the EV-Form in the recommendations' subsection do not contain any information because the evaluator has not made any recommendations, as it is a final report. However, the conclusions are much more extensive and detailed, based on the evaluator's opinion.

5.5.3 *Summary of the Evaluation Reports*

Based on the results of my meta-evaluation, we are dealing with two very similar evaluation reports. Both formally evaluate the IMPALA programme correctly. Both evaluation reports contain all the information required by the ToR. The external evaluator has improved both reports by including issues that are not required in the ToR (such as a case study in the final evaluation report) or details that can help the project stakeholders to understand the results and assist anyone reading the evaluation reports. However, we are not aware of the value that the beneficiaries directly attribute to this type of evaluation, as there is no reference to their interests anywhere in the evaluation.

5.6 Analysis of the Direct Beneficiaries' Perceptions

To facilitate a comparison between the evaluations of the FORGEC case and the IMPALA case, the same scheme that was previously employed in the analysis of beneficiaries' perceptions of the FORGEC case had been applied in this case.

I conducted nine semi-structured interviews (face-to-face or online) with direct beneficiaries of the programme. These interviewees were members of two different

universities, Universidad Agraria de la Habana and Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá, and all of them participated in minimum of two different activities of the IMPALA programme. Three different types of profiles were interviewed: senior leaders, middle managers and administrative leaders. In this case, only one type of interview was conducted. Given the much more specific nature of the activities, it was ensured that the participants had participated in at least two face-to-face activities.

To answer the operational questions of my research (c.f. 3.1.2), I focused and analysed four concrete aspects: a) the importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries; b) the impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project; c) the opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out and d) the value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries.

5.6.1 Universidad Agraria de la Habana

The profiles interviewed at UNAH were one senior leader and four middle managers (including the project manager).

5.6.1.1 Importance of External Evaluation for Direct Beneficiaries

- Personal Context: All participants have been involved in the programme from the beginning, in different roles and in different ways, depending on their professional profile. They have a clear understanding of the objectives and outcomes of the programme.
- Evaluation and Measurement: Although participants have different levels of knowledge about evaluation, all of them understand its importance in project management. External evaluations, in general, are seen as an integral part of the management cycle and, in particular, their results must be considered. “La evaluación forma parte del ciclo, de hecho forma parte del ciclo directivo y tenerlo bien en cuenta con una buena definición del objetivo que va a cumplir esa evaluación “; “Evaluation is part of the cycle, in fact it is part of the management cycle and to take it into account with a good definition of the objective that this

evaluation is going to fulfil“ (IM3). External evaluations are particularly valued by four of the interviewees (senior leader and middle managers) as they provide an independent perspective, not just on whether the project has achieved the defined results or how the funds have been used. This external perspective is seen as crucial for reflection and identification of improvements. “Y también la evaluación externa te permite esa mirada desde afuera de alguien que no está tan implicado, tan involucrado, pero que sí te puede hacer reflexionar sobre esos puntos de mejora”; “The external evaluation allows you to have an outside view from someone who is not so involved, so involved, but who can make you reflect on those points of improvement” (IM2).

Participants have a generally positive attitude towards external evaluations and in concrete the one to the IMPALA project, seeing it as opportunities for institutional and personal improvement. However, only two of the five participants (senior leader and one middle manager) were involved in the external evaluation of the IMPALA. Both noted that in this concrete evaluation, the methodology was defined in advance by the external evaluator and did not always meet their expectations: “A veces te ves reflejado como parte de los criterios o de lo que está sucediendo pero no siempre estás reflejado”; “Sometimes you see yourself reflected as part of the criteria or what is happening but not always you are reflected” (IM2).

The participants agreed that external evaluations should focus on the project's results, objectives, and financial justification, but most importantly on the overall impact of the project to direct beneficiaries. The senior leader stressed that the IMPALA evaluation was rigorous and consistent with the timeline.

Casi siempre la evaluación del proyecto va hacia el cumplimiento del objetivo, hacia la actividad y control económica del proyecto y quizás a alguna medida la satisfacción de los actores o beneficiarios del proyecto. Pero creo que hay que pensar un poco más

allá. Hay que pensar en el impacto y el resultado final expresado en los que reciben el beneficio final de todos y cada uno de los proyectos. Y eso no está valorado o no está escrito en las encuestas de los que financian los proyectos (IM1).

Most of the time, the evaluation of the project goes towards the fulfilment of the objective, towards the activity and economic control of the project and perhaps to some extent the satisfaction of the actors or beneficiaries of the project. But I think we must think a bit further. We must think about the impact and the final result expressed in those who receive the final benefit of each and every one of the projects. And this is not valued or is not written in the surveys of those who finance the projects (IM1).

Feedback helped institutions understand their position relative to the project's objectives. Three of the five participants (senior leader and two middle managers) said interim evaluations, in general, are key to adjusting implementation and correcting mistakes. The senior leader and one of the middle managers also noted that in these concrete project feedback from universities (direct beneficiaries) could be more useful.

... creo que valdría la pena también una retroalimentación ya hacia la institución.

Porque eso te ayudaría en ese feedback, te ayudaría a ver puntos débiles que quizás no son del consorcio, no son del proyecto, pero son tuyos. O puntos de mejora, o puntos también, incluso fortalezas que tiene como institución dentro del proyecto que pudiera estar siendo socializado más con el resto de los socios (IM2).

... I think it would also be worthwhile to give feedback to the institution. Because that would help you in this feedback, it would help you to see weak points that perhaps are not of the consortium, they are not of the project, but they are yours. Or points for improvement, or points also, even strengths that you have as an institution within the project that could be socialised more with the rest of the partners (IM2).

While two participants (one middle manager and one middle manager) stressed the need for proper planning of the external evaluation, they didn't discuss resource allocation, focusing instead on organizing the process. "Porque la evaluación hay que organizarla. ¿En qué momento la vas a realizar? ¿Con qué metodología? ¿En qué personas vas a participar? Tiene que haber un proceso de planificación de ese proceso de evaluación."; "Evaluation needs to be organized. When are you going to carry it out? With what methodology? Who will participate? There must be a planning process for that evaluation" (IM4).

Finally, three participants (the senior leader and two middle managers) underscored the importance of the external evaluator understanding the project's context. Thus, the idea of acknowledging that context can significantly affect evaluation results that reappear in this case.

Porque no creo que un evaluador externo, por mucho prestigio ganado que tenga como evaluador e incluso como parte del conocimiento que tiene del área del proyecto, pero si no conoce el contexto no siempre puede hacer unas valoraciones objetivas que realmente ayuden al proceso de mejora continua (IM2).

Because I do not believe that an external evaluator, no matter how much prestige he/she has gained as an evaluator and even as part of the knowledge he/she has of the project area, but if he/she does not know the context, he/she cannot always make objective assessments that really help the process of continuous improvement (IM2).

5.6.1.2. Impact of the External Evaluation Results at Institutions and Individuals

- Development and Improvement: In this case, only two interviewees (senior leader and one middle manager) were involved in the external evaluation, and only one of the five (a middle manager) did not receive the results. This interviewee emphasised the importance of feedback for improvement.

The results of a project evaluation can lead to changes in the implementation of a project (in the case of a mid-term evaluation), but again all interviewees agreed that an evaluation can lead to positive changes at an institutional, personal, or professional level in general.

At the individual level, all participants agreed that it can have an impact. All of them except one middle manager emphasised that external evaluations could lead to both personal and professional growth: “Yo creo que es hacer un hombre más completo, más integrado. Tanto como profesional como hombre.”; “I think it is about creating a more complete, more integrated person. Both as a professional and as a human being”(IM1). Two participants (middle managers) also note that external evaluations promote professional change (decision-making and leadership skills): “Mi capacidad de trabajo y mi forma de pensar y de actuar y de dirigir cambian notablemente.”; “My ability to work and my way of thinking, acting and leading have changed significantly” (IM5). In this case, two participants (one middle manager and the senior leader) experienced job changes within their institutions, but it is unclear whether this was directly related to the external evaluation.

All the participants, except one middle manager, believe that changes can take place at the institutional level, for example, in decision-making on certain issues or in the way certain practices are conceived, but only if there is reflection and analysis within the institution. “Si la institución está ávida de tener un proceso de mejora continua, de escuchar con objetividad lo que se está evaluando y lo que se está recomendando, puede ser un objeto de cambio en la institución.”; “If the institution is willing to have a process of continuous improvement, to listen objectively to what is being evaluated and what is being recommended, it can be an object of change in the institution” (IM2).

5.6.1.3. *Opinion of the Direct Beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out*

- Collaboration and Interaction: Participants emphasise the importance of tailoring evaluations to the different interests of all the stakeholders. They suggest that a dialogue between stakeholders could improve the evaluation process for direct beneficiaries. The senior leader introduces the idea of creating a tool that serves the needs of all stakeholders.

Yo creo que hay que hacer una evaluación integral. Es decir, el que financia, el que ejecuta y el que se beneficia. De alguna manera hay que crear un instrumento que satisfaga o al menos que permita que cada cual dé su criterio sobre la evaluación final de un proyecto o el resultado que se consigue (IM1).

I believe that a comprehensive assessment must be made. That is to say, the one who finances, the one who executes and the one who benefits. Somehow, we have to create an instrument that satisfies or at least allows everyone to give their opinion on the final evaluation of a project or the result that is achieved (IM1).

This reflects the participants' sense of empowerment, as they believe they should be involved in the design of external evaluations. They see themselves as integral parts of the project and argue that they need to be involved and listen to from the start.

Without their input, important aspects could be overlooked. They emphasise that all stakeholders should be aware of the evaluation criteria from the beginning. To further improve external evaluations, participants propose including assessments of how the project has been implemented and its broader effects, beyond just financial results and project implementation. This comprehensive approach would provide a more complete understanding of the project's success.

Los evaluadores externos vienen con una idea ya inicial. Pero a mí no preguntan que quiero. Solo miran que todo haya funcionado, pero hay veces que desconocen los lugares donde se ha realizado el proyecto. El contexto. Y eso es importante, y a donde nosotros queremos llegar. Eso también. Y que queremos saber o que necesitamos, por eso la retroalimentación (IM4).

The external evaluators come with an initial idea. But they don't ask me what I want. They only check that everything has worked, but sometimes they don't know the locations where the project has been carried out. The context. And that is important, and where we want to go. That's important too. And what we want to know or what we need, that's why the feedback (IM4).

The aim of the IMPALA project was to develop a methodology for measuring the impact of Third Mission activities in universities. In light of the above, all interviewees stressed the need for external evaluations to assess the impact of the project on its direct beneficiaries: “Creo que es clave, ubicarnos en el beneficiario para el cual está el proyecto y conocer cuánto se transformo.”; “I believe it is key to put ourselves in the place of the beneficiary for whom the project is intended and to understand how much they have been transformed.” (IM5).

5.6.1.4. Value and Effectiveness of External Evaluation for Direct Beneficiaries

- Perception and valuation: In this case, all the interviewees talked about efficiency in terms of value. For three of them (middle managers), the value of an evaluation is entirely linked to the useful information it provides. An in this concrete evaluation, this useful information is measing. The results can help both the institutions and the direct beneficiaries to improve their processes, implement new projects, or carry out an internal review of their own institutions regarding specific issues. It is always essential to consider what the project was trying to achieve and whether the project had an impact.

Yo creo que para mí es eficaz la evaluación si me arroja información útil. En cualquier sentido. Ya sea para ver el cumplimiento de determinados procesos, de determinados objetivos que se pueden haber cumplido o no, pero también si me arroja información para la continuidad (M4).

I think evaluation is efficient for me if it gives me useful information. In any sense.

Whether it is to see the fulfilment of certain processes, of certain objectives that may or may not have been met, but also if it provides me with information for continuity (IM4).

For all the interviewees, the effectiveness of the evaluation is linked to the evaluation process itself: the definition of its objective, the result to be obtained, and the indicators to be used for the evaluation. However, the staff of the program reiterated the idea of involving the direct beneficiaries of the projects in the evaluation, as they are the ones who genuinely experience the impact of the project. Evaluations tend to neglect this part because they are more concerned with measuring interventions and their outcomes than with measuring impact.

Es decir, que la evaluación conduce a medir, a evaluar, olvidémonos el término exacto, pero a conocer la transformación que tuvo en la persona, en el beneficiario, en este caso. Creo que es clave, ubicarnos en el beneficiario para el cual está el proyecto y conocer cuánto se transformó. (IM5)

In other words, evaluation leads to measuring, to assessing, let's forget the exact term, but to knowing the transformation that has taken place in the person, in the beneficiary, in this case. I think it is key, to place ourselves in the beneficiary for whom the project is intended and to know how much he/she has been transformed. (IM5)

5.6.1.5. *Summary of the Results Universidad Agraria de la Habana*

In the case of the Universidad Agraria de la Habana, the responses show that only one middle manager's answers differ from the rest of the participants on some issues. Therefore,

there is almost no difference between the opinions of all the participants in all the topics although only two interviewees took part as participants in the evaluation of the programme.

By considering the responses in relation to the different aspects, I can say that all the participants recognise, in general, the importance of external evaluations in order to get feedback from the project to adapt it if necessary (mid-term evaluation) or as a model to follow for new projects. They also emphasise the importance of assessing the impact of the project and the need for the external evaluator to know the context from the outset. The perspective the external evaluator is highly valued in this evaluation and his work, although the methodology should consider their needs and not only assess if the objectives have been achieved. In this case, the participants see changes as positive, and external evaluations can have an impact on some concrete points in their institution. All participants agree that external evaluations can have an impact on their lives. Sometimes personal changes, and at other times professional changes, can be seen after knowing the results of an external evaluation. From the direct beneficiaries' perspective the external evaluation, in general, should be carried out by considering the needs of the direct beneficiaries from the beginning of the evaluation design, even though it was not the case. Dialogue and exchange between external evaluators and direct beneficiaries should take place, and external evaluations will be improved. The reference to measuring the impact of the project results was mentioned by all participants as an important point for improving external evaluations. In this case, the opinion of direct beneficiaries on the value of external evaluation is based on the useful information it provides them. Effectiveness is linked to the evaluation process itself.

5.6.2 Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá

In this university, because of structural modifications at the university and the prerequisite of participation in a minimum of two activities in the program to be interview int

in this study, I was only able to conduct interviews with four individuals: one senior leader) and three middle managers (including the project manager).

5.6.2.1. Importance of External Evaluation for Direct Beneficiaries

Personal Context: Only the senior leader was involved in the programme from the beginning. Internal changes at the university meant that people who had been involved in the project from the very beginning left during the course of the project. The remaining participants became aware of the programme when they joined the project. This knowledge was transferred to them by their superiors, and they were all aware of the aim of the project: to measure the impact of Third Mission activities. Two of the middle managers became involved in the project activities after more than 30% of the project had been completed. Considering the specific profile of each interviewee, their participation in the activities was more concentrated on certain tasks than others.

Evaluation and Measurement: Except for one of the middle managers, the other participants have demonstrated a high level of expertise in the field of evaluation. In particular, one of the middle managers is responsible for the internal evaluation of projects at the institutional level. The four participants reflected in their answers the importance of external evaluation in general. It was stressed that evaluations are conducted to ascertain whether the objectives of a project have been met. The senior leader and one middle manager highlighted the significance of evaluations in facilitating potential modifications to project implementation, thereby enabling the adaptation of current methodologies. Accordingly, they consider external evaluation to be a means of assisting in the attainment of project objectives.

Es una mirada externa a lo que nosotros estamos haciendo y quizás estamos utilizando herramientas, o nos estamos concentrando en algo que un ojo externo puede decir, ojo, mira que quizás hay recalibrar esto, quizás que hay repensar esto..., es importante tenerlo porque le da una mirada externa... (IM6).

It is an external view of what we are doing and maybe we are using tools, or we are concentrating on something that an external eye can say, look, maybe we need to recalibrate this, maybe we need to rethink this...., it is important to have it because it gives you an external view... (IM6).

In this case none of the interviewees took part in the external evaluation. Two middle managers explicitly stated their desire to participate in the external evaluation due to their involvement in the project and a desire to remain informed about its progress and final outcomes. On the other hand, the senior leader emphasized that the decision to not participate in the external evaluation was a personal choice, given that lack of information about the evaluation (schedule, methodology). This position shows a total lack of knowledge about the evaluation of this programme and a non-involvement of the direct beneficiaries at the moment of drafting the ToR of these evaluation. Thus, their attitude towards external evaluation in general appears favourable, although some adjustments related to involvement and communication were needed.

All participants indicate, in one way or another, that the methodology used in evaluations generally was designed by the external evaluator, without considering their expectations. There is no criticism of the work done by external evaluators in this evaluation. The underlying concept of involvement in the design of the evaluation and its methodology was expressed by three of the four interviewees, only one middle manager had no opinion on that topic. They point out that the involvement of the direct beneficiaries in the definition of the methodology is crucial for the evaluation. According to the interviewees, a lack of knowledge about direct beneficiaries and their specific concerns can change results and make evaluations less accurate. The needs of the direct beneficiaries have to be known by the external evaluator at the moment the methodology is defined. The senior leader emphasises the flexibility of the external evaluators, considering that they do not have a complete overview of

the project, and suggested that the methodology could have been more cross-cutting. "...la metodología habría podido ser, decimos con esta palabra que quizás responde a todo un poco, más transversal, un poco más interdisciplinar, que no siendo vista por parte de una sola persona independientemente del perfil que tiene esta persona."; "...the methodology could have been, we say with this word which perhaps responds to everything, a little more "transversal", a little more interdisciplinary, than being seen by a single person regardless of the profile that this person has" (IM6).

In addition to involving the direct beneficiaries in the design of the evaluation, all participants in this case advocate carrying out several evaluations during the life cycle of the project. Two of the middle managers refer to feedback. One middle manager refers not only to the final external evaluation, but also to an initial evaluation process in which the objectives of the project are made clear in a realistic way. Another participant also advocates continuous implementation during the project to correct potential deviations: "...a mí me parece que IMPALA sí fue una apuesta grande para las universidades socias, pero faltó una evaluación permanente del proyecto."; "...it seems to me that IMPALA was a big commitment for the partner universities, but there was a lack of permanent evaluation of the project" (IM7).

According to the senior leader and two of the middle managers, the external evaluator needs to know the context in which the project has been carried out, because the context can influence the way the project has been implemented and by default the evaluation. In this specific case, two middle managers also refer to each of the institutions, which are so different in this programme: "El evaluador externo también tiene que conocernos, debe conocer a los beneficiarios, el contexto. En este caso éramos universidades muy distintas de países muy distintos. Si no se tiene muy claro el contexto, las evaluaciones, pueden fallar."; "The external evaluator also needs to know us; they must know the beneficiaries and the context. In this

case, we were universities from very different countries. If the context is not well understood, the evaluations can fail” (IM7).

5.6.2.2. Impact of the External Evaluation Results at Institutions and Individuals

Development and Improvement: Only the senior leader received the final report of the external evaluation, although the middle managers were willing to receive feedback from the evaluation. Considering that, the answers regarding personal and institutional changes were based on their previous experiences, and all of them see external evaluation as a positive experience.

At an individual level, only two middle managers reported changes in their way of thinking about certain issues. However, none of them observed any personal changes; these are entirely linked to their professional approach and attitude to work, leading them to consider different ways of addressing specific tasks: “En mi ha cambiado, como te decía, como veo algunas cosas. Ahora hay veces que lo miro desde otras perspectivas. Pero sigo siendo el mismo”; “There has been a change in me, there has been a change in the way I look at certain things. Now I sometimes look at them from a different perspective. But I am still myself” (IM8). One middle manager changed their position in the institution, but in that case, we know it is not because of the external evaluation.

Regarding changes at the institutional level because of external evaluation, participants have different perspectives. The senior leader notes that the results do not directly change an institution. External evaluations can provoke an internal dialogue within the institution, creating a moment of reflection on how it acts on certain issues raised by the project: “Yo creo que más que generar una modificación, tiene poder para generar un debate. Un debate interno para repensarse”; “I believe that rather than generating a modification, it has the power to generate a debate. An internal debate to rethink things” (IM6). On the other hand, two middle managers thought that external evaluations could gradually change the way the institution

operates or introduce different working methods. “Sin resultados no vas a modificar nada. A nivel de institución, como te decía, puede que algunas cosas se modifiquen, ya sea porque veas que no funcionan o que están mal enfocadas. Puedes modificar alguna estructura, pero pocas”; “Without results, you are not going to change anything. At the institutional level, as I said, some things can be changed, either because you see that they are not working, or they are poorly focused. You can modify some structures, but only a few" (IM7).

5.6.2.3. Opinion of the Direct Beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out

Collaboration and Interaction: In this case, as none of them had participated in the external evaluation, they were unaware if there had been previous exchanges with people involved in the evaluation. Despite this, participants unanimously agree that an exchange between the external evaluator and direct beneficiaries is essential for a thorough external evaluation, especially given the diversity of direct beneficiaries in this project. Exchange is seen as a way to address the specific needs of direct beneficiaries: “Puedes aplicar un método de evaluación, pero, creo que es mejor preguntar más a los beneficiarios, que queremos, que que necesitábamos saber”; “You can apply an evaluation method, but I think it is better to ask beneficiaries what we want, what we need to know” (IM7).

Only one middle manager talked about empowerment clearly, referring to the implementation of the project, not the evaluation. However, the concept of empowerment underpins the participants’ views on participation and exchange. The senior leader and two of the middle managers believe that direct beneficiaries should be actively involved in the design of this concrete evaluation methodology to achieve more accurate and meaningful results, even though they may not participate in it afterwards. “Yo creo que haber sido un poco más protagonista en la construcción de la metodología, habría generado, de mi punto de vista, una evaluación un poco más, decimos, precisa y quizás un poco más indicativa que te daba el

resultado verdadero”; “I believe that having been more involved in the construction of the methodology would have, in my view, resulted in a slightly more precise evaluation and perhaps more indicative of the true outcome” (IM6).

All participants suggest that if direct beneficiaries were incorporated in the evaluation’s design phase, external evaluations would improve. They also agree that evaluations should assess whether the project results have been applied, in this specific case, within the beneficiaries' institutions, not only if the activity was done and the accountability of the project. “Se debe mirar si esto sirvió para algo. De lo contrario, solo mira la aplicación del presupuesto, y las actividades que se hicieron”; “You should look at whether this served any purpose. If not, just look at the implementation of the budget, and the activities that were done” (IM9).

5.6.2.4. Value and Effectiveness of External Evaluation for Direct Beneficiaries

Perception and valuation: Only two participants, the senior leader and one middle manager, talk about value, linking it to two different topics. Firstly, if the evaluation only confirms that the project was implemented correctly, it has no value: it is just a “number” and evaluations should provide more information than “numbers”. “Para que tenga valor, nos ha de aportar. Si no aporta, para mí no tiene valor. Podemos salir muy bien en la evaluación, pero si no me aporta nada, pues su valor es “numérico” pero nada más”; “It must contribute something to us for it to be valuable. It has no value to me if it doesn't contribute. We can perform very well in the evaluation, but if it doesn't add anything to me, then its value is just ‘numerical’ and nothing more” (IM6).

Secondly, the evaluation should take into consideration the direct beneficiaries and their point of view in relation to the objectives of the project and its usefulness, not only if the activities had been executed. Activities could be executed but not fulfil the needs of the beneficiaries, and this opinion should be reflected in the evaluations.

El valor de una evaluación está en ver si realmente ha servido el proyecto, según el punto de vista del evaluado, pero si el punto de vista no tiene en cuenta al evaluado, el valor puede ser positivo o negativo, pero no reflejará al 100% lo que el beneficiario quiere ver o en lo que está interesado (IM7).

The value of an evaluation lies in determining whether the project has truly served its purpose, from the perspective of those being evaluated. However, if the evaluation does not take into account the viewpoint of those being evaluated, its value may be positive or negative, but it won't fully reflect what the beneficiary wants to see or what they are interested in (IM7).

All interviewees rate the effectiveness of the evaluation in relation to the measurement of the programme's objectives, results, and implementation, as well as its impact. One middle manager pointed out that for an evaluation to be effective, it must be based on the real possibilities of the project and not expect outstanding results.

5.6.2.5. *Summary of the Results Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá*

In the case of the Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá, it can be observed that the responses of the senior leader and those of the intermediate positions differ in certain aspects as the impact of evaluations in institutions and individuals. Furthermore, two middle management positions gave identical answers except for the topic related to the value of the external evaluation, while the third middle manager differs in more aspects.

The answers of the four aspects that helped me to answer the operational questions indicated that the interviewees place a high value on the evaluations and on receiving the results, even though they were not involved in the project evaluation. Conversely, participants also stressed the importance of the external evaluator's contextual awareness to ensure the reliability of the results. Participants also indicated that the evaluations could lead to reflection within institutions and concrete changes in their work, though not at a personal level. For

participants, evaluations need to consider direct beneficiaries to have a broader vision of the project, the context, and the direct beneficiaries' expectations of the evaluation. External evaluations should be improved to include impact assessment of results. The contribution of the evaluation to the participants determines its value. Effectiveness means that the evaluation is carried out in the right way, analysing whether the objectives have been achieved and what the results and outcomes have been.

5.6.3 Summary of the Analysis of the Direct Beneficiaries' Perception

Although none of the participants from the Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá were involved in carrying out the external evaluation, if we compare the responses of the rectors of both universities and the responses of the middle managers, I can see that their opinions are quite similar, except for one middle manager in each university. Therefore, in both cases, there is no difference between the opinions of the different participants. All of them consider external evaluations important, but all of them see the need to evaluate the impact of the programme, not only the achievement of objectives and outcomes.

The main difference between the participants relates to the impact an external evaluation can have on their institutions and on themselves. Although they all agree that there is an impact, the difference lies in the nature of the impact. Most of the participants from the Universidad Agraria de la Habana say that external evaluations can change university structures, even in a simple way. Participants from the Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá, however, understand that it involves reflection in the organisation, but it is very difficult to make structural changes. Changes at the individual level (personal or professional) were also seen differently. Participants from the Universidad Agraria de la Habana think that personal changes are possible, as well as professional ones. On the other hand, participants from the Universidad Javeriana de Bogotá think that only professional changes are possible, but not personal ones.

In both cases, direct beneficiaries feel that their involvement in the evaluation process is a key issue. Their needs should be reflected in the external evaluation process to achieve a more complete and useful evaluation. The external evaluator's knowledge of the context also needs to be considered, as it may influence the results of the evaluation. Direct beneficiaries also see the evaluation of the impact of results as an issue to be included in external evaluations.

An external evaluation is of great value to the direct beneficiaries if it provides new information. A positive external evaluation may be of less value than a negative one. This need for information should be known by the external evaluator and can only be met by an exchange of information between them. Effectiveness is more related to the formal aspect of the external evaluation.

5.7 Summary of the Results

To answer my research question (*How effective is the external evaluation process of International Capacity Building in Higher Education projects in meeting the needs of the direct beneficiaries, as perceived by these beneficiaries?*), I have followed the same structure used in Chapter 4: analysing the ToR, the evaluation reports of the IMPALA programme, and semi-structured interviews with direct beneficiaries from two different universities involved in the IMPALA programme, as well as with the external evaluator and the person responsible of writing the ToR from the implementing unit.

After analysing the ToR of the external evaluation, the data show that the IMPALA ToR are not prescriptive, and the external evaluator defined the methodology to be used, considering all the requirements that appear in the ToR. Direct beneficiaries were not considered when writing the ToR, as it was corroborated by the responsible for drafting them. The external evaluator validated the methodology of the evaluation with the consortium, but we do not know which members of the consortium were asked to do it.

The external evaluator included in the reports all the requirements that appeared in the ToR, as well as information that was not required, such as case studies. This makes the reports easier to understand.

Direct beneficiaries consider external evaluations to be important and positive but feel that they could be improved if their interests were reflected in the evaluation. This improvement requires an exchange of views or discussions between those responsible for the evaluation and the direct beneficiaries at the design stage. Participants also mentioned that they thought the external evaluations should analyse the impact of the programme.

Finally, it should be noted that participants do not value evaluations for their effectiveness but for the new information they provide.

Chapter 6: Comparison Between Case Study 1 (FORGEC) and Case Study 2 (IMPALA)

6.1 Introduction

The objective of this chapter is to undertake a comparative analysis of the results obtained from the different analyses conducted in Chapters 4 and 5. These analyses pertain to the FORGEC and IMPALA cases, respectively. The findings of this comparative analysis will provide the basis for answering my research question.

6.2 Comparison of the Terms of Reference (ToR)

The analysis of the ToR of both projects is important because the ToRs are the documents that guide the external evaluation in both projects. To compare the ToR of both projects, I made two different analyses. Through the first analysis, I have determined whether the ToRs of the cases under examination can be considered prescriptive or not. The second analysis determined the grade of prescriptiveness of both ToRs. The result of both analysis reveals that there are great differences between the ToR of both cases. The results indicate that the ToR of the FORGEC programme are more prescriptive than those of the IMPALA programme. The data that supports this result are based on the following analysis:

First analysis: To know if the ToRs of the projects are prescriptive or not I had compared the results of the Q-ToR checklist analysis where the ToR was graded as prescriptive, semi-prescriptive, open and non-prescriptive considering to the information that appears in the ToR and the information required in our Q-ToR checklist. The five mandatory questions for the European Commission (EC) to be included in the ToR have been marked in blue. The key question that helped me answer my research question was marked in grey.

Table 12

Comparison Between Prescriptiveness Analysis of the ToR of the FORGEC and IMPALA programmes

Q-ToR CHECKLIST	FORGEC ToR	IMPALA ToR
Question		
1. Have the Terms of Reference been formulated in a clear and understandable manner?	Prescriptive	Semi-prescriptive
2. Do the Terms of Reference contain the objective and scope of the programme?	Semi-prescriptive	Semi-prescriptive
3. Do the Terms of Reference contextualize the programme?	Semi-prescriptive	Prescriptive
4. Do the Terms of Reference outline the activities and the work plan of the programme?	Semi-prescriptive	Semi-prescriptive
5. Do the Terms of Reference outline the expected results of the programme?	Prescriptive	Prescriptive
6. Do the Terms of Reference indicate the stakeholders of the programme?	Semi-prescriptive	Non-prescriptive
7. Do the Terms of Reference indicate the beneficiaries of the programme?	Prescriptive	Open
8. Do the Terms of Reference indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation?	Semi-prescriptive	Non-prescriptive
9. Do the Terms of Reference identify the resources (personal) and timing for the evaluation to be carried out?	Prescriptive	Prescriptive
10. Have the Terms of Reference specified the deliverables to be produced after the evaluation?	Prescriptive	Open
11. Do the Terms of Reference contain the budget allocated to the evaluation, and is it in accordance with the evaluation?	Non-prescriptive	Prescriptive
12. Has the interest of the direct beneficiaries (no other stakeholders) of the programme been taken into account in the Terms of Reference?	Non-prescriptive	Non-prescriptive
13. To what extent do the Terms or Reference focus on the assessment of (unintended) outcomes and impacts?	Semi-prescriptive	Semi-prescriptive
Questions in blue: The five key issues identified by the European Commission (2004) as essential for inclusion in the ToR Questions in black: New questions		

According to the data presented in the above table, only six of the thirteen questions were classified in the same way in both cases (numbers 2, 4, 5, 9, 12, and 13). Of these six

common answers, only three relate to the mandatory aspects that the EC requires to be included in the ToR (numbers 2, 4, and 9).

The data also show that out of the thirteen questions, five are considered semi-prescriptive or prescriptive in the ToR of the FORGEC programme, whereas the same questions appear as non-prescriptive or open in the ToR of the IMPALA programme. These questions are numbers 1, 6, 7, 8, and 10. Conversely, only two questions (numbers 3 and 11) are semi-prescriptive or prescriptive in the IMPALA programme but non-prescriptive or semi-prescriptive in the ToR of the FORGEC programme.

In the questions relating to the mandatory topics that, according to the EC, must be included in the ToR of an evaluation, all topics in the FORGEC project are classified as semi-prescriptive or prescriptive. However, in the IMPALA ToR, the answers are distributed among the four categories. In both cases, there is no reference to the involvement of direct beneficiaries during the writing of the ToR.

Finally, I can see that in the ToR of the FORGEC programme, most of the answers fall into the semi-prescriptive or prescriptive categories, and only two of them fall into the non-prescriptive category. In the IMPALA programme, I can see that the thirteen questions are distributed across all categories.

Second analysis: To determine the degree of prescriptiveness of the ToR, the responses to the 13 Q-ToR questions were expressed as percentages.

Table 13

Comparison of the Grade of Prescriptiveness of the ToR of FORGEC and IMPALA programmes

Grade of Prescriptiveness	ToR - Case FORGEC		ToR - Case IMPALA	
	Total number of questions	%	Total number of questions	%
Non-prescriptive	2	15.38%	3	23.07%

(In the ToR, the information detailed in the Q-ToR checklist does not appear in any form)				
Open (In the ToR, the information requested in the Q-ToR checklist appears in a non-explicit form)	0	0%	2	15.38%
Semi-prescriptive (In the ToR, the information requested in the Q-ToR checklist appears explicitly but not in its totality)	6	46.15%	4	30.76%
Prescriptive (In the ToR, the information requested in the Q-ToR checklist appears explicitly in its totality.)	5	38.46%	4	30.76%
TYPE	HIGHLY PRESCRIPTIVE		LESS PRESCRIPTIVE	

The results indicate that the ToR of the FORGEC programme is more prescriptive than those of the IMPALA programme. After analysing all the data, I can observe that the direct beneficiaries were not considered in either ToR. Therefore, their expectations or needs were not considered at any point in the process. I also noticed that only in the FORGEC case the methodology to be followed by the external evaluator is well described I am therefore faced with two different types of ToR and, by analysing the external evaluation reports, I will be able to determine which role the evaluator played in the external evaluation and how he/she applied the ToR.

6.3 Comparison of the Evaluation Reports

The evaluation reports have been compared to determine whether the external evaluators have followed the guidelines of the ToR or whether they have contributed new aspects that were not included in the ToR. The reports have been compared based on the

results of my meta-evaluation done through the EV-Form. The comparison has been divided in the 3 criteria distinguished in the EV-Form: impartiality, equity and quality.

The impartiality criteria focus on the type of evaluation conducted, whether it an internal or external evaluation. In both cases the implementing unit hired an external evaluator. Therefore, the evaluation reports are equally impartial because in both cases the evaluation was done by an external evaluator that has no previous relationship with the programs.

The equity criteria focus in three different aspects: Involvement of any of the project's stakeholders in the evaluation process, evaluation questions are formulated with clarity and adapted to the context of the project and the accessibility of the stakeholders to the evaluation reports. To answer this criterion, I have analysed the evaluation reports and consider the interviews done by the external evaluators and the responsible of writing the ToR as recipients of the reports.

The results of the equity criteria are different in relation to the involvement of the stakeholders in the moment of drafting the evaluation process (in the FORGEC process of evaluation there is no stakeholder's involvement, and in the IMPALA, there was limited involvement of the consortium). Formally, the FORGEC evaluation reports did not include the evaluation questions, but I can find them in the IMPALA reports. Finally, in both cases the evaluation reports were given to the implementing unit, as it was the responsible to disseminate them among all the stakeholders of the project. I will discuss this criterion in more detail in section 6.3.2.

The quality criteria focus on the verification of the established processing guidelines of the evaluation. I have been analysed and compared the information required in the ToR vs. the information that appears in the reports and the degree to which the information regarding the EV-Form quality criteria is present in the evaluation reports of both projects and fulfils the requirements set in the ToR. Due the detailed analysis of the 78 quality-related questions in the

EV-Form, the results show only slight differences between the evaluation reports of the two cases. In relation to the first analysis of the quality criteria and considering that the ToR of the FORGEC program were more prescriptive, the IMPALA's external evaluator introduced a considerable amount of information in the reports that was not covered by the ToR. After the second analysis related to the grade of information that appears in the EV-Form quality criteria was present in the evaluation reports of both projects and fulfils the requirements set in the ToR, the data shows that the IMPALA evaluation reports appear to be more rigorous than those of FORGEC, as the latter has a higher number of incomplete or absent information points

It is important to note that both evaluators provided supplementary information or elaborated on certain aspects of the ToR in greater detail. In both instances, the additional information pertains to two distinct subject areas: voice of the external evaluators and stakeholders' involvement. I will discuss this criterion in more detail in section 6.3.3.

6.3.1 Comparison of the Impartiality Criteria of the External Evaluations

There is no variability at all in these criteria, since in both cases, FORGEC and IMPALA, the evaluation was conducted by an external evaluator.

6.3.2 Comparison of the Equity Criteria of the External Evaluations

The Equity Criteria is based in the formulation and accessibility of the evaluation reports and is focus on three different aspects.

- Aspect 1: Involvement of any of the project's stakeholders in the evaluation process: This direct question helped me to find the answer to the following question: am I facing a participatory evaluation process or not? In the FORGEC reports, there is no reference to the participation of any stakeholder, including the consortium, in the evaluation process. In this case, the implementing unit wrote the ToR, and the external evaluator followed them to carry out the evaluation.

There is also no reference to any kind of approval of the evaluation methodology chosen by the evaluator to carry out the evaluation. In the IMPALA reports, I can see references to the consortium in both the MTER and the FER—not in the definition of the methodology, but in its approval. For example, the external evaluator wrote that the consortium asked the evaluator to assess the coherence of the project, although this specific point was not requested in the ToR. The doubt I had was about the meaning of 'consortium'. Is the external evaluator referring to the whole HEI (beneficiaries + implementing unit) or only to the implementing unit of the programme?

- Aspect 2: Evaluation questions are formulated with clarity and adapted to the context of the project: In the case of the FORGEC reports, they were not included. While the description of the evaluation and its different sections are available, the questions for each of them are not. In contrast, the IMPALA reports include the aforementioned questions, which have been adapted to align with the project's context.
- Aspect 3: Accessibility of the reports for stakeholders: In both cases, the external evaluators delivered the evaluation reports to the implementing unit, which then distributed them among the project stakeholders. Therefore, direct beneficiaries had access to them.

6.3.3. Comparison of the Quality Criteria of the External Evaluations

I analysed the following nine different quality aspects using crosstabulation for each section and/or subsection:

- C.1. Compliance with requirements
- C.2. Context analysis

- C.3. Design and method (52 questions)
- C.4. Reliability of the data
- C.5. Data solidity
- C.6. Credibility of findings
- C.7. Conclusions
- C.8. Recommendations
- C.9. Clarity of the evaluation

6.3.3.1 Comparison of the Information Required in the ToR and the Information That Appears in the Final Reports (Quality Criteria)

This comparison was based on the information presented in the external evaluation reports of the FORGEC and IMPALA programmes. This comparison allows us to ascertain whether the external evaluator has included additional information beyond that specified in the ToR, as outlined in the EV-Form. This document provides a comprehensive overview of the evaluation criteria set forth by the EC, along with new elements not previously considered or detailed.

Table 14

Comparison of the Quality Criteria in the EV-Form and the ToR of the FORGEC and IMPALA Programmes

78 Questions on the quality aspect in our EV-Form	FORGEC	IMPALA
Number of questions of the EV-Form related to quality criteria that appear in the ToR	50	37
Number of questions of the EV-Form related to the quality criteria that do not appear in the ToR (new or concrete aspects)	28	41
Number of questions from this new or concrete aspects that the external evaluator has made some references in the evaluation report	6	26

In the final evaluation of both projects, it was observed that the external evaluators had analysed new information not included in the ToR of either project. Upon analysis, it was

found that 50 of the 78 quality criteria outlined in the EV-Form were also included in the ToR of the FORGEC project. Of the 28 new issues identified in the EV-Form, the evaluator addressed six in the report. Conversely, only 37 correspondences were identified between the EV-Form quality criteria and the ToR of the IMPALA project. In this instance, the EV-Form encompasses 41 novel criteria. The external evaluator of the IMPALA project has addressed 26 of the aforementioned criteria in the report. Considering these observations, it seems evident that the ToR of the IMPALA project are less prescriptive, and that the evaluator has introduced a significant amount of additional information.

Of the six aspects the external evaluator of the FORGEC programme included in the FE report, five are also included in the IMPALA FE report. These are:

1. *Description of the methodology:*

- *Are different data collection methods applied, covering quantitative and qualitative aspects?*
- *Does the evaluation describe the rationality for selecting a concrete method of analysis?*

2. *Reliability of the data (how the data have been obtained and used during the evaluation process):*

- *Does the evaluation describe the sampling for the evaluation process?*

3. *Credibility of findings (analysed data must be reliable and balanced):*

- *Do the evaluation results reflect in an acceptable way the reality of the intervention as perceived by the actors and beneficiaries?*

4. *Clarity of the evaluation (easy to read and logically structured report including an executive summary)*

- *Is the evaluation report relevant to the country/region?*

The only question that does not appear in the IMPALA FE reports is: “Does the evaluation include a discussion on how the mix of data sources was used to obtain a diversity of perspectives, ensure data accuracy, and overcome data limits?” (related to the reliability of data).

In this comparison, it is evident that the external evaluators of both cases have introduced new elements pertaining to the methodology, reliability of data, credibility, and clarity of the evaluation. In my view, three of these questions are of particular significance in the context of this research. The first concerns the rationale behind the methodology employed in the evaluation process. The second relates to the perception of the actors and beneficiaries regarding the execution of the project. The third pertains to the relevance of the evaluation report to the country or region where the project is being implemented.

The final two questions pertain to the beneficiaries, namely individuals and regions/countries. Consequently, it is evident that both external evaluators, despite not being specifically tasked with assessing these aspects in the ToR of either case, consider them crucial for the final evaluation and, consequently, for the projects.

Furthermore, it is evident that the external evaluator's analysis of the IMPALA programme included a total of 29 quality criteria that were not explicitly outlined in the ToR. Of these, five are present in both the FORGEC and IMPALA external evaluations but absent from the ToR. However, the external evaluation of the IMPALA project also analyses ten quality criteria not included in the IMPALA ToR but present in the FORGEC ToR. Consequently, the IMPALA external evaluator incorporated information into the FE report that is typically present in the ToR but absent in this case. These criteria are:

- 1. Compliance with the requirements (this criterion assesses whether or not the requirements that appear in the ToR are adequately addressed):*

- *Does the evaluation adequately address questions according to the questions asked in the ToR?*
2. *Evaluation design:*
- *Methodology – approach to data collection and analysis and stakeholders' participation*
3. *Annexes or information that should be included:*
- *Data collection instruments*
 - *Groups of people interviewed, or actors involved in the process*
4. *Planning*
- *Does the evaluation submit a work plan?*
5. *Relevant stakeholders' involvement*
- *Does the evaluation present a concrete list of stakeholders that have participated in the assessment?*
 - *Does the evaluation define the different stakeholders of the project?*
6. *Reliability of the data (how the data have been obtained and used during the evaluation process)*
- *Does the evaluation describe the data sources of the analysed documents?*
7. *Credibility of findings (analysed data must be reliable and balanced)*
- *Do the evaluation results reflect in an acceptable way the reality described by the data and evidence recorded?*
8. *Clarity of the evaluation (easy to read and logically structured report, including an executive summary)*
- *Is the evaluation report efficient?*

Finally, the external evaluator also analyses 11 quality criteria that did not appear in any of the ToR for either project, nor in the FORGEC's FE Report. These are the following:

1. *Evaluation design:*

- *Organisational chart*
- *Outputs and reports*

2. *Annexes or information that should be included:*

- *Evaluation questions*
- *Evaluation matrix*

3. *Composition of the evaluation team*

- *Does the evaluation present a brief presentation of the evaluation team?*

4. *Relevant stakeholders' involvement*

- *Does the evaluation explain if it was designed as a participatory process?*

5. *Application of the DAC Criteria*

- *Does the evaluation adequately assess the coherence of the project?*

6. *Description of the methodology*

- *Are indicators described, where relevant (previous indicators, national statistics...*
- *Are any log frames, result chains or other theory of change frame (including indicators) used as a reference document for the assessment?*

7. *Reliability of the data (how the data have been obtained and used during the evaluation process)*

- *Does the evaluation describe the rationale for their selection and their limitations?*

8. *Clarity of the evaluation (easy to read and logically structured report including an executive summary)*

- *Is the evaluation easy to read and logically structured with clarity and coherence (e.g. Background and objectives – findings – conclusions and recommendations)?*

As I can observed in the comparison the voice of the external evaluator in the reports are worthy note. Both reports adhere to the ToR but employ distinct approaches to not only offer recommendations or conclusions but also elucidate potential avenues for future action based on the outcomes of the projects and the perspectives of the direct beneficiaries. Stakeholders' involvement could be done during the drafting of the ToR or at the point of approving the methodology. Alternatively, the evaluator may request the inclusion of specific points in the evaluation report. In the IMPALA programme, the external evaluator presents the methodology to the consortium, which subsequently approves it.

6.3.3.2 Comparison of the Degree of Information that is Required in the ToR and the Information that Appears in the Reports (Quality Criteria)

In this analysis, I compared the degree to which the information regarding the EV-Form quality criteria is present in the evaluation reports of both projects and fulfils the requirements set in the ToR.

Table 15

Degree of the Information Detail in the Evaluation Reports of the FORGEC and IMPALA Programmes

Definition Scores	Scores	Total number of Answers			
		FORGEC Mid-Term Evaluation Report	FORGEC Final Evaluation Report	IMPALA Mid-Term Evaluation Report	IMPALA Final Evaluation Report

		(MTER)	(FER)	(MTER)	(FER)
The evaluation report does not contain the information specified in the EV-Form question in any form	1	23	27	20	19
The evaluation report contains the information specified in the EV-Form question but not in its totality	2	8	6	14	13
The evaluation report contains the information specified in the EV-Form question explicitly in its totality	3	40	34	31	31
The evaluation report contains the information specified in the EV-Form question and include complementary data.	4	9	13	10	15
The evaluation report provides more information than required by the Terms of Reference.	5	1	1	6	3

Table 15 reflexes the results of the first analysis (comparison of mid-term and final evaluation reports between cases):

- Score 1: FORGEC project has the higher score (50 answers vs. 39 for IMPALA), indicating that in FORGEC evaluation reports performs worse in providing information.

- Score 2: FORGEC has the lower score (14 answers vs. 27 in IMPALA), suggesting that FORGEC is worst at including some kind of information but not in its totality.
- Score 3: FORGEC has the higher score (74 answers vs. 62 in IMPALA) indicating that it excels in presenting information explicitly and in its totality.
- Score 4: FORGEC has the lower score (20 answers vs. 25 in IMPALA), so in the IMPALA evaluation reports and according to the questions of our meta-evaluation, the evaluator has included more information than the expected when talking to information required in the ToR.
- Score 5: In this case, we find more information in the IMPALA evaluation reports than in the FORGEC evaluation reports that was not required in the ToR. The main findings of this section are given in point 6.5 of this chapter).

6.4 Comparison of the Analysis of the Direct Beneficiaries' Perceptions

One of the ways to find out about the perceptions of the direct beneficiaries in relation to the external evaluation is to carry out semi-structured interviews. The analysis of the direct beneficiaries' perceptions is based on the responses provided by the interviewees in both cases and is structured through four operational questions. The following analysis was conducted: a general comparison between the FORGEC and IMPALA cases; a comparison between direct beneficiaries with different roles in their institutions; a comparison between universities in capital cities and those in other regions; and a comparison between universities in different countries.

To make these comparisons, I have based it on the following four aspects analysed: a) the importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries; b) the impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project; c) the opinion of the

direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out and d) the value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries.

6.4.1 *General Comparison Between Case FORGEC and Case IMPALA*

The importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. This aspect focused on external evaluation in general, not only those related to FORGEC and IMPALA projects. Following the analysis of the data, it can be stated that all participants (whether or not they participated in the external evaluation in that concrete projects) agree on the importance of external evaluation in general for several reasons. These include the provision of feedback to facilitate improvements to existing projects and the use of external evaluations as models for new projects. External evaluations, in general, are also a way of acquiring knowledge and enhancing skills, both on an individual and institutional level. Furthermore, the participants express that the knowledge of the results of the external evaluation, even in the absence of direct involvement, is of significant value. In the case of FORGEC and IMPALA, some participants affirmed that it was important to know that the objectives of the program have been achieved and the accountability of the program, although their needs had not been considered. For other participants, the evaluations of these programs were only informative, as their needs have not been considered, and evaluations did not provide new knowledge to them. Some participants focused the importance of the IMPALA methodology used by the external evaluator, as this methodology was not related to evaluation process in their university. Additionally, some participants did not receive the evaluation results. Therefore, the impact the evaluations may have been completely nullified for those participants that did not receive the feed-back of the evaluations. In FORGEC and IMPALA programmes, participants emphasise the importance of establishing clear evaluation objectives prior to the execution of the evaluation process. Participants of both programs also emphasise the idea of

contextualisation of the evaluation to focus the evaluation, considering that the same methodologies cannot be applied in different context with different characteristics.

The impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project. There is a general consensus among FORGEC and IMPALA participants that involvement in an external evaluation can be a catalyst for change. These opinions are based on the respondents' personal experience of participation in the external evaluation of the FORGEC and IMPALA projects (if this was the case) or alternatively, their personal experience of participation in other projects that were externally evaluated. In the FORGEC programme, there is a divergence of opinion as to whether changes can occur at the institutional level. While some participants believe that such changes can occur, others hold the view that they can only occur gradually. Participants in the IMPALA programme also hold differing views on this subject. Some participants believe that external evaluations can result in tangible changes at the institutional level in specific areas, whereas others hold the view that external evaluations prompt internal reflection processes. At the individual level, opinions diverge further. Participants in the FORGEC programme believe that external evaluation can influence personal and professional interrelations, a view shared by some participants in the IMPALA programme. However, others in the IMPALA programme hold the view that external evaluation affects only the professional aspects of their lives, with no impact on their personal lives. In those concrete cases, some participants did not receive the results of the evaluation, so there is no impact as individuals in that case.

The opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out. In both cases, participants express similar opinions. It is imperative that the needs or expectations of the direct participants be taken into consideration during the design of external evaluations. Furthermore, it is essential to include more precise criteria in defining the objectives of such evaluations. It is recommended that external evaluations be conducted with greater dialogue

between external evaluators and direct beneficiaries. This would enable external evaluators to gain a better understanding of the programme context and cultural differences and modify the pre-established evaluation criteria. The participants appreciated in both cases (FORGEC and IMPALA) the involvement of both external evaluators, who attempted to understand more about the project and evaluation context. In both cases, the idea of measuring the impact of the programme is also a common thread.

The value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. For those participating in the FORGEC programme, the value of the evaluation is contingent upon the outcomes and impacts of the programme itself. Additionally, some participants have indicated that the value of an evaluation may be enhanced if the evaluation incorporates the needs of the direct beneficiaries. The participants of the IMPALA programme generally consider the value of an external evaluation to be contingent upon the utility of the information it provides. Furthermore, they posit that the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the evaluation's conceptualisation could enhance this value. All participants concur that effectiveness is linked to the evaluation process itself. It comprises an appropriate definition of the objectives to be achieved, a satisfactory implementation of the project, and a clear presentation of the results and outcomes.

Conclusions

External evaluations in general are crucial for direct beneficiaries, as they provide valuable feedback for project improvements and as models for new initiatives, although in this concrete research direct beneficiaries did not consider evaluations as a way of improvement at all because the evaluation focus mainly on the objectives, outputs and accountability of the projects. They enhance knowledge and skills at both individual and institutional levels. Evaluation objectives and contextualisation of the evaluation are key point for all the interviewees, as the context can determine the project and by extension the evaluation and the

criteria of the evaluation should consider the context. External evaluations can drive change, although not all the participants have the same opinion, as it differs on the extent of impact at institutional and individual levels. Direct beneficiaries' needs, expectations and dialogue between them and the external evaluator is crucial for effective evaluations. For the participants, the value of evaluations is linked to their outcomes, utility, and the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the process.

6.4.2 Comparison Between Direct Beneficiaries with Different Roles in Their Institutions

In this comparison, I have distinguished two different roles: senior leaders and others (middle managers, faculty or trainers). In the case of FORGEC, self-employed individuals have been excluded from this comparison, as their characteristics (as entrepreneurs) are highly different from the other participants (all of whom work at the university).

The importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. In this case, all of them share a common view on the significance of external evaluations in general. The value they place on these evaluations stems from the insights they gain regarding the implementation and outcomes of various actions. Additionally, they consider the recommendations in the evaluation reports to be crucial to improve the projects (in the case of mid-term evaluations) or as a role model for new initiatives (in the case of the final evaluations).

The impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project. In light of the fact that changes are regarded as beneficial, it is evident that there are discrepancies between the perspectives of senior leaders in this regard. In the case of the FORGEC programme, both senior leaders concur that institutional changes are feasible in certain specific areas of the university, although they acknowledge that this will require a significant investment of time. On the other hand, one senior leader associated with the IMPALA programme espouses a similar perspective. However, the other senior leader in this group holds a different view, suggesting that while institutional reflection may be a valuable

avenue to pursue, it may not be feasible to implement comprehensive institutional changes at this stage.

At the personal level, a similar discrepancy is observed. About the FORGEC programme, senior leaders posit that individuals may undergo a transformation subsequent to the outcomes of an external evaluation, with these changes manifesting at the personal and professional levels. In the case of the IMPALA programme, one senior leader shares the same opinion as that of the FORGEC programme's senior leaders, whereas the other holds a differing view. In this case, the senior leaders posit that individuals can undergo professional transformation, but not personal transformation. Regarding the remaining participants, a number of differences emerge.

With respect to the FORGEC programme, most participants, except one, hold the view that institutions can undergo change. Furthermore, they concur that individuals can undergo change at both the personal and professional levels. In the case of the IMPALA programme, once more, a diversity of views is evident. While some participants believe in individual change at both levels, others adhere to the conviction that change can only occur at the professional level, with no corresponding change at the personal level.

The opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out.

Most participants expressed a similar viewpoint. It is recommended that evaluations be conducted with consideration for the needs of the beneficiaries at the time of evaluation design, analysing the criteria that will be used during the performance of the evaluation. Participants of IMPALA project stress the idea of that impact measurement should also be included in the evaluation. Dialogue and exchange of opinion between the external evaluator and the direct beneficiaries is an effective method for fulfilling the expectations of direct beneficiaries in relation to external evaluation to mitigate their no consideration in the moment of drafting the ToR. This opinion is shared by the senior leaders of both programmes and the

other participants. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the opinions of the two groups.

The value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. The senior leaders of the FORGEC programme concur that the value of external evaluation is contingent upon the extent to which the results of such evaluation can facilitate improvement, particularly in terms of outcomes and impact. Conversely, one of the senior leaders of the IMPALA programme posits that external evaluation is valuable if it provides insights that are not already known. Regarding the remaining participants, it is evident that their responses exhibit a notable degree of consistency regarding the perceived value of external evaluation. In both cases, the value is seen to reside in the acquisition of new knowledge and the demonstration of impact.

The effectiveness of the evaluation is perceived by senior leaders and the majority of participants as a means of demonstrating that the objectives of the programme have been achieved in a satisfactory manner and that the results correspond to the expected outcomes.

Conclusions

There is consensus in relation to the importance of external evaluations, although senior leaders and other participants have mixed views on the impact of evaluations. Some of them believe in both institutional and personal changes, while others only see changes at the professional level. Beneficiaries' needs should be considered in the evaluation process and impact measurement should be included. Dialogue between external evaluators and beneficiaries is crucial for a valuable evaluation. The value of evaluations lies in facilitating improvements and providing new insights. Effectiveness is demonstrated by meeting program objectives and achieving expected outcomes.

6.4.3 Comparison Between Universities Located in the Capital and Those in Other Regions of the Country

In this case, the comparative analysis has been conducted between the universities situated in the national capitals, La Habana and Bogotá, and the universities located in Camagüey and San José de las Lajas, which are situated in different regional contexts.

The importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. In this case, the opinion of the participants from both types of universities is the same; all of them place a high value on external evaluations in general although in general and also in these specific evaluations, they miss their participation throughout the entire evaluation process which makes these evaluations merely informative.

The impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project. The participants from the capital universities hold diverse perspectives on this matter. In the context of Havana, the outcomes of external assessments can exert an indirect influence upon the institution, following a period of reflection, and upon individuals, resulting in changes to their thinking and behaviour. In the case of the university located in Bogotá, the evaluations have the potential to prompt reflection within the institution and facilitate tangible changes in the way of working. However, it is less evident that they have a similar impact at the individual level.

The consensus among those at regional universities is that the outcomes of the external evaluation affect the institution on a specific, tangible level and the individual on both a personal and, subsequently, professional one.

Consequently, there is a notable divergence in opinion on this topic.

The opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out. It is the view of capital universities that the needs of those who will directly benefit from the programme should be considered at the outset of the evaluation process. In addition, the

context of the programme should also be considered, and its impact should be evaluated.

Regional universities also consider the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the design of the evaluation as a fundamental aspect, as well as the impact measurement of the project. It is essential that the objectives and indicators of the evaluation are clearly defined from the outset of the programme and sometimes the criteria of the evaluation should be reviewed before the evaluation was conducted.

In this instance, no distinction is drawn between the types of universities.

The value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. Capital universities attach value to the evaluations if they can facilitate improvements in the specific programme or in new programmes. In the case of the Bogotá participants, the new knowledge that can be brought to them is of concrete value. An evaluation may be deemed valuable yet still fail to contribute new ideas. The effectiveness of an external evaluation is contingent upon the performance and results of the programme and activities.

In addition, regional universities place value on external evaluations based on the beneficial insights they offer. The effectiveness of such evaluations is contingent upon the evaluation process itself, including the definition and achievement of objectives at the conclusion of the programme, the implementation of activities, and the generation of results and outcomes.

A review of this response reveals few discernible differences.

Conclusions

Participants from both capital and regional universities highly value external evaluations. Capital universities see evaluations as catalysts for institutional reflection and change and regional universities emphasize tangible impacts at both institutional and individual levels. Beneficiaries' needs, context and clear objectives should be considered for effective evaluations. Participants stress the idea of value of the evaluation linked to

facilitating improvements and providing new insights. Effectiveness lies in the idea of achieving program goals and outcomes. Despite some differences, the overall consensus underscores the importance of external evaluations.

6.4.4 *Comparison Between Universities Located in Different Countries*

In this case, the comparison will be based on the previous one, as only one out of the four universities is not from Cuba, and it is located in Colombia.

The importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. External evaluation in general is a crucial aspect for all universities, regardless of their country of origin.

The impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project. The majority of participants from Cuban universities concur that external evaluation can influence and drive change at the institutional and individual levels, including personal and professional spheres, but participants need to receive the feedback of the evaluation to be influenced.

In contrast, the Colombian university participants hold a different view, namely that only certain reflections can be made at the institutional level, while individual changes can be reflected at the professional level but not at the personal level.

The opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out. In this case, there is no distinction between the participants from Cuban and Colombian universities, as they all assert that their needs and expectations should be considered during the design of external evaluations. Furthermore, they emphasise that these evaluations should encompass not only the results and outcomes but also the impact that projects have on the surrounding context. It is also essential to consider the context in which the programme has been developed, as well as a clear definition of its objectives at the time of the evaluation.

The value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries. The participants from Cuban universities identified two principal benefits of the external

evaluation: the potential for programme improvement and the opportunity to serve as a model for future programmes or actions. Accordingly, as the Colombian university participants asserted, an external evaluation is valuable if it provides new information to the direct beneficiaries. The new information will facilitate improvements.

All Cuban and Colombian university participants concur that effectiveness is contingent upon the programme's objectives, activities, outputs, and outcomes. Nevertheless, for an evaluation to be effective, it must also have clearly defined objectives and indicators, as indicated by some of the participants.

Conclusions

All participants highlight the importance of external evaluations in general. Cuban participants believe that evaluations drive institutional and individual change, but Colombian participants only see changes mainly at the professional level. All participants agree that effective and valuable evaluations should consider their needs, the context of the evaluation and have clear objectives from the beginning. Cuban participants value evaluations for program improvement and as models for future actions, while Colombians value new information. Effectiveness depends on achieving program objectives and outcomes, and goals and indicators of the evaluation should be defined at the beginning of the project.

6.5 Conclusions. Research Findings

After all the comparisons, I have reached the following findings.

1. Based on an analysis of the Terms of Reference (ToR):

- The interests of the direct beneficiaries were not considered at the time the ToR were drafted. This finding has been corroborated by the individuals responsible for drafting the ToR in both cases.

- The degree of prescriptiveness of the ToR does not always determine the outcome of the evaluations. The flexibility inherent in the interpretation of the ToR may permit evaluators to address a more expansive range of topics, thereby facilitating a more comprehensive examination of novel aspects.

2. *Based on the analysis of the evaluation reports:*

- The key role of the external evaluator. Derived from the meta-evaluation of the Final Evaluation Reports (FER) of both cases, concerns the role of external evaluators. Following an analysis of the FER, it becomes evident that the role of the external evaluator is crucial. In this research, two distinct evaluations were conducted, each with a different type of ToR. The ToR for the IMPALA project were less prescriptive, allowing for a broader and more detailed evaluation by the external evaluator than those for the FORGEC project. Although there were some discrepancies between the two ToR, the outcome of the evaluations was quite similar because of the role of the external evaluator.
- The incorporation of new information can enhance the comprehensiveness and detail of the FER reports, offering a more comprehensive and detailed perspective of the project.

3. *Based on the analysis of the direct beneficiaries' perceptions*

- External evaluations are of great importance to direct beneficiaries in general if they fulfil their expectations.

- There is consensus among direct beneficiaries that evaluations should consider the needs and contexts from the outset.
- External evaluations have a tangible impact at both the institutional and individual levels, although this is contingent on the country in which the university is based. In this case, it is important to note that all Cuban universities are public institutions, whereas the Colombian university is a private one.
- The involvement of direct beneficiaries in the design and implementation of evaluations is a critical factor in increasing the value and effectiveness of these evaluations, as evidenced in both cases.

Chapter 7: Discussion

7.1 Introduction

The findings of this study have confirmed the importance of the Terms of Reference (ToR) when planning the external evaluation of a project, particularly the way they have been drafted. However, the role of the external evaluator has emerged as a particularly salient issue because of the analysis of the evaluation reports and the interviews conducted with direct beneficiaries. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that direct beneficiaries attach significant value to external evaluations when the evaluations offer novel insights and are aligned with their needs and not only verify if the project's objectives have been achieved, or the projects accountability.

This chapter is structured into three sections. The first section addresses the operational questions that were used to answer the sub-questions and the main research question. The second section engages in a discussion comparing the findings with the literature review and the theoretical framework of the research. This discussion will lead us to the final chapter, where we will answer our main research question.

7.2 Discussion

7.2.1 Responses to the Operational Research Questions

7.2.1.1 What Information is Included in the ToR for the External Evaluation?

The first operational research question can be addressed by referring to the findings related to the ToR. In both cases, the guidance provided was prescriptive, although the degree of prescriptiveness was less than that observed in the IMPALA ToR.

However, the most significant aspect was not the information included in the ToR but rather the absence of information. The ToR failed to account for the participation of direct beneficiaries at any stage of the conceptualization process. This finding was significant

because it helped identify beneficiaries' perspectives regarding external assessment outcomes. Therefore, in this research, I can see a gap between the idea promoted by the EC, which emphasises that the needs of direct beneficiaries should be considered in the evaluation process, and what is written in the ToR, which does not refer to these needs at any point.

7.2.1.2 What is the View of the External Evaluator on the ToR and on the ICBHE Evaluation?

The second operational research question can be addressed by referring to the aspects that the external evaluators consider essential for the success of the evaluation (see Chapter 5 and Chapter 6).

The two external evaluators agreed on the ToR, which they consider essential for determining both the type of evaluation to be undertaken and its specific objectives. Additionally, both evaluators concur that the ToR serve as the foundation for the evaluation process, but their role extends beyond that, providing a comprehensive response at the conclusion of the evaluation.

Regarding the evaluations of ICBHE programs, they were considered fundamental for determining the effectiveness and compliance of the intervention, as well as assessing whether the intended goals were met. Moreover, they serve as a foundation for new initiatives by providing insights and recommendations in evaluation reports. This is possible thanks to the independence they have to carry out their work, but also because they try to understand the context of the evaluation and the project.

7.2.1.3. How Have the External Evaluators Compiled Their Reports?

The third operational research question can be addressed by referring to the findings related to the analysis of the evaluation reports.

In this instance, both external evaluators adhered to the ToR of the evaluation but also introduced new information that was not explicitly outlined in the ToR. The inclusion of this

supplementary data rendered the reports more comprehensive and facilitated a more detailed understanding of the project. In some instances, this supplementary data arose from interviews with direct beneficiaries conducted by the external evaluators during the evaluation process.

In this case, the key finding is the role that external evaluators play. In the aforementioned cases, projects with distinct ToR ultimately yielded comparable reports due to the influence of external evaluators. In the IMPALA project, the evaluators were completely unaware of the context of the project and the evaluation. However, he/she made an effort to minimise this lack of knowledge and to understand and respond to the requirements of the ToR. He/she also kept the direct beneficiaries in mind when conducting the evaluation. This finding gives rise to an important question: What would an external evaluation entail if the external evaluator merely adhered to the instructions set forth in the ToR, without incorporating new insights or supplementary information? In the concluding chapter, I endeavour to address this question.

7.2.1.4. How Do the Direct Beneficiaries Perceive the Evaluation of ICBHE Projects?

The last operational research question can be addressed by referring to the findings related to the analysis of the direct beneficiaries' perceptions. This question has been articulated through four concrete aspects, which were analysed with reference to the answers provided in the semi-structured interviews conducted with the direct beneficiaries: a) the importance of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries; b) the impact of the external evaluation results at institutions or individuals involved in the project; c) the opinion of the direct beneficiaries in how the evaluation should be carried out and d) the value and effectiveness of external evaluation for direct beneficiaries.

External evaluations were important to direct beneficiaries, who emphasized the necessity for these evaluations to be tailored to their needs and contexts from the start. A

consensus emerged among beneficiaries that such considerations are crucial for the effectiveness of the evaluations. However, in the evaluations analysis in this research, direct beneficiaries' needs were not considered at the beginning of the evaluation process. Beneficiaries also argued that both the methodology should be tailored to the context and that external evaluators should be familiar with the context. Therefore, in both cases, evaluations do not answer their concrete needs, as they were not considered at the moment of drafting the ToR, the methodologies applied were already determined although the external evaluators tried to understand and be familiar with the context and with the participants. Additionally, external evaluations, in general, have a tangible impact at both the institutional and individual levels, though this impact may vary depending on the country as I can see in that research (e.g., Cuban universities are public institutions, while the Colombian university is private). But this impact is only possible if project participants receive the evaluation feedback and reports. In this case, the external evaluators followed the establishment mechanism and confirmed that they sent the results to the implementing unit, which then forwarded them to the institutions participating in the project. Unfortunately, communication within some of the institutions was not efficient, and some project participants did not receive the results. Thus, the impact of these evaluations is less than what could have been expected at the individual level, but I do not know if the evaluation reports had an impact at the institutional level. Finally, evidence from both cases demonstrates that the involvement of direct beneficiaries in the design and implementation of evaluations is an important factor in enhancing the value and effectiveness of these evaluations. However, it is not possible to value an evaluation or determine its effectiveness if the direct participants (individuals in that case) have not received its results.

7.2.2 Responses to the Research Sub-questions

7.2.2.1 RSQ1: How does the design of the evaluation process facilitate the participation of direct beneficiaries?

To answer the first sub-question, I referenced the responses provided to the first operational research question. The data show that there is a gap between the donors and the implementing unit. Direct beneficiaries have not been considered in the moment of drafting the ToR of the evaluation by the implementing unit. Thus, direct beneficiaries' needs and expectations have not been considered. This no-consideration could affect the perception of the direct beneficiaries in relation to the value and effectiveness of the external evaluation.

7.2.2.2 RSQ2: How does the external evaluator influence the engagement with direct beneficiaries in the evaluation process?

To answer the second sub-question, I referenced the responses provided to the second and third operational research questions.

In light of the responses to the operational research questions, it can be posited that the external evaluators have the capacity to influence the methodology employed in the production of an external evaluation report, and consequently, its outcomes. While the ToR may dictate the methodology to be employed in conducting external evaluations, external evaluators are at liberty to either adhere to the prescribed methodology or supplement it with new information. This additional information may potentially alter the ultimate outcome of an evaluation report, and consequently, the perception of direct beneficiaries regarding external evaluations and reports.

7.2.2.3 RSQ3: How do the direct beneficiaries perceive the effectiveness of the evaluation process?

Considering the responses to the initial two research sub-questions, it can be posited that ToR are fundamental to the process of conducting a project evaluation. Furthermore, it

can be inferred that the ToR may encompass the methodology to be employed. However, it is evident that this methodology, in addition to being implemented in its entirety, can be adapted whenever the external evaluator deems it necessary to incorporate further data or adjust its application. Consequently, the outcome of the evaluation—namely, the report—will depend not only on the ToR but also on the extent to which the external evaluator is involved in the preparation of the report.

It can be stated that the perception of the direct beneficiaries regarding the evaluations is entirely dependent on the ToR and the methodology employed by the external evaluator of the project.

7.2.3 Discussion of Literature

The objective of this section is to establish a connection between the findings and the literature review, referring to the existing theories, with agency theory as the central framework.

7.2.3.1 The Interests of the Direct Beneficiaries Were Not Considered at the Time the ToR Were Drafted.

This finding highlights a potential agency problem (c.f. 2.2.3) between the agent (implementing unit) and the principal (donor), as the agent only follows to the principal's instructions in relation of the ToR but not the idea of considering the beneficiaries in the whole process of evaluation. This directly impacts in the direct beneficiaries' perception of the external evaluation.

This idea can be also complemented by stakeholders theory (c.f. 2.1.3.2), that emphasise the importance of considering all stakeholders' interest, participatory evaluation theory (c.f., 2.1.4.3) that supports the idea of including direct beneficiaries from the beginning in all the phases of the evaluation process, and finally, North-South partnership (c.f. 2.1.2.4) and the power imbalances in evaluation process that exclude the beneficiaries' voices.

As discussed in the literature chapter (c.f. 2.1.4.4), the ToR represent an indispensable and crucial element for conducting an evaluation. Some authors (Chen et al., 2024; Odera, 2021; Roberts et al., 2011) advocate for ToR that incorporate the participation of all stakeholders, as funding organizations do (European Commission, 2014; UNDG, 2017). However, upon analysing the ToR of the cases studied in this research, the interviews with the responsible of writing the ToR, the external evaluators and direct beneficiaries of both projects, it becomes clear that direct beneficiaries did not participate in the whole process of the evaluation neither in the drafting of the ToR. Thus, there is a gap between the theory and the practice in both cases of this research.

As demonstrated in the literature, the exclusion of direct beneficiaries has the potential to have a detrimental effect on several aspects of the evaluation process. First, it can compromise the quality of the evaluation itself (Tantalo & Priem, 2016). Second, a sense of detachment among direct beneficiaries can emerge when their needs and expectations are not taken into consideration, resulting in a loss of ownership over the evaluation process (Cousins & Earl, 1995; Roberts et al., 2011). This detachment can lead to less useful results, as the evaluation may not effectively inform subsequent actions (Fitzpatrick et al., 2011). Consequently, Smithers (2011) asserts the importance of meticulous planning in the evaluation process to prevent unfavourable outcomes. The consequence of not considering direct beneficiaries in these specific external evaluations is that some of the direct beneficiaries saw the external evaluations as merely a way of meeting donors' expectations (i.e. that the programme objectives had been achieved and the budget correctly executed).

This finding is interconnected with two findings related to the direct beneficiaries' perceptions of external evaluations. Consequently, the participation of direct beneficiaries is crucial when drafting the ToR, and their absence in these two cases compromises the value and the effectiveness of the final evaluations in these specific instances.

7.2.3.2. The Degree of Prescriptiveness of the ToR Does Not Always Determine the Outcome of the Evaluations.

This finding suggests that evaluations (seen as a mechanism of control of the donor) do not always reflect the donors' interest, as the (agent) implementing unit (as responsible of drafting the ToR) decides the grade of prescriptiveness, and the external evaluator acts as independent party mitigating the agency problems (c.f. 2.2.3). Context-focused evaluations (c.f., p. 43) also recognise that the outcome of an evaluation not only is determined by the prescriptiveness of the ToR but also by contextual factors.

Roberts et al. (2011) assert that “developing an accurate and well-specified ToR is a critical step in managing a high-quality evaluation” (p. 1). Roberts et al. (2011) define “quality” in relation of the ToR to clearly outlines the purpose, scope, methodology, and expectations of the evaluation in a way that ensures credibility, usefulness, and rigor. According to (Silvestrini et al., 2018) there is a direct relationship between the higher overall quality of the ToR and the higher overall quality of the evaluation reports. The ToR is the document that defines and details how an evaluation should be conducted (European Commission, 2014) and guides evaluators through the process: “[H]igh-quality ToRs guide evaluators by facilitating focused evaluations, with more tailored data collection and analysis, which in turn uplifts the quality of evaluation reports” (Väth et al., 2023).

In this research, we found that the outcome and quality of the evaluation reports were very similar, although the overall quality of the ToRs differed when considering the degree of prescriptiveness of the two analysed. Therefore, the work of the external evaluator and their influence throughout the process can be seen as another driver that contributes to the quality of the evaluation outcomes.

This finding is interrelated with the first finding of the analysis of the evaluation reports and the role of the evaluator.

7.2.3.3 *The Key Role of the External Evaluator.*

This finding underscores the importance of the external evaluator and his role as independent party according to the agency theory in the evaluation process applied to ICBHE projects. In this finding, the evaluation capacity building theory could be complementary if I focus on the skills and capabilities that the external evaluator should have.

According to Roberts et al. (2011), many ToRs allow evaluators the flexibility to develop a more detailed methodology that aligns with the specified scope and objectives of an evaluation. Therefore, the 'evaluators' thematic and methodological expertise is anticipated to be a crucial factor" (Väth et al., 2023).

Fitzpatrick et al. (2011) state that evaluation is more relevant and helpful when there is a trusting and positive working relationship between evaluators and all stakeholders involved. In this research, both external evaluators reported having conversations with the beneficiaries to understand their interests and the context of the project. Direct beneficiaries corroborated it. In concrete, the external evaluator of the FORGEC program tried to understand not only the project but also the context of the evaluation, as he/she never had any relation with Cuba and has never been there. This positive and proactive attitude of the external evaluator was a way to acknowledge their own limitations in this evaluation. The role of the external evaluators is to ensure the evaluation is impartial and that the findings and recommendations are reliable and unbiased (Conley-Tyler, 2005; Fitzpatrick et al., 2011). Establishing a trust-based relationship between the external evaluator and the direct beneficiaries is crucial. This helps direct beneficiaries feel valued and heard, resulting in more accurate and thorough evaluations (Buckley et al., 2021). In the IMPALA final evaluation, the external evaluator uses three case studies based on the project itself to illustrate the evaluation. This inclusion was not described in the ToR but the external evaluator thinks about the usefulness of the evaluation in relation to the direct beneficiaries.

According to various authors (Buckley et al., 2021; Fitzpatrick et al., 2011; Perrin, 2019; Roberts et al., 2011) and associations (American Evaluation Association, 1994), external evaluators must conduct themselves ethically to maintain trust and ensure integrity and accountability.

In this instance, it is evident that the evaluator of the IMPALA project, where the ToR evidenced a reduced degree of prescriptiveness, produced evaluation reports that yielded results analogous to those obtained in the FORGEC project.

It can thus be concluded, as indicated by the extant literature, that ToRs are fundamental to project evaluations. However, it is equally important to acknowledge the role of external evaluators, their capacity to apply appropriate methodologies, and their ability to contextualize evaluations and incorporate new information into the reports, even when not required by the ToR. The second finding in relation to the analysis of the evaluation reports (that incorporating new information can enhance the comprehensiveness and detail of the FER reports) can be considered part of this finding, emphasizing the freedom of external evaluators during the evaluation process.

7.2.3.4 External Evaluations Are of Great Importance to Direct Beneficiaries.

This finding highlights that potential information asymmetries could happen between the donors, the implementing unit and the direct beneficiaries. Although for all of them the evaluation is important, their final interests or goals could be different. Stakeholders theory also recognize the value that different stakeholders place on evaluation process and finally the utilization-focused evaluation (c.f., p.42) supports the agency theory in that case as emphasizes the importance of evaluations to all stakeholders.

All the direct beneficiaries interviewed in this research agreed on the importance of external evaluations in general. Some of them also indicated that the results of these evaluations were important because of the information they reflect (the program's objectives,

activities, outputs, and outcomes). However, most participants explicitly stated that the importance of evaluation is not only measured by the outputs or results obtained, but also by the new information it can bring to them, facilitating improvements at all levels. This new information meets their needs and expectations of evaluation, which are not reflected in these concrete external reports. Direct beneficiaries therefore consider these evaluation reports to be informative rather than formative.

According to the literature, the importance of external evaluations is founded on their ability to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of capacity-building projects (Fitzpatrick et al., 2011; OECD, 1991; Vallejo & Wehn, 2016). We need to bear in mind that an evaluation may be effective and efficient, but this does not mean that it has value, especially when the value may be quite different for each of the project's stakeholders.

Moreover, external evaluations are a valuable source of information. These evaluations involve formulating judgments about the impact and progress of programs, thereby facilitating the refinement and enhancement of subsequent initiatives (Fine et al., 2000). Direct beneficiaries supported this idea through their responses, distinguishing between midterm and final evaluations. They considered midterm evaluations as a reference point for making modifications to the implementation of the project to achieve its objectives

The recommendations derived from these evaluations are significant, serving as a guide for improving and refining future actions (Rutnik & Campbell, 2002). Direct beneficiaries stated that the final external evaluation is considered the starting point for new activities but also see them as a way of improvement if the evaluations include new information

This finding is also linked to the impact that evaluations could have on both institutional and individual levels.

7.2.3.5 Consideration of the Needs and Context in the External Evaluation.

This finding suggests, according to the agency theory, how external evaluators (as independent party) can add value to the evaluation, because of their previous experience and knowledge of the context. Thus, there can be an information asymmetry between the donor and the implementing unit and between the implementing unit and the beneficiaries. Context-focused evaluation stresses the importance of considering local context in evaluation processes to be effective.

There is a consensus among the direct beneficiaries in this research that evaluations should consider their needs and contexts from the outset. This idea aligns with the literature and the positions of various organizations.

According to Chouinard (2014), the context of an evaluation is pivotal in determining its outcomes, exerting influence over perspectives, interactions, and interpretations among all relevant stakeholders. Context includes cultural, social, political, and historical elements, which have the capacity to impact the objectives, methodologies, and results of an evaluation. Consequently, it is essential for evaluators to comprehend and adapt to these contextual elements to ensure the accuracy and significance of the findings. In this concrete research I found two external evaluators with different knowledge of the context of the project and of the evaluation. The FORGEC evaluator recognized his/her limitations as he/she had never been before to Cuba. Therefore, he/she was not only unfamiliar with the project but also with the characteristics of the environment in which it was implemented. On the other hand, the evaluator of the IMPALA program was familiar with the environment, having previously experiences in most of the beneficiary countries of the project and spoke Spanish, which facilitated not only his relationship with the direct beneficiaries but also provided a clear understanding of both the project and the evaluation. The external evaluator of the FORGEC project, to mitigate his/her shortcomings, attempted to understand the context before starting

the evaluation by requesting more information from the implementing unit, as well as information on previous projects and various readings to familiarize himself with the context.

Several authors agree that the context in which an evaluation is conducted shapes its effectiveness (Al Hudib & Cousins, 2020, 2022; Edmunds et al., 2018). According to Chouinard & Hopson (2016), despite noteworthy progress in incorporating cultural context into evaluations in North America and Europe, this recognition remains insufficient on a global scale. This idea is fully reflected by some of the participants, who clearly indicate that the same evaluation methodologies should not be used in culturally different contexts. Therefore, they advocate for their participation in the evaluation process from the beginning, in order to suggest criteria that can be better adjusted to their concrete context.

Fitzpatrick et al. (2011) correlate the validity and usefulness of evaluations, considering ethical reasons, with the evaluator's cultural competence in the context where the evaluation will be conducted (p. 241). Marjanovic et al. (2017) state that evaluators "[need] to be familiar with local evaluation contexts, cultures and associated sensitivities, and tailoring tone and discourse accordingly" (p. 94). As mentioned above, the external evaluator of the IMPALA project attempted to understand the context of the evaluation before conducting it, although he/she was surprised by some attitudes linked to Cuban culture, as he/she expressed in the interview.

The different needs of direct beneficiaries must also be taken into consideration. According to Marjanovic et al. (2017), the expectations of all parties should be discussed at the beginning of the evaluation process, and "this includes specifying what is and is not included in the evaluation scope as well as the expectations of all the parties of their participation in the evaluation... It is also essential for partnership and for mitigating the risks of donor-recipient hierarchies" (p. 97). The OECD (2019) defines relevance as one of the DAC criteria: "The extent to which the intervention objectives and design respond to beneficiaries', global,

country, and partner/institution needs, policies, and priorities, and continue to do so if circumstances change” (p. 7), including the world priorities. Therefore, the needs of the beneficiaries should be considered during the evaluation process.

However, this research has revealed that the beneficiaries' needs were not reflected in the evaluation, as they were not considered during the drafting of the ToR. The beneficiaries themselves repeatedly expressed the need to be present and to adapt the methodology to better suit their needs and expectations. This would entail the provision of valuable information to the evaluators in terms of evaluation criteria, as well as the addressing of topics that were not initially planned for the evaluations but were deemed important by the beneficiaries (for example, the application of project results in their institutions).

7.2.3.6 External Evaluations Have a Tangible Impact on Both the Institutional and Individual Levels.

This finding is related to the evaluation capacity building theory, and how evaluations can build or improve capacity at different levels. The finding also demonstrates that agents (implementing units) can create value beyond the donors' objectives.

The extant literature indicates that evaluations serve not only to measure the outcomes of an intervention but also to influence both organizations (in their policies or decisions) and individuals (in terms of personal growth and professional attitudes) (Fitzpatrick et al., 2011; Patton, 1997; Scriven, 1991; C. H. Weiss, 1998). According to Patton (1997), evaluations can be considered successful if their results are useful to the relevant stakeholders of the evaluated intervention. Furthermore, the emphasis on personal growth through evaluations and the capacity for learning through them is underscored by Fitzpatrick et al. (2011). According to the European Commission evaluation handbook (2024), one of the purposes of evaluations is learning, particularly in the context of capacity-building initiatives. This learning is associated with institutional improvement and benefits for employees, including academics and staff.

In this research, according to the responses of direct beneficiaries, opinions vary in both cases studied on whether institutional changes can occur. Some believe in the possibility of change, while others see it as a gradual process or a prompt for internal reflection. At the individual level, some participants feel that external evaluations impact both personal and professional relationships, while others think the impact is limited to professional aspects. However, as reflected by the participants, for evaluations to have an impact at any level, the direct beneficiaries, specifically the individuals involved in the projects, must receive the results. Without these results, it is impossible for a project to have an individual-level impact. Specifically, some participants from both the FORGEC and the IMPALA projects did not receive the evaluation reports.

In this case, the power relations between the implementing unit and the direct beneficiaries must be considered. Some beneficiaries may see the transfer of knowledge from North to South as a way of perpetuating colonialism. Beneficiaries may therefore be reluctant to change. Even more if their context has not been considered by donors or implementing unit.

Therefore, the direct effects on organizations are not as clear as described in the literature review, but the changes they provoke in individuals at a professional level are evident.

7.2.3.7 The Involvement of Direct Beneficiaries in the Design of Evaluations is a Critical Factor in Increasing the Value and Effectiveness of These Evaluations.

This finding suggests that the relationship between principal (donors) and agents (implementing unit) needs to be expanded and include direct beneficiaries to improve the evaluation process and consequently its results. Similarly, participation evaluation theory stresses the idea of the involvement of direct beneficiaries throughout all the evaluation process.

This finding is entirely related to two previously analysed findings: the participation of direct beneficiaries during the drafting of the Terms of Reference (ToR) and the need to consider the needs of the direct beneficiaries and the context in which the evaluation is conducted during its implementation. In this research there is consensus among direct beneficiaries on the importance of their participation in the evaluation design phase to enhance its value and effectiveness. Participants stressed that they are the only ones who really know their needs as well as their context. The absence of direct beneficiaries may be perceived by themselves as a manifestation of superiority on the part of the donors or the implementing unit. Furthermore, it may be perceived as evidence of a North-South power relation.

According to Patton (2018), stakeholder participation in evaluation processes increases their ownership of the evaluation. In this research, the participants never refer to a sense of ownership; on the contrary, they consistently express their disagreement with not being involved in the entire evaluation process. Some authors also link it to the subsequent use of the evaluation results (Cousins et al., 2014). Fitzpatrick et al. (2011) argue that evaluators have an ethical obligation to ensure the inclusion of diverse stakeholder perspectives, prioritize the public good, and employ rigorous, systematic methods with competence because of the direct beneficiaries. Various authors (Patton, 1997; Scriven, 1991; C. H. Weiss, 1998) emphasize that stakeholder participation, especially that of beneficiaries, can enhance the value and utility of the evaluation, as the results are based on the reality, needs, and experiences of the beneficiaries themselves. On the contrary, this idea is reflected in the interviews conducted with the participants. For them, the importance of the evaluation lies in the new insights it can provide.

According to the OECD (2016), “stakeholder participation helps to develop sustainability, evaluation ownership, and mutual accountability” (p. 65). However, the same

report indicates that a small number of agencies corroborate the direct participation of stakeholders in the planning and design phases.

Thus, this finding aligns with the literature review on the subject and opens some topics for more research.

7.2.4 Discussion of Methodology and Limitations

The methodology used for this study was a comparative case study based on two projects funded by the European Commission: the FORGEC project and the IMPALA project. Common documents related to the evaluation in both cases (ToR and mid-term and final evaluation reports) were compared, as well as semi-structured interviews conducted with direct beneficiaries of both projects, those responsible for drafting the ToR, and the external evaluators.

To compare the documents, I used a quantitative approach. To compare the ToR, I created a checklist of 13 questions (Q-Tor). This checklist focused on understanding the degree of prescriptiveness of the ToR in relation to the guidelines provided by the funding entity. Similarly, for the comparison of the reports (both mid-term and final), I conducted a meta-evaluation. To carry this out, I created a questionnaire with 82 questions (EV-Form) to determine whether the reports met the ToR guidelines or included additional information. Creating these questionnaires was essential for adequately and solidly comparing the documents related to both cases.

Subsequently, semi-structured interviews were planned and conducted. Initially, it was not intended to interview those responsible for drafting the ToR; however, it became necessary to understand their opinions, as the ToR play a very important role in this research. Finally, with all the data, I was able to compare both cases and answer my research question.

During the research, limitations arose that I addressed through my research method in order to conduct the study. The main limitations were as follows:

1. The number of cases to compare. This is a threat to the generalizability of my findings. The initial idea was to compare three cases. However, only two were chosen, allowing for a more detailed analysis and comparison between them. Mitigation has been achieved through the rationale behind the case study selection and being clear of the scope (c.f. 3.5).
2. The comparison of two different projects with different context and conditions. This is a threat to the validity of my findings. To mitigate against this threat and to determine which questions were crucial, and which were not in relation to the prescriptiveness of the ToR—and to measure the degree of prescriptiveness using the answers to these questions—I created a checklist of 13 questions (Q-Tor). These questions were based on documents related to the information that should appear in the ToR according to the (European Commission (2004), and significant questions for the research were added.
3. The comparison of the evaluation reports of two different projects with the same criteria and method. This is a threat to the validity of my findings. What questions should be asked to compare evaluation reports? Should we rely solely on the ToR guidelines? However, since the ToR differed, corresponding to different projects and different DGs within the European Commission. To mitigate against this threat and to determine which questions were crucial, I created a questionnaire of 82 questions (EV-Form) based on the criteria of the Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Spain.
4. The number of direct beneficiaries (universities) to include in the study. This is a threat to the reliability of my findings as I employed a strategic sample approach. Both IMPALA and FORGEC had a different and considerable

number of direct beneficiaries (8 and 13 HEIs, respectively). The original idea was to include all universities or HEIs in the research; however, time constraints and the difficulty of contacting representatives from all of them made this unfeasible. Therefore, I chose only four universities, two from each project, representing the diversity of universities. Selecting diverse universities facilitated determining whether the responses obtained in the semi-structured interviews were context-specific or not, bearing in mind that three universities were from the same country. This approach, while not exhaustive, provided a balanced view that enhanced the reliability of the findings.

5. The prior knowledge that all interviewees had of me. This is a threat to the reliability of my findings, and I implemented different measures to mitigate bias and ensure the integrity of the data collection. Clear role: from the beginning of this research, I was aware of my position in this study and how it could influence the responses of some interviewees due to my relationship with both projects. For this reason, I adopted a pragmatic approach that allowed me to connect to the beneficiaries and create the trust needed to get in-depth reliable information (despite my insider role). I explained my role to all interviewees, indicating that they should view me as a researcher, not as a colleague. A clear separation between the researcher role and my previous professional relationship. Confidentiality assurance: I stressed the confidentiality of the interviews and coding process, which encourage interviewees to speak freely, without perceiving me as a colleague or a representative of a European institution or Spanish university. Reflexivity: I maintained during all the process a reflexive approach, constantly examining my own potential biases,

and their impact in this research. The combination of these strategies strengthened the reliability of the findings.

6. The way of conducting the interviews. The interviews were initially conceived to be conducted in person. Planned trips to Cuba were used to conduct a significant portion of them. However, the high cost of travel meant that the last interviews had to be conducted online, accounting for technological inconveniences and the different time zones of the interviewees. In both cases I used the same standardize interview protocols. In both cases interviews were conducted in an appropriate atmosphere without interruptions or time pressure. In the case of the direct beneficiaries' interviews all of them were conducted in their mother tongue (Spanish) to feel them more comfortable. In the online interviews the camera always had to be plugged in to have visual contact with the participants all the time. In all cases the interviews were recorded.
7. Getting in contact with the direct beneficiaries for interviews. Some of the direct beneficiaries were no longer working at the institutions involved in the research or had relocated. In the specific case of one of the universities in the IMPALA project, it was impossible to contact an individual, which resulted in a lower number of interviews for this case. To enhance the reliability in that case I used multiple contact methods, social media and employed the snowball sampling to reach uncontactable participants.

The limited academic literature written by the direct beneficiaries themselves regarding the external evaluation process in ICHBE, not their results or the results of the projects (c.f., p. 10).

To address limitations and enhance reliability, this research employed purposeful case selection, choosing diverse CBHE projects that reflect common characteristics in the field.

This approach strengthens the generalizability of findings to similar initiatives. The methodology design incorporated multiple data collection methods, and I operationalised my research questions to ensure reliability and validity of my findings. By systematically analysing beneficiaries' perspectives across various contexts and project types, the study offers robust insights into evaluation effectiveness by direct beneficiaries.

7.2.5 Summary

In this chapter, the main findings of the research have been presented. All operational questions, as well as the three sub-questions of the research, have been answered. A new underpinning topic arises: the lingering colonial attitudes in ICBHE projects evaluation. The power imbalance between direct beneficiaries and North donors and evaluators, with their own methodologies and without considering local needs and perspectives, can undermine the effectiveness and sustainability of CBHE projects. These answers will guide us to the response to our research question and the possible recommendations for future research and for the stakeholders involved in capacity-building evaluation processes in higher education, which we will address in the next chapter.

Chapter 8: Conclusion

8.1 Introduction

The aim of this final chapter is to provide an answer to our research question through the answers to the sub-questions and findings presented in the previous chapter. We will reflect on the future, implications, and limitations through recommendations for future research and for the stakeholders involved in the external evaluations of ICBHE projects.

8.2 Response to the Research Question

In order to adequately answer my research question, *How effective is the external evaluation process of international capacity building in higher education projects in meeting the needs of the direct beneficiaries, as perceived by these beneficiaries?* I have analysed the factors thought to influence the external evaluation process, as well as the opinions of not only the direct beneficiaries of these projects but also those who, through the Terms of Reference (ToR), determine how the external evaluations should be conducted and the external evaluators who conducted the evaluations.

Based on the answers to our operational research questions (c.f. 7.2.1) and sub-questions (c.f. 7.2.2), I can state that there is a gap between the theory and the practice in the evaluation process. The donors want to know if the goals of the project has been achieved and the accountability of the project but also consider the needs of the beneficiaries. But in practice, the needs of the beneficiaries are not considered in the evaluation. The gap direct relationship between the process of external evaluations and consequently the outcomes of these evaluations (evaluation reports) and the direct beneficiaries' perceptions of the effectiveness of these reports.

This research shows that direct beneficiaries attach in general great value to these reports for all the information they contain (c.f. 7.2.1.4). This information can help them to

improve the project (if it is a mid-term report), or to take decisions in the future or to serve as a model for new initiatives. In these concrete evaluations, direct beneficiaries only find the donor's needs, in relation to the achievement of the objectives of the project and the accountability of the projects. Their needs or expectations are not reflected in the evaluation reports because they have not been considered in the moment of writing the ToR. Therefore, the effectiveness of the evaluations is limited because the evaluation reports are informative, but they do not add much value to them.

Agency theory suggest that the effectiveness and value of external evaluations, as perceived by direct beneficiaries, depends on how the well the evaluation process aligns with the interest of all the stakeholders (donors, implementing unit and direct beneficiaries).

If an asymmetry problem between the donors and the implementing unit arise (the implementing unit take actions that do not fully align with the donors requirements (in this case of the evaluation process only follows the ToR but not considered the recommendation of the EC in relation to consider the needs of the beneficiaries) the effectiveness of the evaluation for direct beneficiaries will be less effectiveness and less valuable, as the implementing unit is only prioritizing the ToR's requirements over the beneficiaries' needs.

In relation to my findings,

The beneficiaries perceived the evaluation as ineffective or without value is because 2 different problems of asymmetry agency have appeared:

- 1 Between the donor and the implementing unit: not consider the beneficiaries' needs (only prioritize ToR of the donors)
- 2 Between the implementing unit and the donor: not consider enough the context of the project and the evaluation.

But these problems can be solved by the external evaluator (as independent party), as the external evaluator has sufficient independence to conduct the evaluation, he/she not only

follows the ToR but also add more information in relation to the needs of the beneficiaries (after having talked to them). So, the external evaluator can adjust his/her evaluation methodology to better serve direct beneficiaries.

The problem could arise when the external evaluation does not make any effort to understand direct beneficiaries' needs (no communication between them) and have not knowledge in relation to the context of the project and the evaluation. In that case, the external evaluator must recognise his /her limitation and spend more time and effort to understand it.

Conversely, if the implementing unit considers the needs of the direct beneficiaries when drafting the ToR (stakeholder theory), the external evaluator has knowledge about the context (context-focused evaluation) and verifies the needs of the direct beneficiaries (utilization-focused evaluation), and a participatory evaluation takes place, then the result of the external evaluation is valuable for both donors and recipients, enhancing direct beneficiaries' ownership and sustainability of the project. This approach could also reduce the persistence of colonialism.

Therefore, I can say that there is a direct link between the drafting of the evaluation through the ToR and the perception of the results of the external evaluations by the direct beneficiaries. However, this relationship can be completely altered by the intervention of the external evaluators at the time of the evaluation reports if the external evaluator is aware of this discrepancy.

8.3 Implications and Recommendations to Policy and Practice

This section reflects the implications and recommendations for the key stakeholders of ICBHE (funding institutions, implementing units and direct beneficiaries) and for external evaluators of ICBHE projects.

8.3.1. For funding institutions and implementing units

Considering the research findings (c.f. 6.5) and the literature review (c.f. 2.1.4.4), it is evident that the ToR have a significant influence on the evaluation process as a whole, and consequently on its outcome and the direct beneficiaries' perceptions. Consequently, it is essential that the needs of the direct beneficiaries of the interventions are considered when drafting these terms. The literature suggest that most financial institutions already include this consideration in their manuals; however, when the implementing unit drafts the ToR, these needs are not always considered. It could be due to a lack of resources (time and budget) or to avoid potential bias in the results in the case of participatory evaluations.

Nevertheless, the exclusion of the needs of the direct beneficiaries ultimately affects how the evaluation is perceived. The investment of resources in an ICBHE project is substantial; however, these projects may not achieve the desired long-term impact, not only due to the feasibility of the actions but also because the evaluations are not regarded effective by the direct beneficiaries. This diminution of effectiveness of the evaluations can also affect potential new actions or institutional decision-making. Some concrete actions can be done by the donors to solve this problem:

- **Include Agreement in Quality Assurance Plan:** Ensure that the Terms of Reference (ToR) are agreed upon by both the implementing unit and the direct beneficiaries before being published. This will guarantee that the needs and expectations of the direct beneficiaries are reflected in the ToR.
- **Involve Beneficiaries in ToR Development:** Include representatives of the direct beneficiaries in the ToR development team. This will ensure that the ToR are written correctly and encompass the needs of all stakeholders.
- **Promote Participatory Evaluation:** Advocate for the use of participatory evaluation in the ToR. If a fully participatory evaluation is not feasible, at least involve the

direct beneficiaries in drafting the ToR and inform them about how the external evaluation will be conducted.

- **Require Local Expertise:** Mandate that the evaluation team includes a local expert who understands the cultural context and can act as a counterpart to the direct beneficiaries. This will help external evaluators mitigate potential misunderstandings related to the context.
- **Use of Local Language:** Encourage the use of the local language when engaging with direct beneficiaries during the evaluation process.

Applying most of these actions, the involvement of direct beneficiaries is guaranteed.

This involvement would serve to enhance the sense of ownership among the direct beneficiaries regarding both the project itself and the evaluation process. This, in turn, could potentially result in the evaluation being perceived as more effective and could ultimately lead to projects achieving a greater impact and being more sustainable over time.

For this reason, it is crucial that the implementing units involve the direct beneficiaries in the drafting of the ToR, with a view to understanding their needs and expectations regarding the external evaluations and the way these will be conducted.

A salient issue pertaining to external evaluations concerns the temporal management of their execution. It is imperative that final evaluations are conducted in a time-efficient manner, with the understanding that the ideal timeframe for this process is prior to the project's completion. However, this may not always be feasible, as certain activities may not have been completed at that point. Therefore, the external evaluators may not have access to all the relevant and accurate data necessary to conduct the evaluation. One potential solution to this issue could be to conduct the evaluations once the project has concluded, within a maximum execution period and with the budget closed within the project itself. This approach would

ensure that evaluators have all the elements necessary to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the project.

8.3.2 For direct beneficiaries

The fundamental role of direct beneficiaries in external evaluations is:

- **Active Participation in the Evaluation Process:** As direct beneficiaries of the projects, their involvement in the evaluation process is essential.
- **Engagement in Data Collection:** Their participation in data collection activities, such as answering questionnaires, participating in interviews, and focus groups, is crucial. Without their active involvement, evaluations hold value only for donors and lack comprehensive insights.
- **Validation of Findings:** Direct beneficiaries should validate the findings to ensure that the results of an external evaluation are not biased due to the external evaluator's lack of information at the time of conducting the evaluation.
- **Fostering Mutual Respect and Equitable Partnership:** It is important to foster a relationship characterized by mutual respect and equitable partnership between the direct beneficiaries and the external evaluators. This ensures that any barriers to communication or collaboration are eliminated. This is particularly relevant in the context of ICBHE projects, many of which are initiated from a North-South perspective, where direct beneficiaries may be more susceptible to the lingering influences of colonialism or post-colonialism. Direct beneficiaries are uniquely positioned to inform the evaluator about the reality and context of the project and the evaluation.

8.3.3 *For External Evaluators*

It has been observed that the role of external evaluators is essential in ensuring the effectiveness and value of external evaluations from the perception of direct beneficiaries. In this instance, it falls upon the external evaluator:

- **Recognition of Limitations:** Evaluators may have extensive experience; however, they might be unfamiliar with the context of the project and the evaluation. This lack of knowledge must be recognised by them to address it.
- **Consideration of Beneficiary Needs:** Ensure that the needs of the direct beneficiaries are duly considered and incorporated into the ToR to avoid conducting an evaluation that only informs some stakeholders but not all.
- **Preliminary Discussions:** Have preliminary discussions with direct beneficiaries prior to formulating the methodology. This will facilitate the external evaluators' understanding of the needs and expectations of the direct beneficiaries concerning the evaluations.
- **Developing Empathy:** Develop strong empathy with direct beneficiaries to effectively interact with them and acquire first-hand knowledge of the context of the evaluation. This process would help break down any barriers of trust and communication between the direct beneficiaries and the external evaluators.
- **Contextual Adaptation:** Adapt the evaluation methodology to the specific context, as the context can influence project execution and the behaviour of the direct beneficiaries.
- **Validation of Findings:** Validate findings with direct beneficiaries before finalizing reports to ensure that beneficiaries' perspectives are accurately represented.

By following these recommendations, external evaluators can achieve more accurate and effective evaluation results.

8.4 Recommendations for Future Research

Considering the limitations encountered while conducting this research, and in consideration of the implications and recommendations for ICBHE stakeholders and external evaluators, future actions and research endeavours can contribute to ensuring that external evaluations of ICBHE projects are significant in their own right and for all stakeholders involved, not just for the external evaluation results obtained and has discovered many interesting areas of study.

Research is recommended on the creation of a common methodology among different funding institutions to systematically compare evaluations (both processes and reports, but not outcomes). This would enable funding entities and implementing units to compare evaluations across projects and identify potential solutions to common challenges they might face.

Further research is needed in other regions and contexts, including countries with different levels of development, political regimes and educational systems. This will enable a more comprehensive and globally understanding of the direct beneficiaries' perceptions of external evaluations. This can be achieved by facilitating the comparison of results.

Future research on how external evaluations can influence direct beneficiaries in the long term and their relationship with the sustainability and success of ICBHE projects is needed.

Further research is also required to determine the optimal timing for conducting the final external evaluation, aiming to measure whether there are differences in quality and accuracy depending on whether the evaluation is conducted before or after the project's completion.

Another critical area of research concerns how North-South power dynamics, colonialism, or post-colonialism may influence the relationships between implementing units and/or external evaluators and direct beneficiaries and their consequences.

Regarding the absence of literature written by direct beneficiaries on this topic, it is essential to facilitate the production of academic literature (research, case studies, publications) by direct beneficiaries about their experiences and perceptions to expand and enrich the existing literature on the subject.

8.5 Concluding remarks

This study explores the perceptions of direct beneficiaries regarding the effectiveness and value of external evaluations in ICBHE projects. Through two case studies based on the FORGEC and IMPALA projects, and by analysing both documents and interviews with the main stakeholders of both cases, I have observed that direct beneficiaries place great value on external evaluations. However, their effectiveness is compromised when beneficiaries are only included in the active part of the evaluation and not in all the process of the evaluation, including the moment of drafting the ToR of the evaluation. Agency theory can explain why direct beneficiaries have not been considered in the process of evaluation and its consequences. Stakeholders theory and participatory evaluations have shown that their inclusion can improve the outcomes concerning the effectiveness and value of external evaluations; however, participatory evaluations are not very common in this type of project. This research not only demonstrates the importance of beneficiaries' involvement but also the crucial role of the external evaluator throughout the process.

A final consideration relates to the amount of literature written by the direct beneficiaries themselves about the external evaluation process of ICBHE, which is quite scarce. Why is this? Is it due to the project model itself? Or due to the North-South power dynamics in relation to the publication of academic works?

Empower beneficiaries, enhance evaluations.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Q-Tor Check List

1. Have the Terms of Reference been formulated in a clear and understandable manner?
2. Do the Terms of Reference contain the objective and scope of the programme?
3. Do the Terms of Reference contextualize the programme?
4. Do the Terms of Reference outline the activities and the work plan of the programmes?
5. Do the Terms of Reference outline the expected results of the programme?
6. Do the Terms of Reference indicate the stakeholders of the programme?
7. Do the Terms of Reference indicate the beneficiaries of the programme?
8. Do the Terms of Reference indicate a specific methodology to be used to conduct the programme evaluation?
9. Do the Terms of Reference identify the resources (personal) and timing for the evaluation to be carried out?
10. Have the Terms of Reference specified the deliverables to be produced after the evaluation?
11. Do the Terms of Reference contain the budget allocated to the evaluation, and is it in accordance with the evaluation?
12. Has the interest of the direct beneficiaries (no other stakeholders) of the programme been taken into account in the Terms of Reference?
13. To what extent do the Terms or Reference focus on the assessment of (unintended) outcomes and impacts?
<i>Questions in blue: The five key issues identified by the European Commission (2004) as essential for inclusion in the ToR</i>
<i>Questions in black: New questions</i>

Source: Authors' creation

Appendix 2: EV-Form

QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE EVALUATION REPORTS OF THE CASES
A. Impartiality Criteria (type of evaluation carried out)
A.1. Is the evaluation external or internal? (Members of the evaluation team work in the evaluated institutions)?
B. Equity Criteria (the way in which the evaluation has been inclusive (stakeholders, context) and its accessibility).
B.1. Apart from the funding institution, was any stakeholder of the project involved in the planning and implementation of the evaluation process?
B.2. Were the evaluation questions clearly formulated and adapted to the context of the project?
B.3. Is the evaluation report accessible to the stakeholders?
C. Quality Criteria (1) (verifies the established processing guidelines)
C.1. Compliance with requirements. (This criterion assesses whether the requirements that appear in the ToR are adequately addressed).
C.1.1. Does the evaluation adequately address questions according to the questions asked in the ToR?
C.1.2. Is the evaluation carried out within the stipulated timeframe?
C.2. Context analysis (This criterion assesses whether the report addresses the program in its temporal, geographic and regulatory dimensions and analyses its context).
C.2.1. Does the evaluation reflect its temporal, geographic and regulatory dimension?
C.2.2. Are the ultimate objectives of the intervention, its achievements, outcomes and impacts studied in their totality, including its interactions with other policies and unintended consequences?
C.3. Design and method. (This criterion assesses the evaluation tools and methodology used, as well as the design of the evaluation).
C.3.1. Evaluation Design: The evaluation design includes the following elements:
C.3.1.1. Context of the evaluation
C.3.1.2. Objective and scope of the evaluation
C.3.1.3. Evaluation criteria
C.3.1.4. Methodology - approach to data collection and analysis and stakeholder participation
C.3.1.5. Duration of the evaluation
C.3.1.6. Organizational chart
C.3.1.7. Budget of the project
C.3.1.8. Outputs and reports
C.3.1.9. Conclusions, recommendations, lessons learned
C.3.2 The cover and title page of the report should provide key basic information such as:
C.3.2.1. Project name
C.3.2.2. Evaluation date
C.3.2.3 Funding Institution
C.3.2.4. Name of Evaluators
C.3.2.5. Index of the evaluation
C.3.3. Annexes or information that should be included
C.3.3.1. Evaluation questions
C.3.3.2. DAC sheet
C.3.3.3. Evaluation Matrix
C.3.3.4. Data collection instruments (surveys, checklists, etc.)

C.3.3.5. Groups of people interviewed, or actors involved in the process
C.3.3.6. Timeline of the evaluation
C.3.3.7. Documentation of guides for focus groups, guided interviews, and surveys (if needed)
C.3.3.8. List of literature and documentation used
C.3.4. Composition of the evaluation team
C.3.4.1. Does the name of the people forming the evaluation team appear?
C.3.4.2. Does the evaluation present a brief presentation of the evaluation team?
C.3.5. Planning (coherence)
C.3.5.1. Does the evaluation submit a work plan?
C.3.6. Relevant stakeholder involvement
C.3.6.1. Does the evaluation explain if the evaluation was designed as a participatory process?
C.3.6.2. Does the evaluation present a concrete list of stakeholders that have participated in the assessment?
C.3.6.3. Does the evaluation define the different stakeholders of the project?
C.3.7. Application of evaluation DAC criteria and others
C.3.7.1. Does the evaluation adequately assess the relevance of the project?
C.3.7.2. Does the evaluation adequately assess the effectiveness of the project?
C.3.7.3. Does the evaluation adequately assess the efficiency of the project?
C.3.7.4. Does the evaluation adequately assess the outcomes/impacts of the project?
C.3.7.5. Does the evaluation adequately assess the sustainability of the project?
C.3.7.6. Does the evaluation adequately assess the coherence of the project?
C.3.7.7. Does the evaluation base findings on evidence?
C.3.8. Approach and methodology. It must distinguish between different levels of results, intervention logic containing a hierarchy between objectives and means, indicating inputs, outputs, outcome and impact.
C.3.8.1. Are the general objectives of the project (not of the evaluation) included in the evaluation report?
C.3.8.2. Are the specific project objectives included in the evaluation report?
C.3.8.3. Are the project results included in the evaluation report?
C.3.8.4. Are the project activities (timeline) included in the evaluation report?
C.3.8.5. Are the inputs (budget) of the project in question in the evaluation report?
C.3.9 Description of methodology
C.3.9.1. Are the available sources of information indicated?
C.3.9.2. Are different data collection methods applied covering quantitative and qualitative aspects?
C.3.9.3. Does the evaluation describe the rationality for selecting a concrete method of analysis?
C.3.9.4. Does the evaluation include the level of precision required for quantitative methods?
C.3.9.5. Does the evaluation include the coding used for qualitative analysis?
C.3.9.6. Are indicators described, where relevant (previous indicators, national statistics, etc.)?
C.3.9.7. Are any the log frames, result chains or other theory of change frame (including indicators) used as a reference document for the assessment ?
C.3.10 Justification of the methodology used.
C.3.10.1. Does the evaluator present a critique of his/her method and methodological choices?
C.3.10.2. Does the evaluator indicate the risks that would have been run if other methodological choices had been made?
C.3.10.3. Does the evaluator clearly specify the limits inherent to the evaluation method?

C.3.10.4. Does the evaluator explain in a clear manner the evaluation method used?
C.3.10.5. Is the methodological choice use by the evaluator appropriate in order to meet the ToR requirements?
C.4. Reliability of the data (how the data have been obtained and used during the evaluation process)
C.4.1. Does the evaluation describe the data sources of the analysed documents?
C.4.2. Does the evaluation describe the rationale for their selection and their limitations?
C.4.3. Does the evaluation include a discussion on how the mix of data sources was used to obtain a diversity of perspectives, ensure data accuracy, and overcome data limits?
C.4.4. Does the evaluation describe the sampling for the evaluation process?
C.4.5. Does the evaluation explain if the evaluation has avoided duplications in data collection by relying as far as possible on existing data?
C.5. Data solidity (logical sequence between evidence and assessment)
C.5.1. Are the results of the evaluation justified by the data analysis?
C.6. Credibility of findings (analysed data must be reliable and balanced)
C.6.1. Do the evaluation results reflect in an acceptable way the reality described by the data and evidence recorded?
C.6.2. Do the evaluation results reflect in an acceptable way the reality of the intervention as perceived by the actors and beneficiaries?
C.7. Conclusions (Derived from the analysis, supported by facts and identifiable in the report)
C.7.1. Do the conclusions present reasonable judgements based on findings and substantiated by evidence?
C.7.2. Do the conclusions provide insights pertinent to the purpose of the evaluation?
C.7.3. Do the conclusions arise from the analysis supported by facts and analysis that are readily identifiable in the rest of the report and avoid bias or personal considerations?
C.8. Recommendations (they should be clear, concise, derived from the conclusions and based on the analysis and free of bias)
C.8.1. Does the evaluation provide quality recommendations?
C.8.2. Are the recommendations relevant, specific to the addressees, and concrete?
C.8.3. Do recommendations result from the conclusions and are they based on the analysis performed?
C.8.4. Are the recommendations fair and unbiased?
C.8.5. Are the recommendations detailed enough to be concretely applicable?
C.9. Clarity of the evaluation (easy to read and logically structured report including an executive summary)
C.9.1. Is the evaluation easy to read and logically structured with clarity and coherence (e.g. background and objectives - findings - conclusions and recommendations)?
D.9.2 The evaluation report states conclusively and comprehensibly whether and to what extent the project/program:
C.9.2.1. Is the evaluation report relevant/relevant to the country, region?
C.9.2.2. Does the evaluation report achieve the defined goals in ToR?
C.9.2.3. Is the evaluation report efficient?
C.9.2.4. Does the evaluation report cause desired and undesired impacts (outcome and impact)?
C.9.2.5. Does the evaluation report include a summary or executive summary reflecting the evaluation?

Appendix 3: Protocol of interviews with stakeholders

The questionnaires have been different to all the different groups but there were some common questions to all of them. The type of questions was open.

I have distinguished 4 different groups of people to be interviewed:

- a) professors, trainers and local actors
- b) senior leaders, middle managers (including project managers)
- c) external evaluators of FORGEC and IMPALA projects
- d) person responsible for writing the ToR of the external evaluation of the

FORGEC and IMPALA projects.

Protocol 1 - Direct Beneficiaries

The interviews were divided into 3 different parts:

- *Contextualization of the project and the person interviewed in relation to the project.*
- *The ideas that the interviewed person has of an evaluation before his/her participation in the evaluation of that concrete project.*
- *The ideas that the interviewed person has after his/her participation in that concrete evaluation project.*

Q1 – Direct Beneficiaries: Professors and trainers in HEI and local actors in charge of the economic and social development (training):

The type of questions was related to:

- Knowledge of the project in general and explain some ideas of the project in a few words.
- Aims of the project (their knowledge in general)
- Aims they hope the project will achieve.
- Type of activity they participate in
- Their knowledge of in relation to the various evaluation practices
- Their perceptions of the effectiveness of the evaluations.
- Knowledge of the realization of an evaluation (internal or external) and expectations
- If they have participated or not in the evaluation.

- Participants in the evaluation: Their opinion related to the methodology used and changes (if needed)
 - No Participants: Why they don't participate
- Results of the evaluations: if they have been informed or not
 - The importance and value of the project
 - Motivation to participate in this type of initiatives and why.
 - The value of the evaluation of the project
 - Possible changes in their work, possible changes in their role inside the institution.
 - Relationship between project evaluation and changes in their work (job, type of work, way to work) and in the institution and also in their personal life.
 - Opinion about their participation in the project and (if it's the case) in the evaluation project.

Q2 – Direct Beneficiaries: University senior leaders, middle managers)

The type of questions were related to:

- Knowledge of the project in general and explain some ideas of the project in a few words.
- Aims of the project (their knowledge in general)
- Aims they hope the project will achieve.
- Type of activity they participate in
- Their knowledge of in relation to the various evaluation practices
- Their perceptions of the effectiveness of the evaluations.
- The importance of the project for the institution
- The importance of conducting a project evaluation (internal and external)
- Factors that are important to ensure the evaluation is effective and of good quality
- Definition of effectiveness of the results of the evaluation.
- Relationship between project evaluation and changes in their institution and also in their personal work and life.
- Results of the evaluation: if they have been informed or not, and if they have also informed of the results to other people of their own institution
- Expectations of the evaluation: accomplish or not
- Visibility of the project

Protocol 2 – Evaluators And Person Responsible of Writing the ToR

Q3 – Evaluators and persons responsible for writing the ToR

- Previous knowledge of the project and of the institutions involved in the project.
- General opinion in relation to project evaluations. Importance. Useful and why
- Effectiveness and quality: factors to ensure both concepts.

- Terms of reference of evaluation: opinion about them, idea of “key document” to prepare the evaluation, sufficiently clear and explicit in the form and methodology to evaluate the project.
- To what extent were the terms of reference of that evaluation
- Information to be included in the terms of reference of an evaluation to make a quality and valid evaluation
- Methodology indicated in the Terms of Reference in order to assess this project. In the case that there was not detailed, methodology used to evaluate the project and why.
- Information related to the stakeholders’ evaluation expectations before doing the evaluation. Consideration or not of the stakeholder’s evaluation expectations before to elaborate the evaluation.
- Results of the evaluation: how and to whom should be presented the evaluation results (funding institutions / all stakeholders?). Example of this concrete case.
- Feedback received after submitting the evaluation results. Any? From whom?

Appendix 4: Codebook

THEME	CODE	DEFINITION	EXAMPLE
<p>Personal Context The knowledge and relationship of the participants with the programme is important to be aware of the extent to which they were part of it</p>	Knowledge	Refers to participants' knowledge of the program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>"From the very beginning, we were called in by the directorate of the project, and it was explained to us" (IM1)</i> - <i>"I don't have any previous knowledge" (IM7)</i>
	Involvement	Refers to participants' participation in the program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>"Well, I was involved from its conception in writing the project and then as a manager' (FG4).</i> - <i>"I think the project was already 30-40% complete" (IM8)</i>
<p>Evaluation and Measurement Evaluation and measurement are linked through participants' understanding of evaluation, its role in assessing project objectives, and their attitudes towards external evaluations. Participants' opinions were also relevant regarding the evaluators' understanding of the local context, the methodology used, and the evaluation's role in fostering improvement and effective planning.</p>	Knowledge	Refers to participants' knowledge of evaluation in general and their definition of evaluation in their own words	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>"If the project was really well conceived and designed or if, apart from being well conceived and designed, there were distortions of some other kind." (FG8)</i> - <i>"...it seems to me that there are several things that need to come out. One is precisely what the expected results are. Another is whether those results are achieved. Second, the impact, because the result is one thing, and the impact is another. ... Another is how it has been carried out, whether the means and methods available for this have been used appropriately, if the methods, forms, all those issues, the requirements, sorry, the resources, both material and human, as well as financial, have been counted on to achieve those results. All of this should</i>

			<i>come out in an external evaluation of the project” (FG1).</i>
Importance	Refers to the importance of external evaluation for participants to check whether the project objectives have been achieved		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“Evaluation, yes: a fundamental moment in any type of process, but in the context of a project, it is evidently essential.” (FG7)</i> - <i>“An evaluation of a project, the importance that it should have above all is to see what things have not gone well, or what things are still insufficient in what the project has been able to achieve, in order to continue generating projects on that basis that allow the level of quality to be raised’ (FG3).</i>
Attitude	Refers to the attitude of participants towards external evaluation conducted by people outside the project		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“We really liked the fact that the evaluators relied more on exchange than on reviewing documents. It was more about looking, observing, dialogue, conversation”. (FG1)</i>
Participation	Refers to the interest shown in participating in the external evaluation by being interviewed		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>‘When you work as a part, you are even more motivated to participate in an interview or in a survey of this kind because it allows you to express both, I would not say the motivations and the result achieved, but also to evaluate yourself.’. (FG4)</i> - <i>“I would have like to participate in the evaluation” (IM8)</i>
Methodology	Refers to the type of methodology used by the external evaluators. Specifically, whether or not the external evaluators come with a defined methodology		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“The external evaluators already come with an initial idea” (FG1).</i> - <i>“It’s very much an outsider’s view”. (IM9)</i>
Improvement	Refers to the improvements that can be made to a project as a result of external evaluations		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>“Allows us to make a reorganisation and improvement for the completion of the project” (FG4).</i>

	Planning	Refers to the process of planning the external evaluation and the time and resources spent on it	- <i>“We had very little time to prepare because we had to receive these people, we also had to organise all the meetings, interviews, review documents, go to certain entities”.</i> (FG2)
	Contextualisation	Refers to the participants’ opinion of the external evaluators’ knowledge of where the programme took place and, therefore, where the external evaluation takes place. In this case: Cuba, Panamá, and Colombia	- <i>“Sometimes they do not know the places where the project has been carried out. The context. And that is important.”</i> (FG4) - <i>“...this perspective of reality from regions like ours must also be clearly understood. You are in Europe and have a certain way of living and all that, but here, compliance and everything else does not apply in the same way. Here, things are very different.”</i> (IM8)
Development and improvement External evaluation results provide critical insights to guide development and improvement, identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement, not only for individuals but also for institutions.	Communication	Points out the importance of receiving the results of the external evaluation of the projects in which the participants participated	- <i>“If they give you the results of the evaluation, you can see where you were or were not wrong.”</i> (IM7) - <i>“I don't remember ever getting feedback on the results”</i> (FG9)
	Positive changes	Change is seen as positive (at any level)	- <i>“I believe that yes, it has value, that the value is positive, that it is valued by the managers in the institutions, in the universities, it is valued as positive”</i> (FG9).
	Growth	Refers to personal changes experienced by participants after taking part in an external evaluation	- <i>“My way of thinking and acting and leading changes a lot.”</i> (IM4)
	Decision-making	Refers to a concrete type of professional change experienced by participants after participating in an external evaluation	- <i>“... that it can be very useful for day-to-day decision making, in any sense, be it, let's say, some decisions more strategic, others more methodological...”.</i> (IM4)
	Job change	Refers to participants who have changed their position since the end of	- <i>“There were many professors and researchers who upgraded their</i>

		the project. Note that we are talking about the project and not the external evaluation	<i>teaching status or even took on responsibilities or improved the quality of their academic publications". (FG7)</i>
	Reflexion	Refers to the process of reflection within institutions based on the results of an external evaluation	- <i>"The evaluation it makes from my point of view: it creates an internal debate." (IM6).</i>
Collaboration and interaction In external evaluation, collaboration and interaction between external evaluators and direct beneficiaries fosters a meaningful exchange of insights and empower direct beneficiaries to participate in an active way in the process, which increases their engagement and contributes to constant improvement, leading to greater impact	Exchange	Refers to the idea, at the moment of designing the external evaluation, of sharing knowledge between participants and external evaluators	- <i>"Therefore, sometimes it is necessary to hold sessions to share objectives, otherwise they get lost. Some are talking about one thing, others are preparing for another." FG2</i>
	Empowerment	Refers to participants' feelings about the external evaluation process and how these feelings can be improved	- <i>"If the beneficiaries participate in the design, I think the design is richer, more precise, more attractive, there is more commitment."(FG3).</i>
	Involvement	Refers to the role that direct beneficiaries play in the conception and design of the external evaluation	- <i>"Perhaps we would have incorporated some other elements that were not incorporated because they were not conceived in the methodology." (FG1)</i>
	Improvement	Refers to how external evaluations can be improved, specifically their design	- <i>"... methodology could have been, we say, with this word, which perhaps responds to everything a little more transversal, a little more interdisciplinary, than being seen by a single person regardless of that person's profile."(IM6)</i>
	Impact	Refers to incorporating impact assessment of actions into external evaluation	- <i>'In this particular case, the evaluation will determine whether the project has achieved the results initially planned, and then the impact it has had' (IM7)</i>
Perception and valuation Direct beneficiaries' expectations of the evaluation's value and effectiveness are linked to how well it captures meaningful insights and addresses relevant issues.	Value	The value or relevance of the evaluation of a project to the direct beneficiaries. In this case, what makes the external evaluation valuable	<i>"That it really reflects, that it reflects as faithfully as possible the results and the growth of what is being evaluated. The growth, the improvement, the progress, if any". (FG8)</i> <i>"For it to be useful, well, you have to first ask the beneficiaries, the actors, the people who received the service.</i>

			<i>Secondly, you also have to ask those who participated, how was the experience". (FG3)</i>
	Effectiveness	Evaluation effectiveness from the point of view of direct beneficiaries	<i>"Always the evaluation of the project goes towards the fulfilment of the objective, towards the activity and economic control of the project and perhaps to some extent the satisfaction of the actors or beneficiaries of the project. But I think it is necessary to think a bit further. We must think about the impact and the final result expressed in those who receive the final benefit of each and every project" (IM1)</i>

Appendix 5: Approval from the Ethics Committee of Università Cattolica del Sacro

Cuore

Gemelli

Comitato Etico

Gent.ma Prof.ssa Amanda Murphy
Associate Coordinator, responsible for the Higher Education Internationalization area

Gent.ma Dott.ssa Marta Busquets Calopa
PhD School Scienze Linguistiche e Letterarie
Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation

UCSC Milano

Oggetto: Progetto di ricerca "Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and Effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders"

Gentilissime,

Si comunica che Il Comitato Etico, nella seduta dello 06/10/2022, ha valutato la documentazione pervenuta con email del 15 agosto 2022, relativamente al progetto in oggetto. In particolare, è stata valutata la seguente documentazione:

- Descrizione del Progetto di ricerca (in Italiano, inglese e spagnolo);
- Human Research Ethics Application Form;
- Interviews with different stakeholders (in inglese e in spagnolo);
- Project Information for Participants (in inglese e in spagnolo);
- Modulo di consenso informato e al trattamento dati (in inglese e spagnolo).

Il Comitato Etico, con email dell'11/10/2022, ha fatto richiesta di integrazioni e modifiche alla documentazione, pervenute con email del 22/03/2022:

- Modulo di consenso informato e al trattamento dati aggiornati (in inglese e spagnolo)

Alla luce della documentazione il Comitato Etico rilascia parere favorevole alla conduzione del Progetto.

Cordiali saluti

Il Presidente del Comitato Etico
Prof. Andrea Basigalupo

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Sede Legale
Largo Francesco Vito 1, 00168 Roma
Sede Operativa
Largo Agostino Gemelli 8, 00168 Roma

Codice Fiscale e Partita IVA 13109681000

Riunione dello 06/10/2022

Membri presenti:

Prof. Andrea BACIGALUPO, *Clinico Ematologo. Presidente*
Prof.ssa Stefania BOCCIA, *Biostatistico. Vicepresidente*
Dott. Paolo Angelo BONINI, *Esperto di Bioetica*
Prof. Emilio BRIA, *Clinico - Oncologia*
Prof. Alessandro CARUSO, *Clinico - Ostetricia e Ginecologia*
Dr. Antonello COCCHIERI, *Rappresentante dell'area delle professioni sanitarie*
Dott. Alessio DE LUCA, *Farmacista SSR1*
Prof. Sebastiano FILETTI, *Clinico - Chirurgia*
Dott. Francesco FILIDORO, *Farmacista esperto di Dispositivi Medici*
Avv. Danilo GALLITELLI, *Esperto in materia giuridica e assicurativa o Medico legale*
Prof.ssa Fiorella GURRIERI, *Esperto di Genetica*
Dott. Michele LEPORE, *Medico di Medicina Generale*
Prof.ssa Giuseppina LOFFREDI, *Rappresentante del Volontariato \ Associazione Tutela Pazienti*
Prof. Camillo MARRA, *Clinico - Neurologia*
Dott.ssa Barbara MEINI, *Farmacista SSR1*
Prof.ssa Nadia MORES, *Sostituto permanente del Direttore Sanitario*
Prof. Giacomo POZZOLI, *Farmacologo*
Prof. Riccardo RICCARDI, *Pediatra*
Prof. Dario SACCHINI, *Esperto di Bioetica*
Dott. Domenico TARANTINO, *Farmacista SSR1*

Membri esterni:

Avv. Filippo E. LEONE, *Responsabile Grant Office*

Appendix 6: Approval from the Ministerio de Relaciones Internacionales (República de Cuba)

Dirección de Relaciones Internacionales

DRI- 1012

La Habana, 10 de noviembre de 2022
"Año 64 de la Revolución"

Por medio de la presente, comunicamos que el Ministerio de Educación Superior de la República de Cuba, no pone objeciones a la realización del estudio de doctorado titulado "Assessment of Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders".

Este proyecto está realizado por la Sra. Marta Busquets bajo la supervisión del Dr. Christopher Ziguras y la Dra. Jeanine Gregersen Hermans del Centro para la Internacionalización de la Educación Superior, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore en Milán, Italia.

Este estudio investiga el valor de la evaluación de los proyectos internacionales de Capacity Building en la Educación Superior para los stakeholders (actores) directos. Los dos proyectos caso de estudio son:

- Fortalecimiento del Impacto de Universidades Latinoamericanas (IMPALA)
- Fortalecimiento de las Capacidades de Gestión en Entidades Cubanas (FORGEC).

Saludos Cordiales

Dra. María Victoria Villavicencio Plasencia
Directora de Relaciones Internacionales
MES.

Appendix 7: Project information for the participants in the research

Información sobre el proyecto para los participantes

Esta entrevista forma parte de un estudio de doctorado titulado "*Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders*". Este proyecto está realizado por Marta Busquets bajo la supervisión del Dr. Christopher Ziguras y la Dra. Jeanine Gregersen Hermans del Centro para la Internacionalización de la Educación Superior, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore en Milán, Italia.

Este estudio investiga el valor de la evaluación de los proyectos internacionales de Capacity Building en la Educación Superior para las stakeholders (actores).

El objetivo de esta entrevista es comprender la visión que los diferentes stakeholders directos tienen de los procesos de evaluación de un proyecto internacional de Capacity Building en la Educación Superior.

Soy consciente de las limitaciones de su tiempo y estimo que la entrevista durará entre 30 y 45 minutos. La entrevista será grabada y transcrita. Si lo solicita, se le facilitará una transcripción de la entrevista.

Su participación en este estudio es voluntaria y sus respuestas serán anónimas. Su nombre y datos de contacto no se revelarán en el estudio final, en el que se hará referencia a usted con un seudónimo o código. Se eliminará cualquier referencia a información personal que pueda permitir a alguien intuir su identidad.

Si desea abandonar este estudio en cualquier momento, o eliminar los datos no procesados que haya proporcionado, podrá hacerlo sin ningún tipo de perjuicio.

Para cualquier otra información, pregunta o duda, este es mi contacto:

Marta Busquets
PhD Candidate
Tel. +34619082341
Email: marta.busquets@unicatt.it

Appendix 8: Consent form of the participants in the research

Titulo Investigación: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders.

Departamento/Unidad/Centro: PhD School Scienze Linguistiche e Letterarie

Documento: Hoja de información para participar en el proyecto de investigación

UNIVERSITÀ
CATTOLICA
del Sacro Cuore

HOJA DE INFORMACIÓN PARA PARTICIPAR EN EL PROYECTO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Titulo del estudio:

Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders

ORGANIZACIONES PARTICIPANTES:

.....

.....

GRUPO DE INVESTIGACIÓN:

.....

.....

Apreciado Sr / Sra

Le informamos que estamos llevando a término un estudio titulado: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and Effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders. organised by Centre for Higher Education Internationalisation (CHEI)

Por lo tanto, le proponemos que participe en el estudio, que se llevará a cabo bajo la responsabilidad Dr. Christopher Ziguras and Dra. Jeanine Gregersen Hermans.

Antes de decidir si aceptar o rechazar la oferta, por favor lea atentamente este documento. Si necesita más información o algún tipo de aclaración, por favor contacte con: DRA. Marta Busquets Calopa (cuyos detalles de contacto se recogen al final de este documento) que le dedicarán todo el tiempo que usted necesite para aclarar cualquier duda que usted pueda tener, aunque usted también puede contactar con con los operadores implicados en este estudio en cualquier momento

¿Está usted obligado a participar en este estudio?

La participación es totalmente voluntaria. Además, si en algún momento cambia de opinión y quiere retirarse del proceso de evaluación, es libre de hacerlo.

Antecedentes y objetivo del estudio

-*Objetivo:* El objetivo principal del proyecto es investigar el valor de la evaluación de los proyectos internacionales de capacity building en la educación superior para las stakeholders.

-*Diseño del estudio:* Case Studies.

-*Tiempo previsto de duración del estudio:* 3 años

-*Número de participantes:* Mínimo de 30 y máximo 42

¿Qué pasará si usted decide participar en el estudio?

El procedimiento incluye:

Participar en una entrevista abierta de una duración aproximada entre 30 y 45 minutos.

Research title: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders.

Department/Unit/Centre: PhD School Scienze Linguistiche e Letterarie

Document: Information sheet for participation in the research project

What are the possible benefits of participating in the study?

To be able to improve the evaluation processes of other projects by taking into account the expectations of direct stakeholders.

What are the possible risks/side effects of participating in the study?

None

Participation in the study

Your participation is completely free and voluntary.

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to sign the attached *Study Participation and Data Processing Consent Form* before you begin to perform the procedure foreseen by the study.

Your signature on the attached form is to ensure that you have received complete information and that you have freely expressed your willingness to participate in the study; this signature does not imply any commitment on your part to continue the study, nor does it constitute a contractual obligation or a waiver of your rights.

If you decide to withdraw from the study, after initially accepting it, you may terminate your participation at any time by notifying the person responsible for the study without having to provide a reason.

Research title: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders.

Department/Unit/Centre: PhD School Scienze Linguistiche e Letterarie

Document: Information sheet for participation in the research project

INFORMATION NOTICE ON THE PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

1. Foreword

Pursuant to Articles 13 and 14 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the "protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data" (hereinafter also "GDPR"), we provide you with the requested information on the processing of your personal data ("Data").

2. Identity and contact details of the Data Controller

The Data Controller of the processing of your Data is Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, with registered office in Largo Agostino Gemelli 1, 20123 Milan, tel. (+39) 027234.1.

3. Categories of personal data

The conduct of the study determines the processing of common data relating to you, in particular Personal Data and Contact Details, including the personal identification number that will be assigned to you upon your involvement in the study.

4. Processing purpose and legal basis

Personal data relating to you will only be processed insofar as it is indispensable in relation to the objective of the study and, in particular, for the purposes of scientific research carried out on the basis of a project which has been the subject of a reasoned favourable opinion from the competent Ethics Committee.

The legal basis for the processing is your consent, without which your participation in the study will not be possible.

5. Processing Methods

Personal data are processed manually, digitally and electronically applying logics strictly connected to the purposes and, in any case, to guarantee the security and confidentiality of the data pursuant to laws in force.

6. Data Storage Period

The Data referred to you will be processed for the time strictly needed to achieve the abovementioned purposes; with no prejudice to any storage terms established by law or regulations. **Research data are to be retained for a maximum of ten years, commencing from the day that the semi-structured interviews are scheduled.**

7. Subject Categories that the Data can be communicated to

Your data may be communicated to:

- Public bodies (ministry of education of Cuba, Colombia or Panama) or public universities whose staff is involved in the research in order to comply with legal obligations or internal regulations
- Private bodies (private universities whose staff is involved in the research) in order to comply with legal obligations or internal regulations
- Any project partners (European universities or entities, evaluators or funding bodies involved in the research) in order to comply with legal obligations or internal regulations, as well as to allow the project activities to be carried out.

Subjects belonging to the categories to which the data can be communicated will process the Data and use them, based on the case, as Processors specifically appointed by the Controller pursuant to law, or as autonomous Controllers.

The list of designated Data Processors is constantly updated and available at the University's offices.

Research title: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders.

Department/Unit/Centre: PhD School Scienze Linguistiche e Letterarie

Document: Information sheet for participation in the research project

8. Transfer of personal data to extra-EU countries

If necessary for the purposes of the study, your Data may be transferred to non-EU countries. In this case, the transfer will take place with your specific consent.

9. Data Protection Officer

The University has appointed a Data Protection Officer (D.P.O.), e-mail dpo@unicatt.it, whose name you can easily find on the website at <http://www.unicatt.it/generic-pages-privacy>.

10. Rights of the data subject

As a data subject, you have the right to:

- a) Ask the Controller to access, cancel, rectify if inaccurate, integrated if incomplete your data, and to restrict processing in cases set forth in Art. 18 of the GDPR;
- b) Object, at any time, in full or partially, to processing of Data needed for pursuance of the legitimate interest of the Controller;
- c) If the conditions for the portability right pursuant to Art. 20 of the GDPR exist, receive in a structured form, commonly used and readable with an automatic device the Data supplied to the Controller and, if technically feasible, transmit it to another Controller without hindrance;
- d) Revoke consent given at any time;
- e) Lodge a complaint with a supervisory Authority.

Those rights may be exercised by registered mail, addressed to Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Direzione Amministrativa (Office of the General Manager) - Privacy, Largo Agostino Gemelli 1, 20123, Milan, or by e-mail at dpo@unicatt.it.

For further information, clarification and communication, please contact the person responsible for the study, Ms. Marta Busquets at marta.busquets@unicatt.it or by phone at +34619082341

Thank you for your availability and cooperation

Research title: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders.

Department/Unit/Centre: PhD School Scienze Linguistiche e Letterarie

Document: Information sheet for participation in the research project

STUDY PARTICIPATION AND DATA PROCESSING CONSENT FORM

Title of the study: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and Effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders

I, the undersigned: _____

Surname and Name in capital letters of the participating adult.

born in, on: _____

Place and date of birth of the participating adult.

resident in _____, at _____

DECLARE THE FOLLOWING:

In relation to the processing of my Personal Data for the purposes indicated in the privacy information notice, i.e. scientific research activities carried out on the basis of a project, subject to a reasoned favourable opinion by the competent Ethics Commission,

I give consent I deny consent

Place and date: _____ Signature: _____

In relation to the transfer of my Personal Data to non-EU countries for purposes strictly related to the performance of the study, within the limits and in the modalities indicated in the privacy information notice,

I give consent I deny consent

Place and date: _____ Signature: _____

I FURTHER DECLARE THE FOLLOWING:

1. I have read and understood the information sheet of which this form is an integral part;
2. I had the opportunity to ask questions and seek explanations from **Ms. Marta Busquets** and received satisfactory answers;
3. I was informed about the nature, purpose and duration of the study, the procedures that will be followed, the treatment of the participants and the type of cooperation that will be required of them;

Research title: Assessment of International Capacity Building Projects in Higher Education: Value and effectiveness for Direct Stakeholders.

Department/Unit/Centre: PhD School Scienze Linguistiche e Letterarie

Document: Information sheet for participation in the research project

4. I understand that participation in the study is free and voluntary and that at any time I may decide to withdraw / withdraw the person I represent from the study without being in any way exposed to adverse consequences and without my / their rights and my / their relationship with the staff involved being compromised;

In the light of the above, I hereby agree to participate in the study described in this document.

Place and date: _____ Signature: _____

